

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product

GA NUMBER: 730456

Demonstration results of the furniture and building products

Document Information

Report name	Demonstration results of the furniture and building products
Version number	3.0
Document number	D4.6
Due date for deliverable	30/11/2021
Actual submission date	30/11/2021
Lead beneficiary	CONENOR

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 730456

Document Control page

Author	Markku Vilkki (CONENOR)
Version number	v2.1
Date	29-11-2021
Modified by	Markku Vilkki
Comments	
Status	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Draft <input type="checkbox"/> Accepted
Action requested	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Submitted Deadline for action: 30-11-2021

Revision History

Version	Date	Author/Reviewer	Notes
v1.0	10.11.2021	Markku Vilkki	draft v1.0
v2.0	26.11.2021	Giovanni Tosi	Furniture
v2.0	26.11.2021	Ajith Aluvihare Gedara Cranfield University	Construction Disassembly
v2.1	29.11.2021	Giovanni Tosi	Furniture
V3	30.11.2021	Eva Urbano / Victor Martinez (UPC)	Corrections and formatting

Executive Summary

The aim of ECOBULK project is to develop circular innovative solutions within three sectors: automotive, furniture and construction. This document provides the report regarding the demonstration results of furniture and construction building products from the work performed under WP4. The information comes from the demo site findings, concerning construction, assembly, disassembly, joining, integrity, applicability and use of the furniture and building products in several European countries and in both harsh cold northern and sunny warm southern climate conditions.

The validation of manufactured and re-manufactured products for demonstrating the modularity and the reuse/recovery/recycle of products is presented, as well as the feasibility of the processes with respect to disassembling and dismantling practices.

In furniture focus has been very much in validating the new products of Moretti Compact vs. existing European standards and gaining user perception while in construction building products of Conenor containing GFRP-waste such standards do not exist and therefore focus has been in experimental field work gaining first experiences and learning by doing adequate practices "fit for purpose" in different structural assembly designs.

Covid-19 pandemic has resulted physical problems for the execution of field works at all demo sites and caused notable delays to keep with the project time tables. Therefore, the ½ year extension to original 4y. project duration was seen necessary and has allowed the demos to become realised just before the end of the project.

For the furniture sector, the main focus of the activity was on prototypes designed by Moretti Compact and on the binders developed by project partners AkzoNobel, KEAS and Cranfield. Prototypes were manufactured and tested according to international standards and end-user requirements, and they were also dis-assembled and re-assembled in demo sites in order to evaluate the effective feasibility of these two processes and with the objective to promote the extension of its lifespan. Before prototypes deployment, a preliminary evaluation was conducted on different pieces of furniture made of wood panels already in commerce with the aim to have a baseline for comparison. Also, tests on products developed with the innovative binders have been performed to evaluate its suitability for the designed products. These activities have served as inputs for WP7 analysis (LCA, LCC, S-LCA, CBA). Feedback was collected from demo sites under the technical point of view in terms of its ease to manage and assemble/disassemble. The collection of end-user feedback is also possible through the software system developed in WP6 which includes datasheets and questionnaires of the deployed prototypes. All these activities were useful to suggest several requirements about methods to dis-assembly and re-assembly furniture, beyond the concrete definition of the features for a product to be considered as dis-assemblable and re-assemblable; the goal is to have furniture easy to repair and/or refurbish, as well as reusable and recoverable before than recyclable,

since this characteristic is already amply achieved especially for wood-based products.

For the construction sector, the building product demonstrations are realised and located in four European countries; Finland, UK, France and Portugal and with/by their responsible demo owners KymiRing, three universities Warwick/Coventry/Cranfield, FCBA and Lipor. Each demo owner has made their own choice and design for their constructions, partly with help of external design offices/architects, and the use of extrusion components developed and made available by Conenor in Finland. In the UK the gazebo type shelter constructed by the three universities had been designed by Exergy, the original Ecobulk project coordinator who left the consortium. External third party contractors have been used by the demo owners of their choice during the construction phase at demo sites. The main issue in all the Ecobulk building demos is the new Conenor invented agglomeration technique to utilise thermoset GFRP-waste as reinforcement in recycled and virgin thermoplastic materials and products. The extruded recycled composite products/components used in building demonstrations and including their materials have been developed, produced and supplied by Conenor. Testing and characterization of Conenor produced recycled composite material samples have been done in WP3 by CNR in Italy and thereafter in WP4 with the actual products/components used by Warwick University to ensure their applicability "fit for purpose" in structural applications like shelters. Additional technical information and product characteristics vs. some commonly used bench marking products was obtained in a master thesis organised by Conenor together with the University of Easter Finland (UEF). Dismantling case for a structure with building products has been realised in the UK by Cranfield University which provides the project valuable information on how easy it is to disassemble such a structure and recover the non-damaged composites for second use. Recycling case with building products was realised by collecting rest pieces after construction works from two different demo sites; PE-based recycled composites from KymiRing in Finland and PP-based recycled composites from Lipor in Portugal. Collected rest pieces were downsized into small particles in a shredder and new test specimens produced by Conenor using the recovered materials for CNR lab testing and characterization. The study shows the materials are recyclable several times and can be used again and again despite of minor decrease in properties. Compounding experiments and proof of processing with Conenor produced GFRP-waste containing agglomerates into dust free granules was done successfully by Aimplas in Spain using four different material basis and both with manufacturing and end of life wind turbine blade GFRP-waste.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Executive Summary	3
1. Introduction.....	7
1.1. Description of the document.....	7
1.2. WPs and Tasks related with the deliverable	7
2. Furniture	11
2.1. Experimental evaluation of particleboard performances with new compositions	11
2.1.1. Objective	11
2.1.2. Material and method.....	11
2.1.3. Results	16
2.1.4. Conclusion.....	19
2.2. Manufacturing and tests on panels and products.....	20
2.2.1. Particle boards tests	20
2.3. Prototype manufacturing: laboratory tests	32
2.3.1. Laboratory tests on desk.....	33
2.3.2. Laboratory tests on chair.....	34
2.3.3. Laboratory tests on library	36
2.3.4. Laboratory test on bed.....	37
2.3.5. Laboratory test on little cabinet.....	38
2.4. Furniture assembly and disassembly	39
2.4.1. Traditional furniture assembly and disassembly evaluation ..	39
2.4.2. ECOBULK prototypes: rating grids	62
2.4.3. ECOBULK prototypes: dis-and re-assembling tests	70
2.5. Non-wovens in sofa.....	75
2.5.1. Visual perception.....	76
2.5.2. Touch perception.....	78
2.5.3. Comfort perception.....	81
2.5.4. Conclusions on sofas.....	88
3. Construction	90
3.1. Recycled GFRP-waste composite materials and product manufacturing	90
3.1.1. GFRP-waste reinforced thermoplastic materials	90
3.1.2. Conenor agglomeration manufacturing technology	92
3.1.3. Extrusion of multilayer composite building products.....	94
3.2. KymiRing demonstrator, Finland	99

3.2.1.	Outdoor Visitor Benches	100
3.2.2.	Flagman Shelters	101
3.3.	UK universities demonstrators	105
3.3.1.	Gazebo type shelter design.....	105
3.3.2.	Warwick University demo site	106
3.3.3.	Cranfield University demo site	114
3.3.4.	Coventry University demo site	127
3.4	LIPOR demonstrator, Portugal	151
3.3.5.	Material and parts sourcing	151
3.3.6.	Design	152
3.3.7.	Preparation.....	154
3.3.8.	Installation and assembling	154
3.3.9.	Use phase and questionnaire	161
3.4.	FCBA demonstrator, France.....	164
3.4.1.	Outdoor Benches and Seats.....	164
3.4.2.	Wall Module.....	182
3.5.	Compounding at Aimplas, SPAIN.....	217
3.5.1.	Introduction	217
3.5.2.	Conenor agglomerates compounded into granules with 35%-w. GFRP-waste.....	218
3.6.	Recycling and Circularity of Building Products	220
3.6.1.	Re-manufacturing recovered materials from demo sites	220
3.6.2.	Characterization of re-manufactured composite materials by CNR	221
4.	Conclusions and Recommendations	224
4.1.	Furniture	224
4.2.	Construction.....	225
Appendix A: Tables from FCBA test on particle boards.....		228
Appendix B: Structural study on the UK shelter design		234

1. Introduction

1.1. Description of the document

This document provides a report regarding the demonstration results of furniture and building products obtained from the work performed under WP4. The information provided has been derived from the demo site results, concerning among others recycling and recovery strategies for the products. The validation of manufactured and re-manufactured products for demonstrating the circularity and recycling of products is analysed, as well as the feasibility in technical terms of the processes and the differences with respect to common disassembling and dismantling practices.

1.2. WPs and Tasks related with the deliverable

WP4 Demonstration Activities- 'Circular Designed Products Validation:(re-) manufacturing process and product/material circularity

This work package focuses on demonstrating circular designed solutions, which in this case covers the furniture and building product industry, with regards to the manufacturing and re-manufacturing of improved products, following the circular framework developed in **WP2 "Design framework for the three Circular product sectors"** and developing and employing novel manufacturing technologies such as agglomeration with recycled GFRP-waste, compounding and multilayer extrusions.

To meet these outcomes, circular designed building products have been manufactured at Conenor in Finland and showcased at four demo sites in different climate conditions in Finland, UK, France and Portugal, adequate polymer base and waste materials fractions together with functional additives have been identified to be incorporated in new developed manufacturing technologies, materials circularity thru recovering rest pieces from two different demos sites and recycling and re-manufacturing and as well the disassembly and dismantling processes have been analysed to validate and demonstrate the design strategies. Furniture prototypes have also been designed following circularity design guidelines provided by WP2 and have been manufactured and assembled/disassembled at demo sites. Tests on products with the new design and on products with the new binder low-formaldehyde solutions have been carried out to test its feasibility.

D4.1 – Report on the (re-) manufacture of the innovative composite products. This report collects all the relevant aspects related to the manufacture and re-manufacture of the composite-based products and how the materials developed in WP3 have been manufactured into components and then reclaimed and re-manufactured. Several prototype samples have been developed. Among other composite materials analysed, prototype samples for building applications realized by Conenor have effectively incorporated high fractions of recovered materials.

D4.2 – Report on the (re-) manufacture of the innovative wood based products. This report collects all the relevant aspects related to the

manufacture and re-manufacture of the wood based products. This report exposes the mechanical performance of the newly developed particle boards with the low-formaldehyde binder developed in WP3 and its re-manufacturability.

D4.4 Demonstration plans for activities at DEMO SITES: User involvement This report presents initially planned activities with end users on demonstrating Ecobulk circular solutions and how to contribute to “closing the loop” of products in three sectors; automotive, furniture and building by promoting greater re-use, upgrade, refurbishment and recycle of products, parts, and materials.

WP3 - Material development/conditioning for circular designed products

Material to be employed in WP4 has been created and characterised in WP3. This includes composite materials which have been used both in the construction and automotive sectors (Netcomposites, Tecnar, Conenor), nonwoven materials which have been used both in the furniture and automotive sectors (NTT, Technoplants), and new binders which have been used for particle board manufacturing in the furniture sector (KEAS, Cranfield, AkzoNobel). These developments are reflected in the deliverables D3.1 “Report on development of the intermediate materials for composite production”, D3.2 “Report on development of nonwovens intermediate products”, and D3.3 “Report on validation of sustainable binder systems”.

Conenor has also developed in WP3 its innovative and patented agglomeration process technique and tailored mixing equipment to utilise thermoset GFRP-waste as reinforcement in thermoplastic polymers (e.g. PE and PP), both recycled and virgin. Such reinforced polymer material mixtures in over 50 formulations have been developed and tested and analysed by CNR and results used to make appropriate choices what to use in WP4 multilayer building demo products’ “fit for purpose” design and manufacturing in varying climate conditions both hot under sunshine in south-Europe and freezing cold in north-Europe.

WP7 - Life Cycle Thinking for the circular designed products

WP7 is related with this deliverable through two aspects: life cycle analysis and Environmental Technology Verification (ETV).

FCBA in France has carried out work with the aim of which is to validate the environmental performance and claims of ECOBULK solutions through the ETV scheme. The objective of an ETV is to promote environmental technologies by providing technology developers, manufacturers and investors access to third-party validation of the performance of innovative environmental technologies. Technology proposed for ETV is Conenor invented agglomeration process for manufacturing new circular raw materials from recycled and waste feedstock materials; and followed by extruded single- and multilayer products (e.g. planks and panels) thereof for the building and construction industry. The technology has been proposed for ETV due to its ability of recycling complex polymeric waste e.g. fibre reinforced

composites (GFRP) and construction & demolition waste (wood, wool insulations) by manufacturing into new circular raw materials to improve the materials efficiency, as well as their sustainability. However, ETV is not the only solution to valorise what has been developed by the company. Environmental Production Declaration is an independently verified and registered document that communicates transparent and comparable information about the life-cycle environmental impact of products. Benchmark of different EPD database show very few cladding solutions involving the recycling of post-consumer waste. EPD appears to be a solution to valorise the environmental performance of the recycled composite building products developed by Conenor. The work and outcome of this aspect is described in the deliverable D7.3 "Environmental technology verification (ETV)".

Regarding life cycle analysis, the work carried out in WP4 in the construction and furniture sectors are the basis for the development of WP7 analysis including Mass-Flow Analysis (MFA), Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Life Cycle Cost (LCC), Social LCA (S-LCA), and Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA). The outcomes of these analysis can be consulted in deliverables D7.1 "Design and optimisation of the whole Circular Supply Chain", D7.2 "Life Cycle Assessment and Life Cycle Costs", D7.4 "Cost-Benefit analysis", and D7.5 "Socio-economic ethical and cultural repercussions study".

WP8 - Business Planning and Exploitation of Results

D8.1: Comprehensive analysis of the 3 business cases - developed from task T8.4 - covers the business cases for the demonstration products developed by the three sectors within ECOBULK. The case studies are aligned with the demonstrations selected for consideration within task T8.1, the development of value chains and business models. These demonstrators are:

- Moretti – design for disassembly to ease repair and a proposed leasing model for furniture;
- Microcab - design for disassembly to support product life extension and a leasing business model; and
- Conenor - using waste GFRP as reinforcing feedstock in producing new raw materials for outdoor construction and building products.

T8.1 will provide inputs regarding the linear (baseline) and circular value chains, as well as circular business models that are being developed together with the industrial partners. T8.4 will also receive inputs from demonstration activities in WP4 regarding the technical tests and user acceptance tests performed in this WP. D8.1 pulls together details from the development of the materials, products, and value chains, as well as the assessments undertaken of these.

WP9 - Communication and Dissemination Strategies

A formal planning document for using and disseminating knowledge throughout the project results has been developed by KNEIA and ISWA in

WP9 once the intellectual property has been protected. The developments carried out in WP4 have been an importance source of material for communication and dissemination. Communications and publications have been performed dealing with prototypes development, characterisation, disassembly, etc. Conenor invented novel low cost and environmentally friendly agglomeration process for utilisation of thermoset GFRP-waste as reinforcement in thermoplastic materials and products was granted a worldwide patent and put valid in Europe, USA, Canada and China by Conenor. For this reason, the Dissemination and Communication Plan will fulfil obligations to the European Commission on communication and also have the widest possible impact to facilitate the take-up of the new technologies.

2. Furniture

2.1. Experimental evaluation of particleboard performances with new compositions

2.1.1. Objective

Two main issues were focused on, related to board performances in order to:

- Evaluate the impact of recycled wood proportion
- Evaluate the impacts of various adhesives

2.1.2. Material and method

Material

Resins

- Commercial Urea formaldehyde resin (Ref UF): It was a solid resin delivered by Dynea, ref Aerolite UP4116. It was solubilised in water a 60% of dry matter content. No other additive was considered.
- Experimental resin (Ref C): It was used based on the recommendation of WP4 deliverable - month 22, non-formaldehyde systems from Cranfield. Components used were:
 - Alignic acid sodium salt, from Roth, solid, to be mixed with particles
 - Wheat protein, from Manito, solid, to be mixed with particles
 - Sodium hydroxide, from Roth, to be sprayed onto particles once solubilized
- Experimental resin (Ref A): It was delivered from Akzo Nobel industry and is a resin under development.
 - A1 to A3 refers to kronel 19007
 - A4 to A4 refers to Nary 19007

Virgin particles

They were delivered by an industrial mill facility.

Specific care was taken in order to get particle made exclusively of Roundwood, free of recycled wood. They are mainly issue from Norway Spruce.

A quantity of 24kg of fine particles and 64 kg of coarse large ones was delivered to FCBA.

Figure 1: Picture of the virgin fine and coarse particles

Figure 2: Picture of the recycled coarse particles

Particles issue from recycled wood

They were issue from two industrial mill facilities and concerned internal layer only made of coarse particles. Material considered fit with the requests from the legislation in term of chemical composition and possible contaminants.

A quantity of 24kg of fine particles and 64 kg of coarse was delivered to FCBA.

Method

Constitution of the mixes

Six different mixes of particles were considered depending on their origin.

For each adhesive solution, the 6 following conditions were explored:

- | | |
|-------------------------|---|
| • 100% virgin particles | 0 % particles recycled in internal layer |
| • 80% virgin particles | 20% particles recycled in internal layer |
| • 60% virgin particles | 40% particles recycled in internal layer |
| • 40% virgin particles | 60% particles recycled in internal layer |
| • 20% virgin particles | 80% particles recycled in internal layer |
| • 0% virgin particles | 100% particles recycled in internal layer |

Gluing

A separate gluing stage was considered depending on the type of elements to be sprayed, amount of resin was adapted to the size of particles.

Particles and other solid materials (for experimental resin only) were introduced into gluing equipment. A rotating arm homogenised the solid during liquid was sprayed onto particles using spraying nozzle.

Figure 3: Gluing installation

Figure 4: Rotating arm and material of the project

Amount of liquid to be introduced was defined before starting mixing.

- Gluing with UF and other systems: Fine elements were glued at 10% whereas coarse elements were glued at 7% by UF resin.
- Gluing with experimental resin – Referred as Cranfield: Particles, which ever their dimension, were mixed with solid resin components at a dry wood particles to dry powder ratio as 65:35 (w/w). Powder was made of wheat gluten and sodium alginate at a ratio of 84 / 13. Sodium hydroxide dissolved into water was sprayed onto particles mixed with solid additives. Amount was set for moisture content of the final mixture to be 18% and final ratio of additive to be: sodium hydroxide / wheat gluten / sodium alginate at a ratio of 3 / 84 / 13 by weight.

Manufacturing of board

Boards were made of 3 layers:

- 2 external layers made of fine elements, each of layer representing 1/6 of board
- 1 internal layer made of coarse elements, representing 2/3 of board

Glued fine particles were laid into mould, then coarse ones, and finally fine particle finished board surface as described in Figure 5.

Figure 5: The different steps of board manufacturing

a/ Fine particle bottom layer; b/coarse particle internal layer; c/fine particle top layer; d/ board in the mold; e/ board before entering the press

Once all material was arranged to fit with the objective of density 600kg/m³, next step was pressing.

Pressing

Pressing was performed on the equipment presented in Figure 6. Material was introduced in the opened heating press and 21 mm thick iron plates disposed on the sides to fix final board thickness.

Figure 6: FCBA wood based board press facility

A pressing cycle was used as described in the next table, plate temperature was set at 200°C.

Cycle	Pressure on board (bar)	Time (s)
1	3	12
2	25	45
3	47	140
4	14	180
5	5	30
6	3	30
7	2	30
8	1	30

Table 1: Pressing cycle

Pressing time was long as the objective was to obtain qualitative boards to be tested and evaluate the impacts of particle composition and adhesive solution. If a minimised pressing time was to be set, this would require a separate protocol.

A total of 34 news boards was produced during the second period.

Characterisations

The following measurements were proceeded by:

- Determination of humidity according to standard NF EN 322 of June 1993
- Determination of density according to standard NF EN 323 of June 1993
- Determination of the swelling in thickness after immersion in water for 24 hours according to standard NF EN 317 of June 1993
- Determination of the tensile strength perpendicular to the faces of the panel according to standard NF EN 319 of June 1993
- Determination of flexural modulus of elasticity and flexural strength according to standard NF EN 310 of June 1993

These tests are prescribed by standard NF EN 622-5 of December 2009: Fiber boards - Requirements - Part 5: requirements for panels obtained by dry process (MDF).

For all the tests, the specimens were cut according to the methodology of standard NF EN 326-1 of June 1994 relating to sampling, cutting of specimens and the expression of the test results. However, due to the small size of the samples received, the number of test pieces was limited.

After cutting, the specimens are conditioned to a constant mass at 20°C and 65% RH before testing.

2.1.3.Results

The tests related to 2 batches of 6 particles boards received at the “Tests and Simulations Laboratory”.

An analysis of the results is proposed on the basis of a graphical representation of the individual values (grey circles) and the average value (blue circle) framed by its 95% confidence interval for each of the characteristics measured. It allows to highlight absence or existence of significant differences between each configuration of panels tested.

References from C1 to C6 are related to experimental resin application.

A1 to A6 are related to experimental Akzo resin Reference A1 to A3 are referred to increasing ratios of recycled elements, but similar bonding system. Reference A4 to A6 are referred to increasing ratios of recycled elements, but similar bonding system

UF1 to UF6 are related to reference urea-formaldehyde resin. For these, initial letter, S or E, refers to 2 origins of recycle particles. Numbers UF are related to amount of recycled material, from 0 (sample 1) up to 100% (sample 6).

Figure 7: Swelling in thickness after 24h immersion in water acc. to EN 317

Swelling in thickness was impacted by the adhesive system: Cranfield solution was the one the most performant for limiting water absorption. Then, UF systems presented higher values, but still lower than 50%. It was not possible to identify any impact of the ratio of recycled elements in the particle furnish for both these adhesives system. Regarding references A, an impact

of resinification system was observed: A1 to A3 presented lower water resistance compared to A4 to A6. This last was as performant as UF systems. Finally, for both "A" resins an important impact of particle origin was observed: the more the virgin particles, the more the swelling. As a consequence, it seemed recycled particles could be beneficial for limiting tendency of boards to swell in water.

Origin of recycled particles did not impact on board quality.

Figure 8: Modulus of rupture acc. to EN 310

Bending strength differences were large but not significant, whichever the conditions applied. Some trends could however be commented. Indeed, exploring system, ref C showed the highest performances. In this case, there was no impact of particle furnish.

Considering A references, low values were measured for ref A1 to A3. This highlighted lower performance of resin and negative impact of introducing recycled particles. Similar trend was observed in the cases of A4 to A6 and UF bonded systems. This confirmed the impact of the particle sourcing, more than the resin.

These trends are in accordance with past experience which showed bending properties to be more impacted by stratification than bonding systems.

Figure 9: Modulus of elasticity in bending acc. to EN 310

Modulus of elasticity in bending was impacted by the type of resin applied: Cranfield based resin presented the best performance. Only for these, no impact of recycled particle proportions could be identified, whereas for other bonding systems, the more the recycled particles, the less the bending strength. Impact of recycled particles origin was none.

As previously mentioned, impact of external faces properties is high, compared to internal one. Consequently, the type of particles used for the layer could have a limited impact in the case of resins presenting high performances, as mentioned here with Cranfield system.

Figure 10: Internal Bond Strength acc. to EN 319

This new series of tests made possible to reach valuable level of internal bond strength. This was not the case in the previous period, justifying this new campaign.

Hence, internal Bond Strength were low in the case of Cranfield system and A1 to A3. These last references confirmed the low potential of this resin to produce suitable boards.

For A4 to A6 and other UF systems, an impact of particle origin was observed as the higher the reference number, the higher the proportion of recycled particles in the furnish and the lower the internal bond strength. This confirmed the impact of particle sourcing.

2.1.4. Conclusion

The aim of these experiments was to evaluate the performance of particleboard according to two parameters: the rate of wood recycled content incorporated in the particle board and the type of adhesive used, two of them being adhesives developed by the partners of the project ECOBULK, Cranfield University and Akzo Nobel.

The experiment was conducted in different steps depending on the availability of the resins.

In total, more than 50 particleboards of 50x50 cm were produced at a laboratory scale on which were conducted five different tests to evaluate

characteristics such as humidity, density, swelling, tensile strength and flexural modulus.

The origin of the particles (virgin or recycled) influences in some cases the properties of the board depending on the glue used. When it was observed, recycled particles impacted negatively the mechanical performances, whereas in the case of water swelling it was beneficial. Since the behavior of virgin wood particles is different from that of recycled wood particles, the latter have undergone an additional heat treatment and sizing step.

Comparing the 4 resins tested (2 from Akzo Nobel), different behaviours were highlighted. Considering experimental solutions, one was not efficient, the other more, comparable to UF traditional systems in some extent.

2.2. Manufacturing and tests on panels and products.

In this section the manufacturing process of the furniture prototypes is exposed together with the tests carried out. This include the manufacturing of particle boards as well as the manufacturing of the designed ECOBULK prototype.

2.2.1. Particle boards tests

In order to characterise the behaviour of the panel in a standard situation, tests were conducted as if the panels were used as a shelf component.

Material and method

Tests are realized according NF EN 16122:2012, §6.14 with:

- Load = 1,5kg/dm²
- Climate conditions: Temperature = 23°; Humidity = 50%

The test is usually conducted to quantify the shelf deformation subjected to a standard distributed load. The samples were placed on cleat in the unit. The shelves are loaded uniformly with 1kg parallelepiped mass with load specified above (see figure 1). Deflection of the shelf was measured at a point 10mm from the edge where the deflection is the greatest. For this specific test measures were made at t₀ and at several moments in order to follow the deformation against time until T_{final}= 7 days.

Figure 11: Distributed load on shelf (from Afnor)

Samples and experimental setup preparation

Initial samples were divided in two part to double the measurement data. Each part from the same sample was named "A" and "B". For example the two part of cranfield 1 is now cranfield 1A et cranfield 1B.

Figure 12: Initial sample Cranfield 1

Figure 13: Cutting of samples

	Cranfield sample	UF Sample
Dimensions	467 x 228 x 18mm	467 x 228 x 20mm

Table 2: Panel dimensions.

During the test each of this part were placed on a column which is put on the floor and attached to the wall. Sample are put on 4 metal plate cleats. In order to get repeatable tests all these cleats have a specific position in the furniture and the position of the shelf front the front of the column is controlled before each test.

Figure 14: Empty column (left) and fully column with 3 samples at the same time (right)

Figure 15: Shelf and cleat positioning

Repartition of the distributed loaded and measurement point of deformation are the same for each sample.

Figure 16: Point of deformation and distributed load

Results

Results of the first batch of particleboards

Evaluation of deformation

As we can see for these 2 sets of data below (Cranfield A and UF A), there is a significant variation of deformation between the maximum variation (Cranfield 4A and UF 6) and the minimum observed variation (Cranfield 6A and UF3). This variation is more than 50% for Cranfield A. Moreover there is a significant variation too between Cranfield A and UF (difference of the mean = 53%). This could mean that on average the flexural rigidity of the Cranfield A panel is around 50% higher than UF when panels are use as shelves.

However, due to low deformation in absolute value and the precision of measurement in a laboratory environment for this type of measurement, early conclusion should be taken with care.

To replace this measurement on standard furniture context, requirement for this test is that the shelf must not deform by more than 1% (from NF EN 16121, collective furniture). For Cranfield A and UF we are well below from this requirement (0,32% and 0,49% respectively).

Figure 17: Evolution of the shelf deformation for Cranfield samples in the first phase of testing

Mean Cranfield A (mm)	1,51	
Max (mm)	Cranfield 1,86	(Cranfield 4A)
Min (mm)	Cranfield 1,2	(Cranfield 6A)
Difference max/min	55%	

Table 3: Results of the shelf deformation for Cranfield samples in the first phase of testing

Figure 18: Evolution of the shelf deformation for UF samples in the first phase of testing

Mean UF	2,31
Max UF (mm)	2,84 UF 6
Min UF (mm)	2 UF 3
Difference max/min	42%

Table 4: Results of the shelf deformation for UF samples in the first phase of testing

As we can see for Cranfield B results, the mean is slightly the same as for Cranfield A. However, in details min and max deformation are exactly the opposite as measured in Cranfield 4 samples. That confirm that we cannot conclude about the performance of panel use as shelf in the same set.

To improve the methodology we considered that wider sample (ie x2 or x3 of the existent sample) could be more appropriate to have significant results.

Figure 19: Evolution of the shelf deformation for Cranfield samples in the second phase of testing

Mean Cranfield B	1,48
Max (mm)	Cranfield 6B 1,68
Min (mm)	Cranfield 4B 1,2
Difference max/min	40%

Table 5: Results of the shelf deformation for Cranfield samples in the second phase of testing

Humidity and shelf performance

In a second phase, we wanted to qualify the impact of humidity on shelf performance. The procedure of the test is the same as before except that we put the panel for 5 days at a humidity level of 85%. After 5 days, the samples are placed for 1 day at a humidity level of 50%.

Six samples were tested and compared with samples without specific humidity procedure

Figure 20: Results of second testing phase with humidity modification

As we can see on these charts, the humidity procedure described before has an important impact of the deformation after 7 days of load. What is significant here is that the evolution, ie the difference between deformation at t0 and Tfinal, is much higher for samples with 5 days 85% humidity.

We can conclude that even deformation at T0 is slightly higher for 85% humidity sample; the major impact of humidity on shelf is for 7 days load.

Results of the second batch of particleboards

Evaluation of deformation

During the project, a second batch a particleboards was received to follow the same protocol.

Figure 21: Evolution of deformation of UF samples – second batch

Mean UF	2,57	
Max UF (mm)	2,99	UF 1
Min UF (mm)	2,35	UF 4
Difference max/min	27%	

Table 6: Results of deformation for UF samples

Figure 22: Evolution of deformation of Nary samples

Mean Nary	2,28	
Max Nary (mm)	2,44	Nary 1A
Min Nary (mm)	2,06	Nary 1B
Difference max/min	18 %	

Table 7: Results of deformation for Nary samples

	NARY sample
Dimensions	467 x 228 x 16mm

Table 8: Dimensions for Nary samples

As we can see for these 2 sets of data (UF and Nary), there is a variation of deformation between the maximum variation (UF1 and Nary 1A) and the minimum observed variation (UF4 and Nary 1B). This variation is the highest for UF (27%). The difference of the mean deformation of both UF and Nary is equal to 13%. However, the thickness of the NARY sample is significantly smaller than UF sample (16mm vs 20mm). This dimension have an impact on flexural deformation. Even if early conclusion should be taken with care due to low deformation in absolute value and the precision of measurement in a laboratory environment for this type of measurement, we can say that flexural rigidity of NARY sample is higher than flexural rigidity of UF sample.

To replace this measurement on standard furniture context, requirement for this test is that the shelf must not deform by more than 1% (from NF EN 16121, collective furniture). For Nary and UF we are well below from this requirement (0,55% and 0,48% respectively).

Figure 23: Evolution of deformation for Cranfield samples

Mean Cranfield	1,22
Max Cranfield (mm)	1,41
Min Cranfield (mm)	1,03
Difference max/min	37 %

Table 9: Results of deformation for Cranfield samples

The mean deformation is lower than the other two samples, the difference of the mean deformation of Cranfield and UF is equal to 111%, and nary is equal to 87%. However, the difference between min and max is higher than the other samples. According to the notice about measurement precision, this is not a surprised that percent difference is higher than for UF and Nary.

To replace this measurement on standard furniture context, requirement for this test is that the shelf must not deform by more than 1% (from NF EN 16121, collective furniture). For Cranfield we are well below from this requirement (0.26%).

Despite the precautions of the measurement, we notice that the trend of these tests are the same as before. The panel made the resin developed by Cranfield University appear to have higher flexural rigidity than the other two samples.

Conclusion

During the project ECOBULK, different samples of panels were made at a laboratory scale in FCBA's facilities, with different rates of recycled wood and different types of resins.

On this second part of tests run to evaluate the usability of panels for furniture use, the panels made with the resin from Cranfield University were compared to panels made with convention resins. It was not possible to run similar tests on the panels using the resins from Akzo Nobel due the late delivery of the resin.

The first results show that, as a first approximation, UF sample show the lowest bending stiffness of the three sample. At the first batch, the difference of the mean deformation between UF and Cranfield was about 53% and for the second batch, this difference was about 111%. Moreover this difference was nearly the same for NARY and UF whereas NARY sample thickness is 4mm less UF thickness. Thickness is supposed to have a significant impact on flexural deformation that is not the case here.

It is difficult to compare the flexural behaviour between UF and NARY sample because of the difference of thickness sample and the difference on measurement.

If we only take into account the performance standard requirements NF EN 16121 for collective furniture, all of those samples are in accordance with deformation requirements. It is the case for those dimensions. We are not able to extrapolate to bigger dimensions and we advise to do these tests with higher shelf dimensions.

We can also conclude that humidity have a real impact on shelf deformation, above all the shelf deformation after 7 days. This is especially true given that these panel have no surface finish.

2.3. Prototype manufacturing: laboratory tests

Before evaluating the possibility to assemble and disassemble Ecobulk prototypes developed by Moretti Compact, an important activity is related to the validation according to international technical standards, since they are the result of an innovation project and they are new products not put on the market yet. The objective is directly related to the general aim of the project: through the laboratory evaluation, it's important to demonstrate the quality of products and then to ensure a long-life duration, one of the main prerequisites of circularity. The long-life duration can be also guaranteed through an emotional durability: simple lines and shapes as well as neutral colors were defined with this scope. However, the quality of furniture is a more relevant aspect to be kept into account in order to have a life as much long as possible.

In detail, the different elements were tested in COSMOB, a qualified laboratory for furniture sector located in Italy and accredited according to ISO/IEC 17025:2018.

2.3.1. Laboratory tests on desk

The technical reference kept into account for the desk is UNI EN 12521:2016 - Furniture - Strength, durability and safety - Requirements for domestic tables. Probably the desk is the most critical products, since the producer had to make some implementations in order to improve the ergonomic as well as the mechanical resistance of the work top, duly modified after consideration about comfort of the end user. Here below the test results are summarized in tables as reported in official test reports.

Figure 24: Ecobulk prototype: Desk

Under the technical point of view, safety requirements were successfully evaluated as reported in following table.

Safety requirements	Result
The edges of the table tops which are directly in contact with the user are rounded or chamfered. All other edges accessible during use shall be free from burrs and / or sharp edges.	Successful
It shall not be possible for any load bearing part of the table to come loose unintentionally.	Successful
There shall be no shear and squeeze points created by forces applied during normal use, see Table 2.	Successful
There shall be no shear and squeeze points if a hazard is created by the user during normal movements and actions, e.g. attempting to move the table.	Successful

Table 10: Desk safety requirements.

A second aspect is related to stability and then to the possibility to overturn: after the test duly described in following table, the sample does not tip over.

Application point	Nominal vertical force	Results
50 mm from the external edge of the table top	375 N	Successful

As described above, the mechanical resistance was one of the main challenge for the desk, thus horizontal and vertical static load was applied according to the specification reported respectively here below.

Force application side	Nominal horizontal force (N)	Nominal vertical mass (kg)	Cycles	Results
Side 1-2	400	50	10	Successful
Side 3-4	250	50	10	Successful

Height of the table (MM)	Nominal vertical force (N)	Force application point	Cycles	Results
>600	1000	Most unfavourable point, but not less than 100 mm from the edges	10	Successful

The last test carried out on desk, is the horizontal durability, by applying an horizontal force while a vertical mass is positioned on the worktop.

Force application side	Minimum nominal horizontal force (N)	Nominal vertical mass (kg)	Cycles	Results
Side a-b	300	50	10000	Successful
Side c-d	150	50	10000	Successful

Table 11: Desk mechanical stability

2.3.2.Laboratory tests on chair

Even for the chair, many evaluations were done according to the main technical standard to be taken into account: UNI EN 12520:2016 Furniture - Strength, durability and safety - Requirements for domestic seating. Considering that the chair is a product composed generally by a seat and a backrest, forces and loads are applied on these different parts and the tests seem a little bit more complex than other furniture products such as cabinets and tables.

Figure 25: Ecobulk prototype: Chair under test

All the mechanical tests are duly reported in following tables demonstrating the positive results in addition to the fact the sample is stable and does not overturn.

Safety requirements:

Safety requirements	Result
a) the edges of the seat, the backrest and the armrests which are in contact with the user when sitting are rounded or chamfered;	Successful
b) all other edges accessible during use shall be free of burrs and / or sharp edges;	Successful
It shall not be possible for any load bearing part of the seating to come loose unintentionally.	Successful
There shall be no shear and squeeze points created by loads applied during normal use.	Successful
Shear and squeeze points are not acceptable if a hazard is created by the weight of the user during normal movements and actions, e.g. attempting to move the seating by lifting the seat by or adjusting the backrest.	Successful

Table 12: Chair safety requirements.

Static load test on back and seat:

Nominal force to be applied on seat (N)	Nominal force to be applied on back (N)	Nominal minimum force to be applied on seat (N)	Nominal minimum force to be applied on back (N)	Number of cycles	Results
1300	450	410	410	10	Successful

Seat front edge static load test:

Nominal force to be applied on seat (N)	Nominal load applied to not tested samples (N)	Number of cycles	Results
1300	750	10	Successful

Combined seat and back durability:

Nominal force to be applied on seat (N)	Nominal force to be applied on back (N)	Number of cycles	Results
1000	300	25000	Successful

Table 13: Results of testing chair

2.3.3.Laboratory tests on library

For the library, the reference regulation is the EN 14749:2016 - Furniture - Domestic and kitchen storage units and kitchen-worktops - Safety requirements and test methods; the main significant aspect is the realization on test focused essentially on shelves, in order to evaluate any possible downward and the functionality of supports, beyond the general safety and stability controls.

Figure 26: Ecobulk prototype: Library

Safety requirements	Result
The components with which the user can come into contact during normal use shall have no burrs and / or sharp edges nor shall there be tubes with open ended tubes.	Successful

Table 14: Library safety requirements.

Shelf retention - vertical downward:

Dimensions of the tested sample (dm)			Nominal vertical force applied (N)	Point of application	Number of cycles	Results
Width	Depth	Thickness				

3,65	4,01	0,18	100	25 mm from the front edge of the shelf	1	Successful
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Shelf retention – horizontal downward:

Dimensions of the tested sample (dm)			Nominal horizontal force applied (N)	Point of application	Number of cycles	Results
Width	Depth	Thickness				
3,65	4,01	0,18	13	Centre of the front edge of the shelf	1	Successful

Shelf supports

Dimensions of the tested sample (dm)			Distributed nominal load (kg)	Point of application	Number of cycles	Results
Width	Depth	Thickness				
3,65	4,01	0,18	10	220 mm from each support	1	Successful

Table 15: Mechanical stability library

2.3.4. Laboratory test on bed

The bed is probably the safer prototype: due to its configuration, it guarantees ample reassurance in terms of mechanical resistance and stability; nevertheless, all the tests required were performed even for this product, in compliance with UNI EN 1725:2000 – Domestic furniture – Beds and mattresses – Safety requirements and test methods.

Figure 27: Ecobulk prototype: Bed

The activities implemented were focused mainly on evaluating the resistance to load and the durability of the different parts, as reported in following tables.

Fatigue test

Nominal force	vertical	Application point	Cycles	Results
1000 N		Footboard corner	1000	Successful

1000 N	Headboard corner	1000	Successful	
1000 N	Centre of the bed	1000	Successful	
Vertical impact				
Nominal falling mass	Nominal drop height	Application point	Cycles	Results
25 kg	18 mm	7 different points	10	Successful
Fatigue on outer edge				
Nominal force	vertical	Application point	Cycles	Results
1000 N		200 mm from the edge of the surface	5000	Successful
Vertical static load				
Nominal vertical force	Application point	Cycles	Results	
1400 N	Anywhere on the base of the bed where breakage is considered likely to occur	10	Successful	
Vertical static load on outer edge				
Nominal vertical force	Application point	Cycles	Results	
1200 N	In the center of the center line (M) of the bed rail	10	Successful	

Table 16: Mechanical stability bed

2.3.5. Laboratory test on little cabinet

A specific attention was dedicated on this prototype, since it was realized by using innovative panels instead of traditional particleboards: in fact, the product is obtained by assembling new solution with a high percentage of recycled material bonded with new low-emitting and eco-sustainable resins implemented during Ecobulk project by KEAS.

Figure 28: Ecobulk prototype: Little cabinet made with innovative panels

For this reason, the mechanical resistance of the cabinet is a doubly positive aspect, beyond other successful evaluations such as the stability and compliance with safety requirement.

Since we are dealing with a cabinet, the reference standard is the same as the library: UNI EN 14749:2016 – Safety requirements and test methods domestic and kitchen storage units.

Nominal vertical load	Cycles	Results
75 kg	10	Successful

Table 17: Load on worktop.

2.4. Furniture assembly and disassembly

2.4.1. Traditional furniture assembly and disassembly evaluation

The aim of ECOBULK project is to develop circular innovative solutions within three sectors: automotive, furniture and construction. The environmental and economic aspects of the ECOBULK demonstrators are addressed throughout evaluations such as life cycle assessment (LCA), Material Flow Analysis (MFA), life cycle cost analysis (LCC) and Cost Benefit Analysis (CBA).

Further objective of the project is to define the usability of the products through more evaluations, such as the collection of end-user feedbacks as well as the realization of laboratory tests, these latter carried out in order to evaluate the quality of the new models according to international technical references.

Considering the collection of end-user feedback, under the technical point of view, experiments regarding the disassembly and reassembly of furniture were conducted in different demositets.

In detail, the main focus of the activity was on prototypes designed by Moretti Compact, which were dis-assembled and re-assembled in order to evaluate the effective feasibility of these two processes and with the general aim to promote the extension of its lifespan.

Nevertheless, considering also that the prototypes were not immediately available, a preliminary evaluation was conducted on different pieces of furniture, mainly made of wood panels and already in commerce, with the scope to have a term of comparison with similar products in terms of materials.

Moreover, the activities were useful to suggest several requirements about methods to dis-assembly and re-assembly furniture, beyond the concrete definition of the features for a product to be considered as dis-assemblable and re-assemblable; the goal is to have furniture easy to repair and/or refurbish, as well as reusable and recoverable before than recyclable, since this characteristic is already amply achieved especially for wood-based products.

In this regard, the first activity was the interview of experts with five main questions:

- For you, what would be an easily dis-reassembling furniture?
- In which case do we find ourselves disassembling and/or reassembling furniture?
- Have you ever had the case where you disassembly or reassembly a furniture? Why did you do it (or not)?
- Which pieces of furniture are the most complicated to disassemble or reassemble?
- What are the mains difficulties in disassembling and reassembling a piece of furniture?

Based on their answers, a rating grid has been proposed with a grade of dis-reassembly with four items:

- Assembly: the ease of dis-reassembly, the number of steps, the strength of dis-reassembly, the number of required tools
- Quality and mechanical loss: quality of fastener, quality of panel, damage during dis-reassembly, the parts of furniture are standard and substituted, quality of supports.
- Fasteners and joinery: suitable and well-sized hardware, standard fasteners, fasteners with the same prints or method fitting without tools, no definitive fittings, fasteners accessible and visible.
- Information: Notification of assembly and disassembly, if after dis-reassembly there is mechanical loss or not, information about this furniture easy to find on the Internet.

This information was kept into account to define requirements of disassembly and reassembly but also to create a grid of rating; then, some pieces of traditional furniture were chosen to implement the grid and to elaborate in a preliminary way recommendation regarding the design or the choice of fasteners and fittings.

Elaboration of a rating grid

Feedback from interviews

For the elaboration of the grid, it was fundamental to have feedback from technical experts of furniture: since FCBA is one of the most important technical reference in Europe for the sector, eight technicians working in the mechanical laboratory of FCBA were chosen and interviewed, in order to collect their opinion about the topic of dis-reassembly.

Number	Position	Experience
1	In charge of laboratory	More than 20 years
2	Technician of laboratory	More than 5 years
3	Technical auditor	More than 5 years
4	In charge of professional brand	Between 2 years and 5 years

5	In charge of brand	More than 5 years
6	Consultant in design	Between 2 years and 5 years
7	Technical manager	More than 5 years
8	Test manager	More than 5 years

Table 18: Elaboration of a rating grid

Their answers were then elaborated and grouped considering the issues emerged: the final result is the rating grid to evaluate the potential of a furniture in terms of disassembly and reassembly.

Base on literature and the analysis of the interviews of experts, the following grid was defined: it includes in detail a specific parameter and a rate to be attributed, as well as possibility to provide useful comments.

Parameter	Rate	Comment
Assembly		
Clear and easy	/5	Rate if the piece of furniture is easily dis-reassembly, number of difficulties encountered, if the position of furniture needs to be changed...
Ease of step	/3	Minimize the number of steps to complete assembly and disassembly
Strength	/3	The user can dis-reassemble alone: 3 Difficult to do alone: 2 Need to be 2 users: 1 More than two users: 0
Number of tools	/5	No tools: 5 1 classic tool or provided tool: 4 an unusual tool: 3 2 tools: 2 3 tools: 1
Reduce the mechanical loss		
Fasteners quality	/3	
Panel quality	/3	
No damage during the dis-reassembly	/5	
Design with parts and hardware standard and substituted	/5	
Supports quality (Background, feet,...)	/3	
Fasteners		

Appropriate and well-sized fasteners stores	/5	Comments
Standard fasteners	/3	
Dismantling with one or without tools	/3	
No definitive fixing	/5	Loss points depending on the deterioration, if it is visible or not, if it impacts the furniture'
Visible and accessible fittings	/3	Characteristic for the reparability of the furniture
Indications		
Indication of dis-reassembly	/5	
Dis-reassembly furniture	/2	Example: Hardware that attaches to metal, dimensions that allow good functionality of the furniture, no fasteners that damage the furniture
Mechanical loss	/2	Hardware that can be found in home improvement stores
Indications available on the Internet	/2	Yes : 2 No : 1
Reference and brand of the furniture	/1	
Total	/65	

Table 19: Grid rating

Recommendations from experts

The interviews of the eight experts lead to five families of recommendations a shown below.

Figure 29: Categories of recommendations to evaluate the disassembly of furniture

Reversible assembly

The main idea is that the steps to disassemble a furniture should be the same, in reverse order than the steps to assemble the furniture.

The mains recommendations provided by interviewed are:

- The hierarchy of assembly: The furniture must have a planned design for disassembly in opposite order of the assembly.
- Do several tasks in one operation: the aim of this requirement is to minimize the numbers of operations and make the dis-reassembly easier.
- Easy method of fastening: This condition is major to facilitate users who do not have the equipment or are not used to assembling furniture.
- The parts of furniture have to be separated easily: this recommendation aims to reduce the workforce of the tasks, and reduce the risk of breakage.
- Realize the dis-reassembly with less tools: the aim of this requirement is that tools should not be a restraint of the dis-reassembly.

Create a reversible and easy assembling will encourage the users to dis-reassemble furniture. If the ability to disassemble is important, equally the potential of mechanical loss and safety issues should be taken into account. For this specific requirement, the new Ecobulk prototypes were tested according to all technical standards to be in compliance with.

Reduce the mechanical loss

Considering the emergency situation of unavailability of furniture kit as well as the need to reduce the manufacturing costs, companies may have chosen poorer quality materials or fasteners, which lead to design furniture that should be assembled one time. To extend the lifespan of furniture, when dis-reassembling, the furniture has to keep its mechanical strength. To reduce the mechanical lost the people questioned suggested.

- Quality of fasteners: to guarantee a better dis-reassembly, the fasteners should be of good quality.
- Quality of panels: For the longevity of the furniture, the panels have to resist at the dis-reassembly, as time goes by and in case of any bad use.
- The fasteners must not damage the panel: If the fasteners used damage the panels, after dis-reassembly the furniture will endure a significant mechanical loss.
- Strong backing: the aim of strong backing is to secure the stability of the furniture, reduce issue after dis-reassembly, especially in the context of a mechanical loss.
- Standard and substituted pieces: during the dis-reassembly, the users can lose the fasteners or break the parts of the furniture; it is important for the customers to be able to replace the piece or fasteners.

After dis-reassembly, one of the main issue is the mechanical loss and the loss of fasteners. In the next part, fasteners are a central topic in the conception of the dis-reassembly furniture and the expert interviewed shared their experience about the fasteners.

Well adapted fasteners

A well-adapted hardware will increase durability, as this will guarantee easier dismantling and reassembly of furniture. The following criteria concern fasteners and their functionality in term of removability of furniture:

- Well-sized hardware: this requirement is crucial to guarantee the safety of use, and anticipate the breakage after the dis-reassembly.
- Standard fasteners: in case the user loses pieces of fitting, he must be able to find it easily in store. This requirement enables to assembly of disassembly furniture with standard tools.
- Use the same imprint for the fasteners: this recommendation will reduce the number of tools for the dis-reassembly for the user.
- The fasteners must not damage the panel during assembly and disassembly: a deteriorated panel may weak the structure.
- Fasteners must be visible and accessible: this recommendation will make the furniture easier to dismantle and reassemble, and motivate the users to dis-reassemble the furniture.

Beyond these recommendations, there are also further requirements related to the typologies of fasteners used for the design:

- Ban the pieces glued together: the glued parts make disassembly impossible without destructing the piece.
- Ban nails, especially notched nails: the furniture with nails is impossible to dismantle and there can be serious damages of the panels.
- Ban wood screws: this type of fitting create loss of fastening force when the screw is removed, because it degrades the panels.
- The metal fasteners must be fixed to metal: this type of fitting is more durable than the metal fixed on the panel part.
- Uniform hardware: fasteners allowing the dismantling and reassembly of furniture should be with no tools if possible, or with a tool provided, or with standard tools.

These requirements on the fasteners will have an impact of making furniture more durable after having disassembled it, which will lead to more solid furniture products after reassembly. To make assembly and disassembly more accessible to a large number of people, users must have access to useful information as much as possible.

Information about disassembly

One of the most important feedback from the interviews is about the indications provided to consumers. The indications have to support the users during the assembly and disassembly stage. Here below the list of some suggestions proposed by the interviewed experts on information to be provided by manufacturers:

- Dis-reassembly designation: It's important to indicate if this furniture is dis-re-assembly totally or partially, and number of times it can be dissembled and reassembled. This indication allows a consumer to quickly identify this kind of furniture; it also allows manufacturers to

legally protect themselves. This designation must give a competitive benefit without too much constraint for the sellers.

- Notice with assembly and disassembly steps: Instructions should indicate the assembly and the disassembly steps, respectively in the reverse order. This recommendation allow supporting the user during all process.
- Indication of mechanical loss: It's necessary to specify if there is a mechanical and functional loss after dis-reassembly and quantify if possible.
- Indication in free-access on Internet: In case the user lost his notice or other documents with indication, they could always find the indication on Internet.
- Write the brand and reference on the furniture: in connection with the following point, this aspect would facilitate the search for the correct reference of the piece of furniture.

The indications are an additional means for the users to carry out the dismantling of the pieces of furniture either to transport or to sell them. To preserve furniture longer and prevent breakage, the manufacturers can publish a best practice guide to users.

Best practice guide

People not used to disassemble and reassemble furniture may make mistakes during these steps. In order to support them, a guide is another useful tool. For the experts interviewed the best practices that could be shared with the users could be:

- Reasonable employ: This practice is obvious, but some actions can weaken the furniture; this is a basic rule for the use of furniture, especially after the dis-reassembly.
- Reasonable use of tools: Screw by hand if possible; if a drill screwdriver is needed, use with adequate power for the task to keep the panels and hardware in good condition.
- Protect the piece: in case of dis-reassembly for storage or transport to keep furniture parts in good condition. The first reason of complaints is breakage during transport.
- Respect the instructions: To ensure a proper assembly and disassembly of the furniture, the users have to follow the instructions provided by the manufacturer.
- Keep the folder and tools: users are encouraged to keep the folder and tools provided by the supplier.

Some of this information should be provided when purchasing the furniture, on the other hand other general information could easily found on the Internet.

Preliminary experimental use of the rating grid

Before testing Ecobulk prototypes, pieces of furniture which have already undergone stress tests were used to test the rating grid of disassembling. For this evaluation, 6 pieces of standard furniture already in market were tested.

The piece of furniture were chosen for these requirements:

- By the typology of end user (kids), according to Moretti's main destination of use. In particular, we have storage furniture, bedroom furniture especially for children and scalable furniture, garden furniture, office furniture.
- These concepts must correspond to large and heavy furniture that are bulky. Because these pieces of furniture are difficult to transport and must be disassembled.
- Furniture with different fastening systems as gudgeon, inserts, wood screws and nuts for example.
- This designation should rather suit low furniture. This designation for wall unit furniture could be dangerous, for the user, and engage important legal responsibilities for the designers.
- The furniture must be delivered as a kit and not all-glued.

A non-expert operator carried out these dis-reassembly tests, in order to get into the condition of an ordinary user. The tester made observations and provided feedback on the furniture in order to be able to identify the difficulties that a user may encounter.

Figure 30 - Furniture tested for disassembly

It was not possible during the disassembling and reassembling tests to rate all the parameters of the grid. Therefore, the maximum score for each furniture is not the same. The detail of each experiment are available in the

appendix. As shown in the figure below, this first experiment gives significantly different results and dis-re-assembling capacity.

Figure 31 - Disassembling and reassembling score for each furniture

The interviews provided some guidelines on what a dis-re-assembled furniture could be, which lead to a first grid of evaluation.

This grid was tested on 6 pieces of furniture. The furniture was dismantled and reassembled by a non-technical use, to be in real condition, and the furniture has dismantled and reassembled without instructions. The user then rated the furniture according to his impressions and the difficulties encountered.

The grid has the advantage of being able to target some weaknesses of these pieces of furniture. The criteria brings ideas on a definition of dis-re-assembly furniture on good and bad fastening systems, weaknesses and strengths of the furniture, and the indications provided to consumers.

This grid is totally experimental but it can already provide significant feedbacks. However, it could be improved by a college of experts in the different areas of furniture design. The level of dismantling / reassembling of a piece of furniture is usually affected by the design of the furniture, with parts that are durable, and manageable by any user; therefore the weight of the parts must be within the design criteria.

To improve the criteria, it would be necessary to be able to carry out additional laboratory tests, such as maximum load tests after several disassembly / reassembly and to observe how the furniture reacts and if it meets the standards. As for the quality of the panels and the hardware, it would also be necessary to carry out tests and define an acceptable level of quality because it is an important criterion for the durability of a piece of furniture.

To assess whether the furniture can be easily Dis-re-assembly, it would be necessary to have the dis-re-assembly carried out by several profiles of assessors in competition. This will also allow you to see the difficulties that the different levels can encounter during dis-re-assembly.

Finally, this furniture designation could be suitable for different sectors of activity, such as events or catering. This designation will induce a more environmentally friendly look to the furniture. Designing this type of furniture will further develop the second-hand market, improve the reparability and reuse of furniture, and stimulate the development of the functional economy for the furniture industry.

Disassembling and assembling tests on traditional furniture

In this chapter, the results of the preliminary evaluation are resumed for each type of traditional furniture. The aim of this activity is to have a significant term of comparison for new furniture products elaborated during Ecobulk project especially concerning the possibility to easily assemble and disassemble products.

Cabinet number 1 feedback

Figure 32: Cabinet 1

- ✓ "This is a cabinet of basic design. It is a storage cabinet for home use. The hardware consists mainly of eccentric studs on which metal inserts are fixed.
- ✓ The background reinforcement panel is thin and secured with wood screws and grooves. The screws and fasteners are accessible except for two that are below the feet that must be removed.
- ✓ The door is rotated and heavy (heaviest part) and the hinges are fixed with large wood screws.
- ✓ The wardrobe is imposing, the dimensions are 215 centimeters for the height and 60 centimeters for the width and the length, the weight is 60 kg
- ✓ The tools required for disassembly are a flat head screwdriver and a screw gun.

Rating grid for cabinet 1: The red evaluations are not taken into the total

Assembly	rate	Comments
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Clear and easy	2,5/5	Except the door must dismantled and reassembled in a standing position. When standing, the door cannot be reassembled with a single user
Ease of step	1,5/3	the door which must be mounted upright and there are inserts hidden behind the furniture legs
strength	1,5/3	The whole structure easily done on its own except for the door.
Number of tools	3,5/5	To carry out the assembly and disassembly 1 compulsory screwdriver is necessary, and the screw gun that saves a lot of time.
Reduce the mechanical loss	rate	Comments
Fasteners quality	1,5/3	grade assigned to judgment (Find ways to quantify it)
Panel quality	1,5/3	grade assigned to judgment (Find ways to quantify it)
No damage during the dis-reassembly	3/5	Damage observed on the fixings for the door hinges, and for the rear reinforcement support
Design with parts and hardware standard and substituted	/5	Not defined
Supports quality (Background, feet,...)	1/3	unsuitable feet and reinforcement panel
Fasteners	rate	Comments
Appropriate and well-sized fasteners stores	2/3	The structure for fixing the right and left edge panel to the bottom and top panel is suitable. except for the door
Standard fasteners	3/3	Identical flat recess on all screws
dismantling with one or without tools	3,5/5	The screw gun is optional but saves a lot of time, a flat screwdriver is enough
No definitive fixing	4/5	no definitive fixing, but use of wood screws for the back panel

Visible and accessible fittings	2/3	All screws were accessible except those under the feet
Indications	rate	Comments
Indication of dis-reassembly	/5	
Dis-reassembly furniture	/2	
Mechanical loss	/2	
indication available on the internet	/2	
Reference and brand of the furniture	/1	
Total	27,5/48	The cabinet collapsed at the end of the assembly, because the door mounted alone and lie on the left side. It is a bad handling of the user, which is in question. The assembly requires at least two for the door.

Table 20: Rating grid for cabinet 1

Cabinet number 2 feedback

Figure 33: Cabinet 2

- ✓ "It is a piece of furniture designed to be dismantled and reassembled.
- ✓ The hardware consists of only 4 door hinges, gudgeon and inserts
- ✓ The back reinforcement panel is sturdy secured by groove systems, and is the heaviest part of the kit.
- ✓ The screws and fasteners are all accessible, the fasteners do not damage the panels, no fasteners can be removed, be careful when disassembling or transporting
- ✓ Swing doors that fixed by hinges with a clip system the doors are easily removable without damaging the hardware or the panels.
- ✓ The cabinet is heavy, its weight is 64.35 kilograms, it is transportable as is, but it was designed to be completely removable and reassembled and can inspire more voluminous furniture designs
- ✓ The dimensions are a height of 114 centimeters, width 100 centimeters and the depth is 45 centimeters.
- ✓ The only tool needed to disassemble and reassemble is a flat screwdriver
- ✓ Disassembly and reassembly without the instructions and only (person not used to disassembly and reassembly)

Rating grid for cabinet 2: The red evaluations are not taken into the total.

Assembly	rate	Comments
Clear and easy	4,5/5	The cabinet is disassembled in a standing position, the door clips may not be seen by the user.
Ease of step	2/3	When the inserts of the loosened edges everything is easily done alone. On the other hand, the weight can make assembly difficult.
strength	2 /3	strength required due to weight
Number of tools	4,5/5	Disassembly and reassembly only required one tool, a screwdriver.
Reduce the mechanical loss	rate	Comments
Fasteners quality	3/3	Quality that seems to be appropriate, judgment made visually
Panel quality	3/3	Panels that look dense
No damage during the dis-reassembly	5/5	no degradation observed

Design with parts and hardware standard and substituted	/5	
Supports quality (Background, feet,...)	3/3	The back support panel seems to guarantee the good balance of the furniture.
Fasteners	rate	Comments
Appropriate and well-sized fasteners stores	3/3	Fasteners are suitable for assembly and disassembly, especially for doors
Standard fasteners	3/3	can be assembled and disassembled with a basic tool
dismantling with one or without tools	5/5	just a screwdriver is needed
No definitive fixing	5/5	fasteners which do not prevent dismantling
Visible and accessible fittings	3/3	yes for all fasteners
Indications	rate	Comments
Indication of dis-reassembly	/5	
Dis-reassembly furniture	/2	
Mechanical loss	/2	
indication available on the internet	/2	
Reference and brand of the furniture	/1	
Total	45/48	the cabinet can be completely dismantled and reassembled, the only constraint could be the weight of the parts of the cabinet

Table 21: Rating grid for cabinet 2

Cabinet number 3 feedback

Figure 34 - Cabinet number 3

- ✓ It is a piece of furniture designed to be dismantled and reassembled.
- ✓ La quincaillerie se compose que de goujons et d'inserts tous les deux en métal
- ✓ The back reinforcement panel is sturdy secured by groove systems, and is the heaviest part of the kit.
- ✓ The screws and fasteners are all accessible, the fasteners do not damage the panels, no fasteners can be removed, be careful when disassembling or transporting
- ✓ The doors are sliding, there is a rail at the top with a system of clips to fix the doors, and at the bottom a groove at the bottom of the doors is put and they slide using a piece of PVC
- ✓ The cabinet is heavy, its weight is 82,5 kilograms, it is transportable as is, but it was designed to be completely removable and reassembled and can inspire more voluminous furniture designs
- ✓ The dimensions are a height of 118 centimeters, width 128 centimeters and the depth is 45 centimeters.
- ✓ The only tool needed to disassemble and reassemble is a flat screwdriver
- ✓ Disassembly and reassembly without the instructions and only (person not used to disassembly and reassembly)

Rating grid for Cabinet 3: The red evaluations are not taken into the total.

Assembly	rate	Comments
Clear and easy	5/5	The cabinet is disassembled in a standing position,
Ease of step	2/3	When the inserts of the loosened edges everything is easily done alone. On the

		other hand, the weight can make assembly difficult.
strength	2 /3	strength required due to weight
Number of tools	4,5/5	Disassembly and reassembly only required one tool, a screwdriver.
Reduce the mechanical loss	rate	Comments
Fasteners quality	3/3	Quality that seems to be appropriate, judgment made visually
Panel quality	3/3	Panels that look dense
No damage during the dis-reassembly	5/5	no degradation observed
Design with parts and hardware standard and substituted	/5	
Supports quality (Background, feet,...)	3/3	The back support panel seems to guarantee the good balance of the furniture.
Fasteners	rate	Comments
Appropriate and well-sized fasteners stores	3/3	Fasteners are suitable for assembly and disassembly, especially for doors
Standard fasteners	3/3	can be assembled and disassembled with a basic tool
dismantling with one or without tools	5/5	just a screwdriver is needed
No definitive fixing	5/5	fasteners which do not prevent dismantling
Visible and accessible fittings	3/3	yes for all fasteners
Indications	Rate	Comments
Indication of dis-reassembly	/5	
Dis-reassembly furniture	/2	

Mechanical loss	/2	
indication available on the internet	/2	
Reference and brand of the furniture	/1	
Total	44/48	the cabinet can be completely dismantled and reassembled, the only constraint could be the weight of the parts of the cabinet and assembly the doors

Table 22: Rating grid for Cabinet 3

Bunk bed feedback

Figure 35: Bed

- ✓ Bunk bed for children this kind of furniture are often disassembled and reassembled, in the context of resale or storage.
- ✓ The hardware consists of screws and nuts that are fixed in the wood. The bed base fixed with wood screws.
- ✓ The box spring is a panel plate that heavy, thick and compact
- ✓ The screws and fasteners are all accessible, the fasteners damage the bed base panel plate but the up-down stability is preserved
- ✓ It is a bunk bed, in view of its size, in the case of a sale or a move, it is necessary to dismantle, moreover it is a childbed, and this kind of furniture is frequently the second-hand market.
- ✓ The dimension of the bed is a width of 94 centimeters and a length of 204 centimeters and the height of the head and foot is 102 centimeters
- ✓ The tools required for disassembly are a flat screwdriver, an Allen key, and a screwgun

- ✓ Disassembly and reassembly without the instructions and only (person not used to disassembly and reassembly)

Rating grid for bunk bed:

Assembly	rate	Comments
Clear and easy	3/5	The cabinet can be dismantled from the position of use. The assembly and disassembly time is extended because of the bed base fixing system
Ease of step	2/3	except the bed base, the fixing system is understandable even without the instructions
strength	2/3	alone, some parts are difficult to wear
Number of tools	3/5	3 tools are needed for assembly
Reduce the mechanical loss	rate	Comments
Fasteners quality	3/3	The pieces are voluminous and it looks suitable
Panel quality	3/3	the quality of the panel seems to be suitable for disassembly and reassembly
No damage during the dis-reassembly	3/5	some parts are fixed by wood screws
Design with parts and hardware standard and substituted	/5	
Supports quality (Background, feet,...)	2/3	the low structure is maintained by wood screws, this is not the most suitable solution
Fasteners	rate	Comments
Appropriate and well-sized fasteners stores	1,5/3	The fasteners for the high structure is well suited, on the contrary for the low structure
Standard fasteners	2/3	Flat and 6-sided recesses
dismantling with one or without tools	2/5	3 tools were needed including a screw gun
No definitive fixing	3/5	the shelf cannot be dismantled, this part once dismantled is voluminous

Visible and accessible fittings	1,5/3	The screws of the bed base which are very numerous and it is necessary to position yourself under the bed
Indications	rate	Comments
Indication of dis-reassembly	/5	
Dis-reassembly furniture	/2	
Mechanical loss	/2	
indication available on the internet	/2	
Reference and brand of the furniture	/1	
Total	35,5/48	The furniture can be dismantled and reassembled, some systems can be improved, in particular the fixing and the weight of the bed base. The part with the shelf cannot be dismantled and is voluminous

Table 23: Rating grid for bunk bed

Table number 1 feedback

Figure 36: Table 1

- ✓ The fasteners consists of nuts and screws
- ✓ The table consists of a panel and a metal structure for the support

- ✓ The fasteners consist of screws with an Allen key imprint, most of which are in the metal structure and are hardly visible and accessible.
- ✓ The screws are fixed in nuts incorporated in the table
- ✓ It is a table that can transported assembled, but the fixing system can inspire models of larger tables or other furniture.
- ✓ The dimension of the table is a width of 80 centimeters and a length of 160 centimeters and a high of 73 centimeters
- ✓ To dismantle and reassemble the whole table, a screw guns is sufficient with the adapted bit

The furniture was dismantled and reassembled without the instructions and alone.

Rating grid for table 1: The red evaluations are not taken into the total.

Assembly	rate	Comments
Clear and easy	3,5/5	The step of disassembling and assembling the panel to the structure takes time for 6 screws
Ease of step	2/3	Buried fasteners and not easily accessible
strength	1,5/3	Alone, the panel is difficult to carry
Number of tools	3,5/5	Only one tool is needed, but the rod must be long enough and magnetized
Reduce the mechanical loss	rate	Comments
Fasteners quality	3/3	The quality of the fasteners seems suitable for several disassembly
Panel quality	3/3	Panel looks durable and is protected from fasteners
No damage during the dis-reassembly	5/5	No deterioration observed
Design with parts and hardware standard and substituted	/5	
Supports quality (Background, feet,...)	3/3	Support structure is made of metal, and the balance seems reasonable
Fasteners	rate	Comments
Appropriate and well-sized fasteners stores	2/3	The system allows disassembly and reassembly but some steps are binding
Standard fasteners	2/3	Allen key print

dismantling with one or without tools	3,5/5	Only one tool is required, but not all users are equipped with these kinds of tools, and cannot be supplied with the kit.
No definitive fixing	5/5	All the parts come apart, the table can be completely dismantled
Visible and accessible fittings	2/3	The screws that assemble the table and the structure are difficult to access
Indications	rate	Comments
Indication of dis-reassembly	/5	
Dis-reassembly furniture	/2	
Mechanical loss	/2	
indication available on the internet	/2	
Reference and brand of the furniture	/1	
Total	39/48	The table is completely removable. On the other hand, there are constraints: the necessary tool is not in the possession of all users, and the fastening system between the table and the structure is difficult to access. Alone, the table is difficult to handle.

Table 24: Rating grid for table 1

Table number 2 feedback

Figure 37: Table 2

- ✓ The fasteners consists of nuts and screws
- ✓ The table designed with a panel and a metal frame that attached by wood screws to the table, and the legs attach to the frame with a metal system in which a screw is inserted to secure the leg.
- ✓ The fasteners consist of screws with a BTR key recess, which are voluminous
- ✓ It is a table that can be moved or stored as is, but the fixings can inspire larger table models or even other furniture
- ✓ The dimension of the table is a width of 70 centimeters and a length of 140 centimeters and a high of 73 centimeters
- ✓ To dismantle and reassemble the whole table, a BTR key is sufficient.
- ✓ The furniture was dismantled and reassembled without the instructions and alone

Rating Grid for table 2: The red evaluations are not taken into the total.

Assembly	rate	Comments
Clear and easy	5/5	There are only the legs of the table to dismantle
Ease of step	3/3	4 steps for disassembly and reassembly
strength	1,5/3	The table panel is heavy
Number of tools	4/5	only one Allen key is required for disassembly and reassembly

Reduce the mechanical loss	rate	Comments
Fasteners quality	3/3	Very bulky fasteners and looks sturdy
Panel quality	3/3	As the table panel is heavy, it looks very compact
No damage during the dis-reassembly	5/5	No damage to the parts that need to be dismantled
Design with parts and hardware standard and substituted	/5	
Supports quality (Background, feet,...)	3/3	The legs of the table are made of metal
Fasteners	rate	Comments
Appropriate and well-sized fasteners stores	3/3	fasteners designed for disassembly and reassembly
Standard fasteners	2,5/3	Allen key fingerprint, but size is larger than average
dismantling with one or without tools	5/5	Only one Allen key is required
No definitive fixing	5/5	No definitive fixing on the parts necessary for disassembly
Visible and accessible fittings	3/3	Once the table is turned over for disassembly, everything is visible and accessible
Indications	rate	Comments
Indication of dis-reassembly	/5	
Dis-reassembly furniture	/2	
Mechanical loss	/2	
indication available on the internet	/2	
Reference and brand of the furniture	/1	
Total	45/49	This table with these fixings is completely removable and robust. Only constraint is that the table is heavy for a single person

Table 25: Rating Grid for table 2

2.4.2.ECOBULK prototypes: rating grids

Beyond the long life, it is also necessary to ensure the possibility to reuse and recover the products before recycling; at the moment, especially for wood-based products, the recycling process is well implemented: furniture for instance, is realized in some part of Europe with particleboard panels of almost 100% and they are completely recyclable at the end of life, in a circular process implying the re-realization of particleboards and packaging elements. For this reason, it's important to prioritize reuse and recovery, and it can be reached through the realization of modular furniture completely assemblable and disassemblable. In this regard, the same experimentation carried out on traditional furniture, was done on Ecobulk prototypes in different demotes, with the final aim to evaluate the effective easiness to disassemble and reassemble elements, even in comparison with products already on the market. The following paragraphs describe the experimentations performed in different demos; in this regard it's important to highlight that the evaluation was made mainly on the same product, the desk, because it is potentially the most critical one among all furniture prototypes and in order to have a comparison among the different demos (FCBA, Warwick and COSMOB: even if this latter is not properly a demo, the technical feedback of experts is very significant considering the aim of the project). Further demonstrations were made about the chair in LIPOR in Portugal and in the Coventry University in the UK

General feedback on desk

Figure 38: Desk used for assembling and disassembling evaluation

- ✓ It is a desktop prototype designed by Moretti with the aim of being disassembled and reassembled several times
- ✓ The fasteners consist of inserts and screws both made of metal
- ✓ The desk consists of several kit blocks that fit together.
- ✓ The screws and fixings are all accessible, the fixings do not damage the panels, to facilitate the tasks the studs can remain fixed to the desk but be careful when moving or storing not to damage them.

- ✓ The desk consists of two boxes, and two boxes on which the table is fixed
- ✓ The weight of the desk is 45 kilograms, the fixing systems can be transposed to larger pieces of furniture.
- ✓ the height of the desk is 76 centimeters, width 150 centimeters, and depth 50 centimeters
- ✓ The only tool needed to disassemble and reassemble the desk is an Allen wrench.

Rating grid for desk evaluated in demosite 1: FCBA

The red evaluations are not taken into the total

Assembly	rate	Comments
Clear and easy	5/5	The cabinet can be disassembled in the working position, no need to change it.
Ease of step	3/3	Once the screws have been identified and extracted, the desk can be dismantled in 4 steps
Strength	2 /3	The parts can be manipulated, but require strength to be able to be assembled and disassembled
Number of tools	4,5/5	Disassembly and reassembly only required one tool, an Allen key.
Reduce the mechanical loss	rate	Comments
Fasteners quality	3/3	Quality that seems to be appropriate, judgment made visually
Pannel quality	3/3	Panels that look dense
No damage during the dis-reassembly	5/5	no degradation observed
Design with parts and hardware standard and substituted	/5	
Supports quality (Background, feet,...)	3/3	The balance seems good especially because the rear panel is suitable
Fasteners	rate	Comments
Appropriate and well-sized fasteners stores	3/3	Fasteners suitable for disassembly and reassembly

Standard fasteners	3/3	can be assembled and disassembled with a basic tool
dismantling with one or without tools	5/5	just a Allen key is needed
No definitive fixing	5/5	fasteners which do not prevent dismantling
Visible and accessible fittings	3/3	Accessible and identifiable fasteners
Indications	Rate	Comments
Indication of dis-reassembly	/5	
Dis-reassembly furniture	/2	
Mechanical loss	/2	
indication available on the internet	/2	
Reference and brand of the furniture	/1	
Total	47,5/49 (97%)	The desk can be dismantled but partially, it is necessary to define if this can be acceptable to consider a piece of furniture as removable. If this "level of disassembly" is sufficient then the index is excellent.

Table 26: Rating grid for evaluated in demosite 1.

Rating grid for desk evaluated in demosite 2: Warwick

Assembly	rate	Comments
Clear and easy	4/5	The instructions provided in previous documents was enough to build the furniture. Very simple

Ease of step	3/3	
Strength	3/3	The parts seem very resistant
Number of tools	4/5	Two tools were needed. Very simple
Reduce the mechanical loss	rate	Comments
Fasteners quality	3/3	High quality material, great design
Panel quality	3/3	Excellent wooden materials
No damage during the dis-reassembly	5/5	No damage during disassembly
Design with parts and hardware standard and substituted	5/5	
Supports quality (Background, feet,...)	3/3	
Fasteners	rate	Comments
Appropriate and well-sized fasteners stores	3/3	
Standard fasteners	3/3	The number of tools could be decreases to 1
dismantling with one or without tools	4/5	Although the disassembly process is very simple, tools are required
No definitive fixing	5/5	All parts can be taken apart if needed
Visible and accessible fittings	3/3	
Indications	rate	Comments
Indication of dis-reassembly	3/5	No provided, but very simple

Dis-reassembly furniture	2/2	Very simple
Mechanical loss	2/2	No mechanical loss
indication available on the internet	2/2	No need to check
Reference and brand of the furniture	1/1	Indicated in general assembly instructions
Total	61/66 (92%)	This was done for the desk. The furniture is of very high quality and simple to install

Table 27: Rating grid for desk evaluated in demosite 2.

Rating grid for desk evaluated in demosite 3: COSMOB

Assembly	rate	Comments
Clear and easy	4/5	Different steps easy to be understood
Ease of step	2/3	Some practicality is needed
Strength	3/3	
Number of tools	4/5	
Reduce the mechanical loss	rate	Comments
Fasteners quality	3/3	
Panel quality	3/3	
No damage during the dis-reassembly	5/5	
Design with parts and hardware standard and substituted	3/5	Design could be improved in future

Supports quality (Background, feet,...)	3/3	
Fasteners	rate	Comments
Appropriate and well-sized fasteners stores	3/3	
Standard fasteners	3/3	
dismantling with one or without tools	4/5	Only one tool is necessary.
No definitive fixing	5/5	
Visible and accessible fittings	3/3	
Indications	rate	Comments
Indication of dis-reassembly	3/5	To be provided but intuitive
Dis-reassembly furniture	2/2	
Mechanical loss	2/2	No losses
indication available on the internet	0/2	Not found
Reference and brand of the furniture	0/1	Not found
Total	55/66 (83%)	

Table 28: Rating grid for desk evaluated in demosite 3

Rating grid for chair evaluated in demosite 4: LIPOR

Assembly	rate	Comments
Clear and easy	5/5	

Ease of step	3/3	
Strength	3/3	
Number of tools	5/5	
Reduce the mechanical loss	rate	Comments
Fasteners quality	3/3	
Panel quality	3/3	
No damage during the dis-reassembly	-/5	not applicable
Design with parts and hardware standard and substituted	-/5	not applicable
Supports quality (Background, feet,...)	2/3	
Fasteners	rate	Comments
Appropriate and well-sized fasteners stores	2/3	
Standard fasteners	2/3	
dismantling with one or without tools	-/5	not applicable
No definitive fixing	5/5	
Visible and accessible fittings	2/3	
Indications	rate	Comments
Indication of dis-reassembly	-/5	not applicable

Dis-reassembly furniture	-/2	not applicable
Mechanical loss	-/2	not applicable
indication available on the internet	-/2	not applicable
Reference and brand of the furniture	-/1	not applicable
Total	35/39 (90)%	

Table 29: Rating grid for desk evaluated in demosite 4

Rating grid for chair evaluated in demosite 5: Coventry

Assembly	rate	Comments
Clear and easy	4/5	
Ease of step	2/3	
Strength	1/3	Some doubt about the backrest
Number of tools	2/5	
Reduce the mechanical loss	rate	Comments
Fasteners quality	2/3	
Panel quality	2/3	
No damage during the dis-reassembly	-/5	not applicable
Design with parts and hardware standard and substituted	-/5	not applicable
Supports quality (Background, feet,...)	1/3	

Fasteners	rate	Comments
Appropriate and well-sized fasteners stores	3/3	
Standard fasteners	2/3	
dismantling with one or without tools	-/5	not applicable
No definitive fixing	2/5	
Visible and accessible fittings	3/3	
Indications	rate	Comments
Indication of dis-reassembly	-/5	not applicable
Dis-reassembly furniture	-/2	not applicable
Mechanical loss	-/2	not applicable
indication available on the internet	-/2	not applicable
Reference and brand of the furniture	-/1	not applicable
Total	24/39 (62)%	

Table 30: Rating grid for chair evaluated in demosite 5

2.4.3.ECOBULK prototypes: dis-and re-assembling tests

For the dismantling activity it is necessary the utilization of a tool, an allen key.

Figure 39: tool required

The desk fasteners consist of screws with an Allen key recess, in case of disassembly, it is necessary to be careful in order not to lose them and metal inserts, which are voluminous. These are the same fixings for all parts of the desk.

Figure 40: Fasteners

The inserts fit into the locations provided in the panels, to secure the different parts of the desk.

Figure 41: Separation of top

To facilitate dismantling, only one side is unscrewed and the inserts remain attached to the blocks. Once the blocks are disassembled, it's possible to confirm that the system is suitable for disassembly and reassembly, but requires force to fit the parts properly.

To separate the blocks, the fastening system is the same as for the worktop; as for the table, it's necessary to unscrew only one side.

Figure 42: Separation of blocks

Even in this case, the user has to force the action and has to be careful not to break the studs during disassembly. The inserts remain on the table structure.

In general, 3 steps are required to disassemble the prototype; it's important to highlight that at the end of the project we will have separated blocks but not separated panels: this is fundamental because the basic unit is the block, whose combinations allow to reuse or recovery the products with this specific design. The separation in panels would be suitable only for space saving but not necessary for recovery and quite difficult since the panels are assembled without the same fasteners as those used for blocks.

Figure 43: Desk completely disassembled

For the assembly phase, it could be enough to follow the same path of disassembly, starting by assembling the bottom blocks with the structure of the table top, for the right side and the left side. Assembly requires force to ensure that the parts fit together properly.

In conclusion, this desk is made up of 4 parts that come together, 2 boxes that make up the bottom of the desk and two parts that make up the table with a box. The fasteners are designed to be unscrewed and screwed several times, they are metal screws that attach to metal inserts; no fastener attaches to the panel, and this prevents damage to the furniture and therefore reduces mechanical loss during several disassembly and reassembly. Once disassembled and reassembled, the desk does not appear to suffer any mechanical loss, and the balance appears to remain the same. On the other hand, the piece of furniture is partially dismantled; the parts of the piece of furniture being glued, could be also considered as removable-reassemblable according to the criteria set for traditional furniture but probably more complicated. The weak point of "this level of disassembling" would be that the piece of furniture takes up space even when dismantled because the basic unit is the block instead of panel. On the other hand, the piece of furniture is modular and the sellers could more easily supply the parts of the assembly even several years after the purchase.

Considering the chair, the main result provided by the LIPOR demo site is that installation was very quick. Most of the components were already assembled by the manufacturer MORETTI and all that remained was to install

the seats. Two people performed the tasks of unpacking, assembling and placing the furniture in 30 minutes.

Figure 44: Furniture prototypes deployed at LIPOR demo site.

Figure 45: Furniture prototypes deployed at LIPOR demo site, details on the cubes

In general, most of the evaluation performed at demo sites gave positive results with high percentages: 83%, 90%, 92% and 97%, thus positively

comparable with traditional products; a less percentage was obtained with one chair, but since it is only one block with extension, the test not so significant.

Figure 46: Furniture prototypes deployed at Coventry demo site

2.5. Non-wovens in sofa

An experiment was conducted on 3 sofas, one of them being modified to include the non-woven materials developed by Tecnotex (NTT).

The protocol experiment was presented in a previous report, the focus here is made on the results obtained.

The questionnaire first addresses questions relating to sight, then smell and finally touch, the aim being to allow each sense to express itself. The sofa that contains the recycled material is called Sofa B in the experience.

Figure 47: Sofa B containing the non-woven material developed by Tecnotex

2.5.1. Visual perception

Linked to design

In order to assess visual perception, we asked the subjects: "Do you like the aesthetics of this sofa". Subjects were given the choice of answering yes, no or no opinion. Once the subject had answered, we asked them to explain why they liked or disliked the aesthetics of this sofa. Here below the results of first phase.

Figure 48: Graphs representing the results of visual perception related to aesthetics

We can observe that the assessments differ according to the sofas:

- Sofa C is the most popular, it is unanimously appreciated. Three aspects were highly appreciated by both groups: the modern design (positive opinion of 11 people), the simple but not simplistic aspect (positive opinion of 10 people) and the materials used (fabric and wood for the foot) (positive opinion of 9 people) (see appendix for more details).
- Sofa A is rather appreciated (between 50% and 76% positive opinions). For group 1, the most appreciated aspect is the colour (for 8 people), while for group 2 the colour is rather a negative aspect. The most appreciated aspect for group 2 is the impression of softness/friendliness of the sofa, this is an element that is also appreciated by group 1, but in second place (4 positive opinions). The other most appreciated secondary aspects are common to the different groups. There is the dimension that is perceived positively by a total of 7 people and the form (6 positive opinions). (see annex for more details).
- Opinions are very mixed for sofa B (see histogram 1). Certain aspects such as the simple/ober aspect of the sofa are appreciated by both groups (criterion appreciated by 7 subjects), the geometric aspect is also appreciated by several subjects in group 1. However, these elements are a disincentive for other subjects: the angular/geometric aspect is perceived negatively by 10 subjects and the simple aspect is rather translated as a lack of originality/ a sofa too banal for 8 subjects. This last element is also the most present criterion in the answers of the non-opinionated. Other aspects are not appreciated such as the lack of welcome and the perceived rigidity of the sofa.

Thus, we can see that opinions and criteria often converge between groups. Nevertheless, we can also see a divergence of opinion for certain criteria and

for the perception of certain sofas. These differences of opinion mainly reflect differences in preferences between individuals.

Related to comfort

We decided to ask the subjects about their perception of comfort. Subjects had the choice to answer that the sofa seems to be extremely comfortable, very comfortable, not very comfortable or not at all comfortable. For this and the following questions, we chose to distinguish between the right and left parts of sofa B (being made of different materials).

The graphs below represent the results of this question:

Figure 49: Results of sofa questionnaire

We can see :

- Sofa A is the sofa being perceived as the most comfortable: more than two thirds of the subjects find it very to extremely comfortable whatever the group (68.1% for group 2 and 80% for group 1). Group 1 finds it slightly more comfortable than group
- Sofa C is the second sofa being perceived as comfortable: More than half of the subjects in both groups find it very to extremely comfortable (50% of group 2 and 64% of group 1). Group 1 finds it slightly more comfortable than group 2.

- For sofa B: the opinions are similar in both groups for the right part, the sofa is seen as uncomfortable for half of the subjects, not at all comfortable for $\frac{1}{4}$ of the subjects and very comfortable for $\frac{1}{4}$ of the subjects. On the other hand, the visual perception of comfort is very heterogeneous for the left side: $\frac{2}{3}$ of the subjects find the sofa very comfortable in group 2 while $\frac{2}{3}$ of the subjects in group 1 find the sofa little/not at all comfortable.

Thus, we can observe that responses can be heterogeneous within the same group, but the perception of comfort seems to be quite similar between the two groups. Only the left side of the sofa is not unanimous between the groups and within the group: group 2 perceives it as much more comfortable than group 1. On the other hand, for sofas A and C it seems that group 1 tends to find the sofas slightly more comfortable than group 2.

2.5.2. Touch perception

In order to assess the perception by touch, we asked the subjects: "Do you like the way this sofa feels to you by touch? Subjects were given the choice of answering yes, no or no opinion. Once the subject had answered, we asked them to characterize the feeling of touch.

In the case of Sofa A we can see that the majority of the subjects like the feeling of touch, both in group 1 and group 2 (see graph below).

Figure 50: Graphs showing the results of perception by touch for sofa A

- Touch sensation is described by both groups through terms related to comfort, type of fabric and thermicity (see appendix for more details).
- In terms of comfort, the two groups have characterised the sofas in the same way: the terms "soft" and "gentle" are the most common ones for both groups. Some subjects in group 1 also described other more particular sensations such as the welcoming, natural and reassuring sensations that the sofa provides. On the other hand, for group 1 we find a negative term related to fragility.

- For both groups, the fabric is described as rough (for 3 people in group 2 and 9 people in group 1). Yet we also find opposite terms in both groups describing the fabric as being smooth (2 people in group 2 and 4 people in group 1).
- We can find in both groups words related to the thermality of the sofa. For the vast majority of users, the sofa feels warm (10 opinions).
- On the graph we find more negative answers for group 1 than for group 2. This is also reflected in the descriptive terms used by the subjects. In fact, in group 1 we identify some negative aspects related to the fabric and material such as: "seems to get dirty easily", "non-uniform foams", "roughness" or "hard at the armrests".

For sofa B we can see that the opinions differ according to the groups: the majority of the subjects in group 1 do not like the feeling the sofa gives to the touch and the opinions are very mixed for group 2 (1/3 like the sofa, 1/3 do not like it and 1/3 have no opinion) (see graph below).

Figure 51: Graphs showing the results of perception by touch for sofa B

- Once again, the feeling to the touch is described by both groups through terms related to comfort, type of fabric and thermicity for both sides of the sofa.
- As far as comfort is concerned, we can find the same sensations in both groups, whether for the left or the right side: the sofa is described by the majority of people as **hard** (for 28 people) and **rigid** (for 16 people), but also **tender** (for 7 people) and **soft** (for 6 people).
- For both groups, the fabric is mostly described as rough (for 32 people) on both the left and right sides. **Soft**" (mentioned by 8 people) and **"smooth"** (mentioned by 6 people) are also found for the left side. Positive properties are also stated: "resistance", **"breathable fabric"**. However, many negative terms are also described for both the left and the right side: **"abrasive"**, **"fragile"**, **"unpleasant"**, **"clinging"**.

- We can find in both groups words related to the thermality of the sofa. The left side is characterised as warm for the majority of people, and the right side as cold. Group 2 characterizes the sofa as **generally cold**.
- Group 2 is the only group to have stated terms related to the material used: "synthetic fabric", "artificial", "plastic".

For sofa C we can see that the majority of opinions are positive in both groups, especially for group 1 which appreciates the sofa has more than 76% (see graph below).

Figure 52: Graphs showing the results of perception by touch for sofa C

- Once again, the sensation to the touch is described by both groups using terms related to comfort, type of fabric and thermicity.
- In terms of comfort, the sofa is described as **"soft"** and **"light"** by both groups. However, several subjects in group 1 also used contrary terms: **"rigid"**, **"hard"** and **"firm"** and mentioned negative characteristics such as **"too loose backrest"**; **"not very strong"**; **"not very thick"**.
- For both groups, the fabric is mostly described as **"smooth"** (15 reviews) and **"soft"** (13 reviews). Conversely, several subjects in group 1 found this sofa to be **"rough"** (for 7 people).
- Terms referring to the material used were also cited: "unpleasant synthetic/plastic feeling" (cited by 4 subjects in group 2 and 1 subject in group 1) and "artificial", "jean-like" feeling for two people in group 1.
- We can find in both groups words related to the thermality of the sofa. For the vast majority of users, the sofa provides a feeling of warmth.
- Thus, we can see that sofas A and C are mostly appreciated by the subjects as far as touch is concerned. Opinions are once again very mixed between groups and within groups for sofa B. It is interesting to

note that, for the same sofa, the descriptive terms used can be opposite (for example: use of the word "rough" by several people but also use of the word "smooth" by others). Perception by touch is therefore a very individual feeling. The only difference in the terms used between the two groups is that group 2 uses many more terms related to the recycled aspect of the materials (e.g. "feeling of plastic").

2.5.3. Comfort perception

Comfort of the seat

In order to assess the perception of the comfort of the sofa seat, we asked the subjects whether the seat was extremely comfortable, very comfortable, uncomfortable or not comfortable at all. Once the subject had answered, we asked them to explain why.

For sofa A we can see that opinions differ between the two groups. The majority of the subjects in group 1 find the sofa comfortable. However, for group 2, opinions are very mixed: 54.5% find the sofa comfortable and 45.5% find it uncomfortable (see graph below).

Figure 53: Graphs of the results of the perception of seating comfort for sofa A

- Subjects from both groups found the sofa very comfortable or extremely comfortable because the sofa is "soft but not too much" (for 18 people) (see appendix for more details).

- The subjects in group 1 found the sofa uncomfortable or not at all comfortable because it has "too much seating depth" (for 5 people).
- In group 2, the main cause of the lack of comfort is due to "too soft a seat" (for 4 people), but the second most common cause is that the sofa has "too deep a seat" (for 2 people).

For sofa B (left side): we can see that the opinions are quite similar between the two groups: the largest half find the sofa comfortable. On the other hand, the opinions are a little more heterogeneous for group 1: we find more opinions "extremely comfortable" and "not at all comfortable" than for group 2.

Sofa B (left side) - Group 1
 Comfort of the seat

Sofa B (left side) - Group 2
 Comfort of the seat

Key

- Extremely comfortable
- Very comfortable
- Not very comfortable
- Not at all comfortable

Figure 54: Graphs showing the results of the perception of seating comfort for sofa B (left side)

- The majority of the subjects in group 2 found the left side of the sofa very or extremely comfortable because the sofa is "quite soft" (5 opinions) and provides "good support" (for 4 people).
- The majority of the subjects in group 1 found the left side of the sofa very comfortable thanks to its aspects "soft and firm"; "not too firm"; "firm but enveloping", "firm" (for 4 people).
- On the other hand, for both groups, firmness is the element that makes the sofa uncomfortable or not at all comfortable for several subjects.

For sofa B (right side): we can see from the graph below that opinions are rather mixed in both groups but tend towards a poor appreciation of the right side of the sofa as 2/3 of the subjects answered "not very comfortable" or

"not at all comfortable". The proportion of "very comfortable" is higher for the subjects in group 2, however we find in group 1 the appreciation "extremely comfortable" while it is not present in group 2.

Figure 55: Graphs showing the results of the perception of seating comfort for sofa B (right side)

- As with the left side of the sofa, the subjects found the right side of the sofa comfortable because it is "soft" but also "firm" which provides "good support" and is appreciated for back problems (see appendix for more details).
- Nevertheless, the majority of subjects find the right part of the sofa uncomfortable, both groups agree that this part is "too firm/ hard/ rigid".

For sofa C we can see that the majority of the subjects find the sofa "uncomfortable" or "not at all comfortable" (about 2/3 of the subjects). Group 1 tends to give a better appreciation of the sofa (about 44% of the subjects compared to 31.8% for group 2), but some subjects found the sofa "not at all comfortable" while no subject in group 2 gave this appreciation.

Figure 56: Graphs of the results of the perception of seating comfort for sofa C

- The subjects in group 2 found the sofa C comfortable because **"soft"**. Those in group 1 appreciated the **"support"** of the sofa (5 opinions) but also the "soft" aspect (3 opinions) (see appendix for more details).

Nevertheless, most people find the sofa uncomfortable. This perception is mainly due to the feeling of the sofa's frame when you sit on it, but also to the sofa's "too soft" appearance and a feeling of springiness ("I feel like I'm sitting on a trampoline" says one subject).

We can see that sofa A and the left side of sofa B seems to have a comfortable seat, while the right side of sofa B and sofa C seems to have an uncomfortable seat. The most appreciated elements of comfortable seating are the softness, support and posture. On the other hand, the elements that were not appreciated the most are the unsuitable dimensions (too deep seat), the feeling of the frame, the softness and firmness. We were not able to find any significant differences between the two groups in terms of perceived seating comfort: we can find the same descriptive terms used for both groups in most cases, and the evaluations do not tend to be more positive for any of the groups. One of the only differences is that group 1 seems to tend to use a wider range of terms than for group 2: for each sofa, all possible ratings were used ("extremely comfortable", "very comfortable", "not very comfortable"

and "not at all comfortable") whereas group 2 seems to have more homogeneous opinions.

Comfort of the backrest

We can see from the graph below that the majority of the subjects find the sofa A comfortable. Group 1 finds the sofa all the more comfortable than group 2 since the proportion of "extremely comfortable" is higher (see graph below).

Figure 57: Graphs of the results of the perception of backrest comfort for sofa A

- Subjects in both groups found the sofa very comfortable or extremely comfortable because the sofa provides "good support" (for 9 people), is "soft" (8 reviews) and has "good firmness" (4 reviews for group 1). (see annexed table).
- For both groups, the element that makes the sofa uncomfortable is the "too soft" aspect of the sofa (for 7 people), which "prevents good posture", good lumbar support or good cervical support (for 6 people).

For sofa B (left side): we can see that the opinions are quite similar between the two groups: the largest half of the subjects find the sofa comfortable. However, the proportion of "uncomfortable" and "not at all comfortable" responses is much higher for group 1.

Figure 58: Graphs showing the results of the perception of backrest comfort for sofa B (left side)

- The majority of the subjects in both groups found the sofa very comfortable or extremely comfortable because the sofa provides "good lumbar support" (14 reviews) and "a pleasant welcome" (7 reviews).
- The majority of the subjects in both groups found the sofa uncomfortable or not at all comfortable because the sofa is "too firm" (for 14 people) and "provides poor lumbar or cervical support" (for 5 people).

For sofa B (right side) we can see that the opinions are quite similar between the two groups: about $\frac{3}{4}$ of the subjects find the sofa "uncomfortable" or "not at all comfortable" (see graph below).

Figure 34 - Graphs showing the results of the perception of backrest comfort for sofa B (right side)

- The majority of the subjects in both groups found the sofa uncomfortable or not at all comfortable because the sofa is "too firm" and "steep" (for 25 people).
- The other subjects found the sofa very comfortable because it has "good firmness" (according to 4 subjects) and "good lumbar support" (according to 2 subjects), especially for people with back problems.

The backrest of sofa C is perceived as "uncomfortable" or "not at all comfortable" for more than half of the subjects. Group 1 tends to have a more positive appreciation of the sofa as the share of "very comfortable" is higher, however we find the appreciation "not at all comfortable" for a few subjects while it does not appear in group 2. On the other hand, in group 2, the share of "uncomfortable" represents almost $\frac{3}{4}$ of the responses, but the majority of the positive responses used the best possible rating of "extremely comfortable" while it does not appear in group 1.

Figure 59: Graphs of the results of the perception of backrest comfort for sofa C

- The majority of the subjects in both groups found the sofa uncomfortable or not at all comfortable because the sofa is "too firm" (for 9 people), lacks height for good lumbar and cervical support" (for 10 people) and the frame feels uncomfortable, which is unpleasant for the subjects (8 opinions).
- The other subjects found the sofa very comfortable because it provides "good support" (for 6 people) and "good firmness" (for 4 subjects).

Thus, we can see that, just like the sofa seat, the back of sofa A and the left side of sofa B seems to be comfortable, while the right side of sofa B and sofa C seems to have an uncomfortable back. The most appreciated elements in terms of backrest comfort are the good support, firmness, softness and warmth. On the other hand, the elements that were not appreciated are the too firm, stiff aspects, and especially the fact of not being able to have a good support. We were not able to observe any significant differences between the two groups: the appreciations seem to be relatively similar between the two groups (except for sofa C). Nevertheless, group 1 tends to have a more positive appreciation of the sofas (except for sofa B).

2.5.4. Conclusions on sofas

Our analysis revealed that the two groups seem to have a fairly similar perception of the sofa. Sofa A seems to be appreciated in terms of aesthetics, perceived comfort, smell, touch as well as the comfort of the seat and

backrest. Sofa C also seems to be appreciated in terms of aesthetics, perceived comfort and touch. However, opinions are very heterogeneous within the groups and between groups 1 and 2 regarding sofa B.

There are a few differences between the two groups, but these differences are not significant. Group 1 seems to tend to have a more positive perception of sofas A and C (in terms of aesthetics, perceived comfort, sense of smell as well as seat and backrest comfort). Nevertheless we believe that these differences may be related to individual tastes and the intrinsic and personal sensitivity of each subject. In the touch perception test, we found that for the same sofa, some of the descriptive terms used could be opposite, which is a reflection of individual sensitivities. This phenomenon is also reflected in the heterogeneity of the responses that can be found throughout our analysis.

This first experiment would lead to the conclusion that the consumer is not affected by knowing a product contains recycled materials. In the next period, some further analysis will be done to complete the results and evaluate and/or test potential improvements of the method.

3. Construction

3.1. Recycled GFRP-waste composite materials and product manufacturing

3.1.1. GFRP-waste reinforced thermoplastic materials

Recycled and waste materials produced by agglomeration technique into "recycled composites" and intended for A) direct extrusions and/or B) to become pelletized/compounded into granules at a second processing stage to be used in any existing thermoplastic processing method e.g. injection and/or compression moulding and other, can be various and in practise more or less limited what to use. Possibly the most typical product made thereof is a decking board and/or made of wood and/or other natural fibres + virgin and/or recycled thermoplastic polymer PE/PP/PVC and additives like minerals, processing aids, coupling agents, colouring pigments UV- and heat stabilizers and named as wood-plastic composite (WPC).

In the Ecobulk-project focus was given to develop material formulations containing in particular thermoset (polyester/vinylester/epoxy) based glass fibre reinforced plastic waste (GFRP) using the Conenor invented agglomeration technique and replacing partly or totally wood/natural fibres in conventional wood-plastic composites (WPCs) to make them stronger and stiffer, eliminate creep and thus adequate for structural applications. This is therefore that thermoset GFRP-materials do not have any existing feasible recycling technique nor volume application developed for the market and waste volumes from various sources are huge and ever increasing. The need and lack is well understood especially in the wind energy industry for the turbine blades where predicted EoL waste volumes are expected to reach dozens of megatons annually in coming next decades while the use production and use of wind turbines is globally expanding rapidly.

There are basically two ways of mechanical GFRP recycling methods, the first one is mechanical way which involves shredding, crushing and milling. Second method is, fiber recovery from polymer matrix, and this is often expensive and applicable to carbon fibers but not for glass fibers. Therefore, high value products like CFRP are treated with this process. Recycling GFRP-composites is challenging due to their high resistance towards chemical and thermal condition. However, it has also techniques for them to recycle through cement kiln route, which is also supported by EU legislation. In this process, GFRP-waste are reduced their sizes, fed them into cement clinker to produce cement. However, it is stressed that cement kiln processing is not a circular method, instead this can be considered as EoL solution for GFRP-waste.

Figure 60 below presents in a way those techniques today being developed/evaluated for the GFRP waste treatment methods. None of them is currently in industrial volume use – other than landfill – and vary in their readiness level and capital investments needed. Omitting landfill, which is basically forbidden by the EU-legislation already in 2016 but still widely

happens all over Europe, mechanical processing presents the lowest investments costs and most rapid entry to market and is thus a very lucrative option to become adopted to market use. In mechanical recycling value chain the first processing step with bulky objects is downsizing those into smaller processable parts by either blade saw or jet cutting. And with wind turbine blades often at decommissioning site to ease out their transport. Next they need to become further downsized by shredding either at decommissioning site by mobile shredders or at a recycling site where also metal detectors remove metals (substantially but not 100%) from the shredded mixed material.

Note, however, that the shredded mixed blade material typically contains small quantities of other materials than just GFRP and some are to be considered as non-wanted contaminants one has to learn to live with.

Figure 60: Waste management categories hierarchy

Ref. SusChem; Polymer Composites Circularity – White Paper
<http://www.suschem.org/publications>

Figure 61: Categories between Repurpose – Recycling - Recovery

3.1.2. Conenor agglomeration manufacturing technology

In the Conenor invented agglomeration technique bulky GFRP-products are in step 1 after dismantling first pre-cut into smaller parts followed by manual sorting i.e. removing metal, PUR-foam, cables, fixtures etc. clearly visible not GFRP-material. This step with wind turbine blades takes typically place at the dismantling site.

In step 2 mechanical downsizing of the bulky GFRP-parts into small a few cm flakes take place at a shredder where ferrous metals are separated with a magnet and the outcome GFRP-waste is stored at big bags ready for the Conenor agglomeration processing in step 3.

When using GFRP-product manufacturing waste, preferably in the multilayer product outer surface layer formulation, derived as dust from product polishing, it can be used as is without any pre-processing. Pultruded, SMC etc. and semi-finished products and rejects need to be downsized in a shredder equally as EoL-bulky GFRP-items.

Figure 62: Value chain recycling EoL wind turbine blade waste

The Conenor agglomeration procedure is consisting of 3 consequent steps:

1. weighing of all material fractions being used take place prior to mixing and
2. feeding of weighted material fractions take place in three intervals into the hot mixer during the mixing cycle and
3. cooling the agglomerates in the cooling mixer some 5-10 minutes while a new next batch is being processed in the hot mixer.

Figure 63: Conenor agglomeration process

Technical parameters of high intensity mixer Herfeld 100/200L used:

- output up to 100 kg/h – operating 380V/3-phase/max. 75A
- hot mixer 100L with 40kW drive and 3-blade mixer, 1350rpm, controls full and half speed
- instrumentation for total current (A) and hot mixer material temperature (°C)
- volatile exhaust with fan out of hot mixer opening on top
- cooling mixer 200L with 7,5kW drive and 1-blade mixer, cold water circulation in 2-wall bowl structure
- typical loading a' 25 or 30kg batch size, total cycle time 20-25 min.

In industrial operations for commercial quantities the scale-up of agglomeration processing is realised as illustrated in Figure 64 below.

Bigger sized mixing equipment are existing from several existing equipment suppliers worldwide up to 2000 liter size and giving outputs in excess of 2ton/h. Manufactured batches are stored after the mixer preferably in mixing silos homogenizing all batch materials into one quality. From the mixing silos material is fed into individual extrusion lines and/or compounding into

granules/pellets for injection moulding and other conventional thermoplastic polymer processing.

note; for compounding Conenor GFRP-waste containing agglomerates, see AIMPLAS compounding trials verification is section 3.5.

Scaling-up Agglomeration

Figure 64: Scaling-up agglomeration processing

3.1.3.Extrusion of multilayer composite building products

Product shapes and materials

In the beginning of the project Conenor provided the participants a list of components and shapes of products possible to be developed with the existing and new developed extrusion tooling for the aims of the demonstrators.

An additional feature "Fire Retardancy in EN class B" was also offered using a halogen free flame retardant at the product outer surface if needed but did not became utilized in any of the outdoor demonstrations.

This list below consist of both solid and hollow extruded profiles and panels in multilayer (type A-B-A) structures.

Conenor Components "Shopping List"

- I) Outdoor Furniture
- II) Building & Construction

Conenor composite components available :

N.o	Name	Dimensions	Layers		Notes
			single	multi	
1	Solid Plank R	120x30mm	x	x	round corners
2	Solid Plank S	120x30mm	x	x	sharp corners
3	Solid Plank F-F	140x30mm	x	x	female-female edges
4	Hollow Board	120x28mm	x	x	
5	Hollow Board F-F	140x28mm	x	x	female-female edges
6	Solid Panel 5	390x5mm	x		straigh edges
7	Solid Panel 10	390x10mm	x		straigh edges
8	Solid Panel 10B	390x10mm	x		bevelled shi lap edges
9	Hollow Pillar 5	125x125mm	x	x	5mm wall
10	Hollow Pillar 10	125x125mm	x	x	10mm wall
11	Hollow Pillar 15	125x125mm	x	x	15mm wall
+	Feature "Fire Retardancy"		x	x	EN Class B

Figure 65: Extruded recycled composite products available from Conenor

Alternative waste and virgin material basis to be chosen and formulations thereof to be developed for the use in extrusions are various as well as from where to source those. As the logistics of those targeted waste materials is not existing in the market before creating the value chains and get them working, it is logic to use those optional ones known and preferably found locally to eliminate unnecessary transport costs and unwanted negative effects in the LCA calculations.

Related to GFRP-waste local sourcing of manufacturing waste was possible in collaboration with company Exel Composites located just some 100km away from Conenor. The waste materials are derived at Exel from shaving operations as coarse dust and stored in big bags on wooden pallets. The dusty shaving waste is usable in Conenor agglomeration process "as is" and became used in the product outer surface layer at dosing level typically 35%-w. as about the same of blade waste in the core layer.

End of Life wind turbine waste was originally sourced from Holland from company Virol but due the high level of contamination e.g. bulky metal parts was changed into company Demacq, also in Holland, specialized in this activity. However, also the quality supplied by Demacq was relatively low containing moisture, mud and sand, PUR-foam, non-ferrous metals and technical plastic particles which do not become molten in the processing temperatures of PE and PP but remain as defects in the product.

Figure 66: Contaminants in the wind turbine blade waste and Demacq quality

Therefore, as none of the contaminants other than visible metal parts were removed at Conenor for the blade waste, it must be concluded that the quality of blade waste used in manufacturing the Ecobulk materials is the lowest quality one can think of. Sorting the contaminants out of the GFRP-waste would result better quality feedstock material as well as better quality materials and products made thereof.

Recycled post-consumer polyethylene (HDPE) and polypropylene (PP) supplies were predominantly sourced from company Swerec in Sweden and supplied in 1ton big bags. The origin of the recycled plastics comes from consumer goods such as cosmetic bottles, canisters and other packaging products from the European market. Also other locally in Finland sourced industrial based wasted pipes were found available from Lahti city waste collection plant, shredded at Conenor and used in making the recycled composite material formulations. The supply form is mixed colours in shredded and washed flakes about 10mm size, see foto below.

Figure 67: Shredded thermoplastics (HDPE, PP) in mixed colours by Swerec

Figure 68: Wasted PE (blue)- and PP-pipes (white) from Lahti city

Figure 69: Shredding wasted pipes at Conenor for agglomeration processing

Other materials used in the agglomerated extrusion formulations include;

- wood fibres (Nordic pine in compressed pellets) sourced locally
- processing and product performance additives;
 - g-MAH coupling agent in granule form
 - compatibilizer in granule form
 - processing aid (wax) in granule form
 - UV-stabilizer in granule form
 - colorants in powder form

Extrusion of multilayer profiles and panels

Extrusion of Ecobulk composite profiles and panels was realised at Conenor invented rotary extruders CONEX[®].

The Conenor invented multilayer CONEX[®]-extruder utilizes a simple die to form the multilayer product shape fed with two individually operated rotors nested inside each other. The main benefit of the CONEX[®]-extruder is that both material layer formulations, product inside and outside, can be freely chosen in optimization of the product cost and performance while in co-

extrusion the outer material layer must be always plastic rich with less reinforcing fibers.

Conenor CONEX® CWE 500-2 two rotor extruder and line as shown in figure xx below, was used to produce multilayer composite building products; solid and hollow planks 120x30mm and hollow beams and pillars 125x125mm.

LAY-OUT : Conex Wood Extrusion, CWE 500-2, line

Figure 70: Schematic diagram of CONEX® CWE 500-2 extruder and line

Figure 71: Extrusion of building products planks and pillars

Ecobulk solid panels in dimension 395x10mm were manufactured using Conenor two rotor CONEX® CE 280-2 extruder and panel line as shown in figure 48 below.

**EXTRUSION PROCESS DIAGRAM FOR MULTILAYER COMPOSITE PANELS
IN A_B_A-STRUCTURE WITH TWO ROTOR CONEX®**

Figure 72: Conenor two rotor CONEX® CE 280-2 extruder and panel line

3.2. KymiRing demonstrator, Finland

<https://www.kymiring.fi/>

Figure 73: KymiRing

The Finnish demonstrator "KymiRing MOTOGP track" is located at Kausala some 60km north from Conenor and thus very convenient in near distance. The track has been under construction past a couple of years and yet at its finalization stage with the infrastructure.

Opening of the track for the European MOTOGP racing was supposed to take place July 2020 but due Covid-19 restrictions postponed till 2021 and again postponed for the same reason to July 2022. For the reason that there was

no need for the infrastructure, it has caused also delays in the Ecobulk planned infrastructural constructions i.e. visitor benches and shelters at KymiRing to become accomplished.

The original plan at KymiRing consists of 150 meters of visitor benches, 50 units a' 3m long, to be situated around the track in nature and 20 modular shelters in size a' 3x3 meters for visitors plus an info cabin.

At later stage the one constructed modular visitor shelter did replace the info cabin and the 20 modular visitor shelters became replaced by flagman shelters for good reasons given below.

3.2.1. Outdoor Visitor Benches

Benches were designed to be ready pre-assembled at Conenor with extruded planks as bench covers and the supports underneath to become built by KymiRing at site to their chosen design.

Figure 74: KymiRing outdoor bench covers with extruded planks by Conenor

The 50 bench covers a' 3m long were manufactured and delivered by Conenor to KymiRing during summer 2019 but due to the delays became constructed by KymiRing only after summer 2021.

Figure 75: Visitor benches located around the track in nature at KymiRing

3.2.2. Flagman Shelters

The original idea of modular shelter constructions with Ecobulk components at KymiRing was planned for visitors and design was made by KymiRing chosen external architect office named Sankari in Finland.

Figure 76: Modular visitor shelter design by Sankari

After constructing the very first modular visitor shelter at KymiRing, it became clear to have a need to change the approach for the following reasons;

- the shelter is structurally unstable
- it takes much long time to construct
- results a lot rest pieces at site
- becomes expensive

Figure 77: KymiRing modular visitor shelter

Therefore, the plan had to be re-considered for more appropriate shelter application and a “flagman shelter” became chosen. Flagman shelters are needed around the track in several positions for racing inspectors in case of an accident or equal reason to discontinue racing and give

warning/information to drivers by waving a flag in different colours e.g. yellow not to pass the driver in front.

Materials for total of 20 flagman shelters were produced and delivered by Conenor to KymiRing during spring 2021 and stored at the site, see figure xx below.

Figure 78: Images of the flagman shelter constructions at KymiRing

Note the shelter on four long pillars at each corner is fixed to the metal wall by bolted joints as well as planks securing its stability even at heavy wind conditions. Roofing in pane design is with composite panels without external metal nor bitumic coating.

Material consumption in **one flagman shelter** is the following;

- Hollow pillars 125x125 mm long 2x3000 + 2x3500 mm

- Roofing support planks 120x30 mm 2x1800 + 6x2000 + 3x1000 mm
- Flooring planks 120x30 mm 9x1200 mm
- Cross supports 120x30 mm 4x1500 mm
- Roofing panels 395x10 mm 6x2100 mm
- Wall panels 395x10 mm 9x1200 mm

Material consumption in **one visitor bench** is the following;

- Feet (from pillar material) 125x125 mm 6x120 mm
- Side planks 120x30 mm 2x2300 mm
- Supports 120x30 mm 2x400 mm
- Bench cover planks 120x30 mm 4x3000 mm

Joining was made with standard wood and other screws, corner irons and nailing plates with pre-drilled holes.

Figure 79: Fixtures used at KymiRing

Figure 80: Conenor supplied 20 flagman shelter materials at KymiRing

Feedback from KymiRing personnel working with Ecobulk products;

+ ease of working, easy cleaning, good weatherability, no rotting

- heavy weight, complex fixing with drilling and use of corner irons, low screw withdrawal force with standard screws

Assembly times expected to improve when constructing more and by learning, now;

- visitor bench 2x4 man hours

- flagman shelter 2x16 man hours

3.3. UK universities demonstrators

3.3.1. Gazebo type shelter design

The original gazebo type shelter designed for the UK demonstrators was made by previous project coordinator Exergy who provided Conenor the list of extruded components to be manufactured and supplied to each three universities. The shelter design is presented in figures below.

The list of components in grey colour consists the following;

- hollow planks 120x28mm (lighter weight for roofing structure)
- square tubes 125x125mm for load bearing beams and pillars

Grey colour was made easily by adding carbon black in the extrusion formulation and tuned lighter using titanium dioxide white. UV-stabilization additive was used to provide protection against sun light degradation.

It was agreed to make the flooring, if needed, from locally found and sourced materials in the UK market.

Figure 81: Exergy design for the UK shelter

Figure 82: UK shelter materials ready for delivery at Conenor

3.3.2. Warwick University demo site

This section covers the construction of the construction demonstrator at the University of Warwick. A brief presentation of previous activities is done, follow by a description of the shelter construction.

Preliminary activities

Before the construction of the construction of the shelter, a location was chosen and a survey of the terrain was done. Below images of the possible locations at the University of Warwick. The location in purple was chosen as it gave good access to the public and the construction team.

Figure 83: Possible locations at Warwick University

After a location was chosen, a terrain survey was done, shown in the image below. The survey showed that the space chosen did not overlap with important services.

Figure 84: Terrain survey of chosen location

Additional preliminary activities included testing the mechanical integrity of different join systems for the shelter. Below a brief description of these activities.

Structural characterisation of screw joints

Two types of commercial screws were considered: wood screws, M3, M4, and M5 (Fig. 1) and self-drilling screws, No. 8 ($\varnothing 4$ mm) and No. 10 ($\varnothing 5$ mm) (Fig. 2).

Figure 85: Pozidriv Countersunk Stainless Steel Wood Screw, A2 304, 5mm Thread, 25mm Length

Figure 86: RS PRO Bright Zinc Plated Steel Self-Drilling Screw No. 10 ($\varnothing 5$ mm) x 25mm Long

In the case of using wood screws, it is highly recommended that small pre-holes, with 2 to 2.5 mm diameter, are made in the GRP material prior insertion of any screws. This is to avoid delamination and cracking of the material. If shown appropriate, self-drilling screws may be used without making pre-holes.

The selection of the screw type and diameter shall be consistent with the expected forces and moments found in the structural study done by Scott White and Hookins LLP (appendix 1). Given that these forces or moments were not reported in the outcome of the structural study *203307 - Eco Bulk Enclosure*, this report is not in capacity to recommend a particular screw type and diameter. Moreover, this report will inform the selection of an adequate screw type and diameter considering the outcome of the structural study, as well as logistical aspects (e.g. material availability, time, number of staff and tools on site) around the construction of the Ecobulk shelters.

Table 31 summarises the screw withdrawal force for the screws considered.

	Self-drilling screws		Wood screws		
	No. 8 (Ø4 mm)	No. 10 (Ø5 mm)	M3	M4	M5
Max force ($n = 10$) [N]	1080 ± 66	1053 ± 79	987 ± 93	1279 ± 57	1375 ± 113

Table 31: Summary of screw withdrawal force for the screws considered

It shall be noted that the structural study report reads: “The 3D model analysis indicated that the loads, deflections, and stresses on the frame are not likely to be high and should be acceptable, provided the stability and joint connection issues are resolved”. Following this, it is suggested that M4 wood screws or No. 8 (Ø4 mm) self-drilling screws may be used to the EcoBulk shelter units. The screw withdrawal force is reported in Table 1.

It is recommended to use heavy duty flat and square brackets (Fig. 3) to secure the structural GRP sections. The selection of heavy duty brackets shall be done in agreement with the screw type and diameter selected as well as the availability of parts. Details on the location of these connections was presented to Scott White and Hookins LLP in the past.

Figure 87: Sabrefix Heavy Duty Angle Brackets Galvanised 90 X 63mm

The support of the GRP slat cladding elements may be done using lower gauge square brackets and M3 wood screws or No 6 (Ø3.5 mm) self-drilling screws. Note that No 6 self-drilling screws were not tested for this report; moreover, they are likely to be sufficient to secure the GRP cladding elements.

Construction of the shelter

The construction of the shelter at the University of Warwick was done in March 2021. Once the selection of the location and the underground survey was done, the construction started. The construction was done by William Gough & Sons Ltd, based in Coventry. The images below show the progress in the construction.

Figure 88: Progress of construction 1

Figure 89: Progress of construction 2

Figure 90: Progress of construction 3

A set of furniture for the public use was installed. Posters with information about the shelter, with an invitation to complete a consumer perception survey, were also installed.

Figure 91: Shelter completed

After the construction, roughly 15% of the material was lost as left over or was slightly damaged during transportation to site. Some of this material will be stored until the termination of the project.

Figure 92: Leftover material

Monitoring

The shelter was monitored after construction. Signs of deterioration as consequence of weathering or use were the object of this monitoring activities. After 10 months since the installation of the shelter, no signs of degradation in the construction material were found.

Stakeholder consultation

A consultation of stakeholder's perception of the EcoBulk composite materials used in building an outdoor shelter unit at University of Warwick (UW). Two groups were targeted: i) the team in charge of building the shelter, ii) users of the shelter after construction. A survey for each group was used to collect the information.

In general, the construction team showed a high level of concern for waste in their places of work, and a believe that most materials used in construction should be widely recycled. Consistent with this, the construction personnel reported that sustainability factors positively affected the purchase of raw materials and tools. They stated that the fact that products contain recycled materials did not always stop them from purchasing them. However, less support and interest were given to construction materials and PPE containing recycled material. In relation to the EcoBulk material in the shelter, the

personnel found the material easy to work with, with no particular difference with traditional materials. Moreover, the sustainability qualities of the EcoBulk materials improved or left unchanged their opinion of the EcoBulk shelter at UW. In the results of the surveys and in conversation, it was clear that the construction personnel had a positive perception of the EcoBulk materials.

Similar results were found when surveying the second stakeholder group. Most of the users showed high interests in solving sustainability issues by making materials and products more recyclable and circular, shown in figures below. However, a remarkable difference between the two groups was found. In general, users declared that the fact that products contain recycle materials would not stop them from purchasing them. This was seen across all products, whereas the construction personnel made a distinction between products that they would purchase and those they would not.

Figure 93: Answer to the question: How aware or concerned are you of the following?

Figure 94: Answer to the question: For each of the following statements, select whether you Agree, Neither agree or disagree, or Disagree

Figure 95: Answer to the question: How likely are you to buy

Figure 96: Answer to the question: Which product categories would you be likely to buy, rent or lease knowing that they contain recycled materials?

Figure 97: Answer to the question: Does knowing that the material used for the construction of the shelter and furniture at the University of Warwick contains recycled materials make their "image" Better, Similar or Worse?

The results from stakeholder engagement have shown a positive perception of products containing recycled materials, and in particular, of the EcoBulk materials for the outdoor shelter built at the University of Warwick.

3.3.3.Cranfield University demo site

The EcoBulk project works on demonstrating circular economic applications in the field of automotive and construction industries with the involvement of other partners such as universities, industries and some organisations. The Cranfield University is one of the partners that constructed an outdoor shelter by using extruded planks and beams made from crushed wind turbine materials as a demonstration activity under the work package (WP) 4 of the EcoBulk project. The WP4 of the project aims to validate re-manufacturability of circular design concept of EcoBulk products. Under the WP4 of the project, three UK universities including the Cranfield University are building outdoor shelters using hollow pillars and structural beams extruded by using waste particles taken from wind turbine blades. They were produced by a company called Conenor in Finland.

The extruded planks and beams are novel. So, the impacts of exposing them to the outdoor weather, stresses and strains over time should be assessed. The changes in mechanical, physical and surface properties over time are taken into account to validate the durability of the extruded planks and beams manufactured by using crushed particles of used wind turbine blades.

A survey is conducted for the constructed who worked with the novel material to identify how hard or easy to work with the new material comparatively

with similar materials they work with. Another survey is carried out among the general public to identify how people think about the circular economy initiatives. A disassembly case study together with the survey results are presented in section 4.

Construction of the structure

The planks and the beams were received by Cranfield University in March 2020 when the UK was locked down. They were exposed to the weather partially during that period of time. Planks and beams were then stored in an indoor environment prior to the construction. The construction was started after 8 months of the planks and beams were arrived.

The construction of the outdoor structure was done according to the plan provided. After constructing the frame of the structure, the horizontal planks were fixed on the top of the structure as its roof as shown in Figure 98:. After the construction of the roof structure was done, A bowing effect of the main beams were observed due to the weights of the planks on it as shown in Figure 98. The vertical planks were then constructed as walls following the plan of drawing provided.

Figure 98: Bowing of beams

In order to eliminate the bowing effect and to make the structure more stable, diagonal braces were introduced afterwards as in Figure 99 below.

Figure 99: The structure with diagonal braces

Monitoring the bowing effect

In order to evaluate the bowing effect of the beams over time, the distance between a fixed points on the ground and the mid-point of the beams were taken by using a laser measurer over time as shown in figure 72. The changes in distances are shown in tables and figures show the changes in distances from point 1, 2, 3 and 4 respectively.

In general, the beams bend over time. (The distances reduce over time). The effect of rain is one of the significant factors in bowing the beams. When readings were taken after rainy weeks, the distances reduce and they increase during sunny weeks.

The shelter is not in public use now considering health and safety requirements. As a result that, the survey for users can't be conducted. Physical and mechanical tests are going to be done after dismantling the structure in order to compare their properties with the unused planks and beams.

Figure 100: Distances between fixed points and the mid points of the beams.

Date	Days	Height in m			
		Point -> 1	2	3	4
12/06/2021	0	1.794	1.616	1.644	1.982
17/06/2021	5	1.792	1.609	1.639	1.976
21/06/2021	9	1.790	1.604	1.635	1.978
25/06/2021	13	1.789	1.603	1.633	1.974
06/07/2021	24	1.792	1.607	1.637	1.976
15/07/2021	33	1.790	1.603	1.638	1.979
20/07/2021	38	1.792	1.602	1.628	1.979
02/08/2021	51	1.791	1.600	1.626	1.976
10/08/2021	59	1.793	1.600	1.630	1.975
19/08/2021	68	1.786	1.599	1.626	1.974
31/08/2021	80	1.789	1.598	1.628	1.974
10/09/2021	90	1.792	1.600	1.630	1.973
22/09/2021	102	1.796	1.602	1.631	1.973

28/09/2021	108	1.79	1.598	1.627	1.972
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Table 32: Changes in heights over time

Figure 101: Distances from 'Point 1' over time

Figure 102: Distances from 'Point 2' over time

Figure 103: Distances from 'Point 3' over time

Figure 104: Distances from 'Point 4' over time

Dismantling Construction Building Products and Conducting Surveys at Cranfield University

Dismantling of the shelter

Dismantling of the structure was done after 10 months since its construction. The same University engineering team that did the construction carried out the dismantling. For this, the planks on the roof were removed first and this was followed by the removal of the planks on the walls (Figure 105). The unscrewing of planks and beams was easy, and it was similar to timber materials (Figure 106:). The team who dismantled the structure did not face any particular issues with during the dismantling.

Two people involved for the job for 4 hours. (8 man-hours). Considerable health and safety measures were not taken as it was not considered as 'working height'. Both men were using a ladder and a drill as tools to unscrew the structure. As the engineering team says, the beams could reuse unless they have bended and the defect of the cross-section. But no defects were seen on plank components. In general, the dismantling of the structure was not a complicated process.

Deformations of the planks removed from the structure were not seen, though dismantled beams were bowed and their cross-sections were deformed. This was most likely due to the outdoor weather conditions, stress, UV lights etc.

The cross-sections of beams were deformed during their life. This effect was seen in the beams as well as in the pillars. This is not surprising as the material used for beams and pillars was identical.

Figure 105: Dismantled shelter structure

Figure 106: Unscrewed planks

Figure 107: Bowing effect of the beams

The bowing effect of beams remained the same after dismantling the shelter and was approximately 10 mm.

Figure 108: Deformation effect of the cross-sections of beams and pillars.

Figure 109: Cross-section of a beam of the dismantled structure

Figure 110: Cross-section of a beam of the dismantled structure

The planks and beams were taken by a local waste management company, Cawleys¹. They segregate waste materials and try to recycle it when possible. The University expectations are that the material will not end up as landfills.

The university also has some leftover planks and beams. These are going to be used for outdoor applications as needed.

Conducting surveys

Survey for constructors

This section below reports the Survey for the Constructors and the results. The survey was answered by the Maintenance manager of the University taking the inputs from the team who constructed the outdoor structure.

The survey for constructors consists of 11 multiple choice questions in order to identify constructors' point of view on the project, material, willingness to buy recycled materials etc. From the constructors' point of view, they are very happy about the concept and all the other aspects. They also mentioned that the drilling and screwing of the planks and beams were a bit harder than when performed on other composite materials that they have already worked with.

Answers for the Survey for Constructors

The Cranfield University is partner in the European Commission research project [ECOBULK](https://www.ecobulk.eu). This project aims to develop innovative products in a

¹ <https://www.cawleys.co.uk/>

circular economy perspective. Different partners are currently working on new materials for construction with recycled content. One of these products is the shelter unit you help building recently at the Cranfield University.

We would appreciate your help to identify your perception of recycled composite materials in construction.

Please be aware that your answers are anonymous, and that no personal information will be requested during this survey.

1. "I agree to answer this survey, part of the European Commission research project [ECOBULK](#). It is clear to me that my answers are anonymous, and I will not be asked to share any personal information". Please tick.

Yes P

No

2. Indicate how aware and concern you are of the following issues (Options: 1 - Not at all concerned, 2 - slightly concerned, 3 - moderately concerned, 4 - very concerned, 5 - extremely concerned, 6 - No opinion): Please enter the number for each.

- Waste management/disposal 3
- Pollution by single use plastic 2
- Recycling of plastics 2
- Recycling of large bulky waste (e.g., from construction) 3
- Recycling of composite materials (glass fibre, carbon fibre, others) 2
- Reuse and repurposing of products 2

3. For each of the following statements, select whether you 1 - strongly agree, 2 - agree, 3 - neither agree or 4 - disagree, 5 - disagree, or 6 - strongly disagree. Please enter the number for each.

- The UK as a whole generates too much waste 1
- Your office/business is generating too much waste 1
- Your office/business make efforts to reduce the amount of waste and recycle more 2
- Your household generates too much waste 2
- Your household make efforts to reduce the amount of waste and recycle more 2

4. For these materials, state whether you think it is critical to have, or not, mainstream recycling capabilities. Please tick all if you think that it is critical.

Steel P

Aluminium P

Glass P

Soft plastic (plastics that can be crunched) P

- Composite materials (glass fibre, carbon fibre, others)P
- Hard plastic (plastics that can't be crunched) P
- Paper/wood/cardboard P
- Textiles P

5. Does a product containing recycled material prevent you from buying, renting or leasing it for your business? Please tick.

- Yes
- No
- Sometimes or maybe P
- No opinion

6. If yes, maybe or sometimes, why? (Several answers possible)

- Inferior quality of the product P
- Less appealing look of the product
- Difficulties to find such products P
- Lack of information about the proportion of recycled content
- Inferior lifespan
- Higher cost P
- Other
- Never thought about this

7. Which product categories would you be likely to buy, rent or lease for your business knowing that they contain recycled materials? (Select more than one if applicable)

- Clothing (e.g., work trousers or shoes)
- Tools and electronics P
- Vehicle parts / equipment P
- Construction material P
- Consumables
- Others

8. If you were to buy, rent or lease any product that contains recycled material for your business, which of the following would you find to be the most important aspect, when compared with those without any recycled material? Several answers are possible.

That the quality of the product with recycled material is the same or higher
P

That the cost of the product with recycled material is the same or lower
P

That no additional training is required to handle the product with recycled material

That no additional tools/consumables are required to handle the product with recycled material

No opinion

9. Does knowing that the material used for the construction of the shelter at Cranfield University contained recycled materials make the space's image better, lower or similar? Please tick one.

Better

Similar P

Lower

No opinion

10. For each of the following statements about the construction material used in the shelter, select whether you 1 - strongly agree, 2 - agree, 3 - neither agree or disagree, 4 - disagree, or 5 - strongly disagree. Please put the number for each.

- It was easy to work with 5
- It was similar to working with wood 5
- The machines and tools used for traditional materials worked well with it 4
- It was easy to make joints with 5
- You would not mind working with similar materials in the future 4

10. When choosing between two different products/supplies for construction, how likely is it that sustainability factors would affect your decision? Please tick one.

Very likely

Likely

Equally likely P

Unlikely

Very unlikely

No opinion

11. How likely are you to buy, rent or lease (Options: 1 - Very likely, 2 - likely, 3 - equally likely, 4 - unlikely, 5 - very unlikely? 6 - no opinion). Please put the number for each.

- A more costly, environmentally friendly product over a cheaper version 4
- A product made from recycled materials over one with fully virgin material 3
- A refurbished cheaper product over a fully new more expensive one 3

Thank you so much for your sharing with us. For more information about the [ECOBULK](#) project.

Survey for users

The end user survey consists of 16 questions including multiple choice questions, and short answer questions. The ideas of the general public about purchasing, using of products made from recycled material are asked in the questionnaire. Unfortunately, this was not done due to the health and safety issues as a result of bending the beams.

Conclusion

Cranfield University constructed the Ecobulk outdoor shelter using the planks and beams provided, exactly according to the plan provided. After construction of the structure, the bowing effect of the beams due to the weight of the horizontal and vertical planks was seen. It was observed over time using a laser measurer. The effect of rain increased the bowing effect, and it was reversed during sunny days.

Due to the bowing effect of beams, the structure was not allowed for the public considering health and safety factors. It was dismantled after about 10 months of construction. The dismantling process was easy as a dismantling of a timber structure. The dismantled planks and beams were taken by a waste management company for recycling purposes.

3.3.4. Coventry University demo site

Coventry University was selected as one of the demonstration sites in the UK to showcase the ECOBULK outdoor shelter and indoor furniture. Different sites and locations were analysed and evaluated for the best and optimal location for the demonstrations, ensuring a high level of stakeholder's engagement and user engagement to truly get the best feedback and results of the products and materials.

Figure 111: Singer Halls Student Accommodation and Godiva Place Student Accommodation

Figure 112: Bishop Gate Student Accommodation and The Cycle Works Student Accommodation

These were the shortlisted sites for the installation of the indoor bedroom furniture, with student accommodation selected to be the ideal scenario for testing as the material will be used on a day-to-day basis.

Figure 113: The Hub

The Hub at Coventry University was selected for the indoor furniture pertaining to sofas, chairs, and tables for the communal areas.

With the different demonstration sites analysed with the University Estates Teams and the student accommodations team, the overall agreement and

acceptance of selecting Singer Hall and The John Laing Building to be used for the demonstrations for the indoor and outdoor shelter of the ECOBULK project.

Regarding the outdoor furniture, Singer Hall is demonstrating at the following location:

Figure 114: Singer Hall Shelter Location Map

Figure 115: Singer Hall Potential Shelter Location

This will allow the continuous accessibility to students and staff members. The hub was also selected for the indoor furniture in the following locations:

Figure 116: Location in The Hub for indoor furniture

Procedure pre-installation

In comparison to the process the other two UK Universities, Coventry University had to undertake a different approach and process for the installation of the outdoor furniture. With Coventry University being a city university rather than a campus university such as Warwick and Cranfield, different and strict procedures and processes had to be followed.

When looking at the shelter installation, the Estates department needed to be consulted regarding the site location. Several sites were drawn up to be potential demonstrations, with each site needing to go through some vigorous checks to ensure the site being appropriate for the installation. This procedure includes several site visits and checks from the Estates regarding the underground services, other items, and the surrounding areas. Depending on the area chosen, the suitable demo site administrators and facility managers had to be consulted to attain permission and for several other checks such as traffic, future plans and other aspects which may be relevant and of importance to the installation. Moreover, the University security team had to be consulted regarding the health and safety aspect of the installation shelter in terms of student and staff safety as well as the protection from external users considering the area is accessible by the public. A Tree Protection Order

(TPO) checks were completed for the site and found the site to be outside the conservation area and with the site have no TPO's.

Finalising the site, confirmation was required from seniors managing the Estate and therefore going forward with the installation, other members of the Estate team were contacted for further checks. From the Environmental team, a topography survey was required as the site selected was a green area with trees in the surroundings. A topography survey had to be carried out and an arboriculturist had to be appointed to carry out a formal survey/impact assessment. Furthermore, Planning Permission was required from Coventry City Council for the installation to go ahead, due the University being a city campus. Along with this the following had to be completed:

- Record Utility Pack

Once this stage of the process was completed, a planning application was submitted to the council which outlined the plans for the shelter installations. The following documentation had to be submitted:

- A drawing/document register

Drawing Number	Drawing Name	Date				
		26/04/2021	30/04/2021	03/05/2021		
ECOBULK-COV-100	Singer Hall Location Plan - 1:2500	P01				
ECOBULK-COV-101	Singer Hall Location Plan - 1:1250	P01				
ECOBULK-COV-102	Singer Hall Site Plan - 1:250	P01				
ECOBULK-COV-103	Ecobulk Design Access Statement	P01				
ECOBULK-COV-104	Ecobulk Heritage Statement	P01				
ECOBULK-COV-105	Singer Derwent 2RegisterPlanWM705237-2	P01				
ECOBULK-COV-106	singer derwent raglan1RegisterPlanWM755756	P01				
ECOBULK-COV-107	Singer HallsRegisterPlanWM571077-2	P01				
ECOBULK-COV-108	Coventry University Shelter	P01				
ECOBULK-COV-109	Ecobulk_outdoorshelter_Connection details01	P01				

Figure 119: Shelter Installation Drawing Register

Figure 120: Location plan at 1:1250

Figure 121: Location Plan at 1:2500

Figure 122: Site Plan at 1:250

- Design Access Statement

Design Access Statement

Author: Mr Kassim Caratella

Author's Position: Research Fellow – Institute of Future Transport and Cities

Date Issued: 26/04/2021

Revision Number: A

Introduction:

The purpose of this report is to illustrate and demonstrate design that is accessible and inclusive to all.

Statement

A multi-use shelter will be installed externally at the Singer Hall site as part of an EU funded research project to demonstrate the use of second life materials in designing construction materials.

Singer Hall student accommodation is located in Coventry City Centre, referring to the location and site plans to view the existing and proposed development plans. The shelter will be of 20m² with pictures of the proposed installation below:

Figure 123: Images of the UK shelter installation in Coventry

In terms of access, no issues will arise from the installation as the shelter will be installed on external ground area as can be seen below:

Figure 124: Plan view of the site of the installation

Figure 125: View of the area of the shelter installation

The approach around the site will not change due to this development and therefore is not considered an issue. No car-parking, setting down points, or location dropped kerbs will be obstructed through the installation.

- Title Deeds

Title Number : WM705237

This title is dealt with by HM Land Registry, Coventry Office.

The following extract contains information taken from the register of the above title number. A full copy of the register accompanies this document and you should read that in order to be sure that these brief details are complete.

Neither this extract nor the full copy is an 'Official Copy' of the register. An official copy of the register is admissible in evidence in a court to the same extent as the original. A person is entitled to be indemnified by the registrar if he or she suffers loss by reason of a mistake in an official copy.

This extract shows information current on 25 APR 2018 at 12:16:30 and so does not take account of any application made after that time even if pending in HM Land Registry when this extract was issued.

REGISTER EXTRACT

Title Number	: WM705237
Address of Property	: Workshop premises at 19-33 (odd only) at Raglan Street, Coventry
Price Stated	: Not Available
Registered Owner(s)	: COVENTRY UNIVERSITY HIGHER EDUCATION CORPORATION a higher education corporation of Priory Street, Coventry CV1 5FB.
Lender(s)	: None

- Drawings of existing, proposed which reference the site plan & location plan.
- Existing Images. (Covered in Design Access Statement)
- Heritage statement

Heritage Statement

Author: Mr Kassim Caratella

Author's Position: Research Fellow – Institute of Future Transport and Cities

Date Issued: 26/04/2021

Revision Number: A

Introduction:

The purpose of this report is to illustrate the thought process of the Heritage for the proposed shelter installation at Singer Hall.

Statement

During the works of the project, a soft dig will take place, in the unlikely event that any artefacts and the like are found.

The planning application process can take up to 12 weeks and with the submission of all the documentation as well as some minor changes when liaising with the local authority, Coventry University were able to receive the official planning acceptance for us to start the construction of the shelter.

Installation Process

Once the planning application was successful and granted, the next steps were to gain quotes from different contractors which are contracted to Coventry University. Following the details of the drawings and the proposed foundation details, it was agreed between Estates, contractors, and the structural engineers to develop pad foundations instead of a strip foundation. This was due to the ground level being at a slope and would allow the structure to be set up better with this foundation detail. Furthermore, this allows the contractor to work quickly and efficiently, with pad foundations being less labour intensive, cheaper and will structurally support the shelter.

During the commencement of the construction process, the ground was dug to allow for the pad foundations to be filled onsite. The process included marking out the foundations in respect to the drawings provided by the architect (as can be seen from the images below):

Figure 126: Outlining the pad foundation positioning

Figure 127: Size of the pad foundation for the shelter

Once the foundations were dug to the specific depth, width and length, for the concrete to be poured and to set, formwork had to be created on site.

Figure 128: Filling of the pad foundation with concrete

Figure 129: Formwork for the pad foundations

Once the curing was in process, the contractors went to collect the rest of the materials to prepare for the construction of the shelter. The material was received in the following manner:

Figure 130: EcoBulk shelter pieces in storage

One of the main comments from the contractors when the shelter came to site was the lack of directions and instructions in terms of installation. There are very similar pieces and although from a manufacturing standpoint, it is efficient, the contractors found it was difficult to determine which component went where due to them being same but being different sizes. Attempting to sort and map out the right pieces for the structure was time consuming and added days to the construction process. The architectural drawings were not sufficient to make the judgements of the components.

Figure 131: Shelter slat pieces on site

During the sorting process, the contractors were labelling each of the pieces to determine which of the components fit together (see image below). This allowed the contractors, to get the build quickly and efficiently and ensuring the wrong components were not put together.

Figure 132: Erection of the main structure

Once the components were sorted, they were attached to the foundations and each other using the specified brackets and fittings outlined by the designers.

Figure 133: Installation of main structure to pad foundations

As the construction progressed with no clear fitting instructions, the decision was taken by the contractors to shore up the reinforcement by using additional brackets at the base of the structure as can be seen in the above images.

Figure 134: Timber support for the installation

Furthermore, when installing the main frame of the building, timber support beams were required to ensure the structural integrity of the shelter whilst the shelter was being put up. It was noted by the contractors, the support was quintessential, a without them, the structure was already incurring some bending.

Continuing with the construction of the shelter, once the main frame was complete, the contractors set on sorting the slats in terms of their positioning due to them being different sizes. Furthermore, each individual slat required two brackets, one at the top and one at the bottom (see image below). This led to the time-consuming process of installing them on all the slats. This led to significant time delays which delayed the completion of the shelter. For future purposes, the slats should be manufactured with premade holes for the ease of the contractors to complete the installation in a timely manner.

One of the issues when installing the slats onto the shelter, was the distance between each of them. The drawing suggested a gap of 90mm between each one, however the measurement was not as accurate as it was not possible to install the slats with the specified brackets. This was not a major obstacle or barrier as the contractors on site were able to spread the spacing, however going forward, when going to market, the set of instructions will need to be

Figure 135: Bracket fixings to slats

more accurately represented.

Figure 136: Front view of completed shelter

Figure 137: Inside view of completed shelter

Figure 138: View of rear of shelter

The installation process took 8 days to complete, and the finished product came out better than expected. Positive responses were deemed from passing students as well as contractors and the Estates Team. The shelter is going to be in place for the foreseeable future for students and staff to continue use with a better insight into it during the spring/summer seasons.

Public Perception Study

As the EcoBulk shelter at the demonstration was completed, Coventry University have developed and distributed a user engagement study to determine the user perception on Circular Economy, sustainability, and the use of second life products. This is being done to understand how people perceive second life of materials and what is or needs to be required to encourage people to engage with using these types of products and to understand what needs to be done to make the products more marketable for regular use. This will also enable us to see how the quality of the product is on a day-to-day use basis and if users can see vast differences between the products.

The methodology we have selected is qualitative and quantitative as we are looking to reach out to as many stakeholders as possible to get their views and feedback. The stakeholders we are engaging with are the following:

- CU Procurement Team
- CU Students
- CU Staff and Academics

- Futurelets (Private student accommodation)
- CU Estates
- CU Internal installers
- External Procurement
- External Installers

Internally, we have discussed the project with internal Facility Managers and Operators, which will allow us to develop an internal workshop to discuss the aspect of Circular Economy and second life use of materials for products and how can they be integrated within the university system and processes in terms of procurement strategies, environmental strategies, and Estates management.

The screenshot shows a questionnaire interface with the following content:

- Header: p.2 EcoBulk Questionnaire (with a Jump dropdown)
- Section: Circular Economy and ECOBULK Project
- Question 4: Text input field "What is your current role at Coventry University?"
- Question 5: Radio button question "Are you aware of the Circular Economy concept?" with "Yes" and "No" options.
- Question 6: Rating scale question "Please rate your level of awareness and concern of the following issues:"

	Not at all concerned	Slightly concerned	Moderately concerned	Very concerned	Extremely concerned	No opinion
Waste management/disposal	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Pollution by single use plastic	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Recycling of plastics	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Recycling of large bulky waste (e.g. from construction)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Recycling of composite materials (glass fibre, carbon fibre, others)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Reuse and repurposing of products	<input type="checkbox"/>					

Figure 139: EcoBulk user questionnaire and surveys sample

Conclusion

To conclude the Coventry University installation, the process has taken 8 days to complete, with a success build. Aesthetically, it has been very pleasing, with many compliments given by staff, students, and members of the Estates team. There were, however, a considerable amount of constructive feedback, such as having a better set of direction apart from the architectural drawings and finding an easier method for the installation of the brackets, e.g., manufacturing the panels with the holes already in. This will be detailed within the stakeholder engagement and user questionnaires in WP8.

A video was produced by Coventry University demonstrating the stages of constructing successfully the shelter from start till end. link <https://we.tl/t-og8h49gIYF>

3.4 LIPOR demonstrator, Portugal

3.3.5. Material and parts sourcing

Understanding the sunny and hot climate conditions in Portugal, the polymer matrix base was changed from more ductile and flexible polyethylene (PE) used in Nordic countries into more rigid and stiff polypropylene (PP). It is known that rigidity of thermoplastic materials i.e. the flexural modulus (E) are temperature dependent and maintaining sufficient stiffness especially in structural load bearing components beams and pillars in shelters is of concern and must taken into account.

The choice of colour made by Lipor was beige which is achieved in mixed composites by combining three colour additives namely carbon black, titanium dioxide white and yellow iron oxide. Beige is also optimal for maintaining the original light colour without notable colour fading in sunny weather conditions.

The extruded profiles needed for Lipor constructions made and supplied by Conenor are the following;

- solid planks 120x30mm (used also 3x bolted together for foundations)
- hollow planks 120x28mm (lighter weight for roofing structure)
- square tubes 125x125mm for load bearing beams and pillars

UV-stabilization additive was used to provide protection against sun light degradation.

Figure 140: Recycled composites at Conenor ready for shipment to Lipor

3.3.6.Design

The design of all structures at Lipor were made in collaboration between Lipor and local architect design agency Inbict Arquitectura Lda. It must be noted at the time of making the architectural designs in the project what to construct, there was not available yet any data of the upcoming Conenor component mechanical performance.

The space available for installing the building components is at the Lipor's closed landfill. This area has been converted in a park with an area of approximately 19 ha, and were created zones for recreation and training that can be used by the population of Greater Porto.

Figure 141: Lipor adventure Park

It is possible to see in the following images the final sketch of the equipments that were installed.

Figure 142: Tree Bench, Recycling Bin Shelter, Drinking Fountain Shelter

3.3.7.Preparation

During the material installation phase, it was necessary to adapt the project according to the technical information available, and it was necessary promote adjustments on site.

These improvements and changes were discussed by the project team with Conenor.

To guarantee the quality and reliability of the installations, it was necessary to verify key factors: structures, foundations, weights, fasteners.

The main actors in the different components of the project are identified below:

- Fastener Selection – TUDELFT, CONENOR
- Structural Design – LIPOR
- Component’s supplier - CONENOR
- Construction and assembling - LIPOR
- Implement a labelling System – ITENE, UPC

Figure 143: Arrival of materials in Lipor-Portugal, from Conenor-Finland

3.3.8.Installation and assembling

The installation phase took place between May and November 2020.

This period is the result of having developed a non-sequential process, as several corrections to the project were necessary to ensure the stability and safety of the equipment. it was even necessary to receive extra materials from Conenor to make the security reinforcements possible.

At this stage, several difficulties related to production, installation, safety and assembly times were identified:

1. The sketch's team redesign the project, according the productions adjustments:
 - Panels dimensions (from 15mm to 10mm) >> less weight
 - Acceptance of materials range with tolerances +/- 3mm
 - Solid post/pillar to Hollow pillars
 - Safety requirements – alterations in the floor surface
2. Difficulties Related with the assembly:
 - Time to assembly the equipment's (prevision: 30-45 days)
 - Poor estimation of assembly costs, and time required (higher budget to installation)
 - The assembly process and connection elements were carried out on site
 - Equipment's are innovative and never has been construct noting so complex with these materials
 - Need of time to test the construction techniques and fasteners

The following images represent the various stages and construction techniques associated with the various installations:

Figure 144: Structures and foundations, before the assembling

Figure 145: Connection detail of the Recycling Bin Shelter

Figure 146: Connection detail and reinforce of the Drinking Fountain Shelter

Figure 147: Connection detail of the Tree Bench

Figure 148: Finished three structures at Lipor Park, Oporto, Portugal

During installation, the assembly times of the various activities carried out were recorded, as well the assembly methods. Changes in the methodology for assembling and reinforcing structures increased the time for the installation.

The records are shown in the table below:

Assembly check list

Phases	Task / Activitie	Recycling Bin Shelter	Tree Bench	Drinking Fountain Shelter	Notes
1	Material Preparation	470	690	420	Cut and shape steel. Clean and cut, wood and manufacture formwork.
	Local Instalacion Activities	40	150	90	Delimitation of the construction site. Deforestation and cleaning of the land, alignments and quotas
	Foundation Scavation	120	150	145	Manual and mechanical excavation, up to the base of the cleaning concrete, from the foundation intel
	Concrete Foundation	725	960	1520	Cleaning concrete application. Assembly and support of formwork. Steel armor frame and assembly. Applying concrete to the foundation.
Time (minutes)		1355	1950	2175	
2	Pilar's Fixations	240	1720	460	Includes application of metallic connection elements (brackets and screws).
	Floor Structure			460	Includes application of metallic connection elements (brackets and screws).
	Floor Assembly	60		2225	Includes application of metallic connection elements (brackets and screws).
	Structures Cover	900	400	1200	Includes application of metallic connection elements (brackets and screws). BEVERAGE: Includes the mechanical lifting of the roof elements.
	General Assembly Activities	1020	2040	450	
	Fastners Aplication				
	Cuttting Activities		400		
	Final Arrengments	120		120	
	Foundations Reinforcement	240	2100		Increase in the dimensions of foundations in the Ecoporto and increase in the number of foundations in the Tree.
	Structural Reinforcements	1200	980	960	Adding pillars and beams, at Ecoporto and Bebedouro, connected by metallic connecting elements (hardware and screws). Fixation of 12 gantries to the new foundations, in the Tree, connected by metallic elements (squares and screws).
Time (minutes)		3780	7640	5875	
Total Time (minutes)		5135	9590	8050	
Total Time (days)		11	20	17	Geral calculation considering 2 workers per day

Table 33: Lipor Assembly check list

About the installation of this equipment's, we can **conclude** the following:

a) the initial objective of installing the equipment was fulfilled;

- b) conditions of safety and use of equipment are guaranteed;
- c) there is a high need for labor for the installation, which may affect the economic viability of the studied solutions;
- d) the materials used are of high quality, and currently meet the necessary requirements.

3.3.9. Use phase and questionnaire

Once the construction prototypes were installed, the QR plates were put in place as can be seen in Figure 149, Figure 150, and Figure 151.

Figure 149: Drinking fountain with QR code.

Figure 150: Tree bench with QR code.

Figure 151: Recycling bin shelter with QR code.

With this QR codes it is possible to access the datasheets of the deployed prototypes and also answer a survey for gathering end-user feedback through the End-User and Stakeholder Platform. The description, properties and survey for the tree bench prototype can be seen in Figure 152 and Figure 153.

ECOBULK Label Scanner Stakeholder test Profile Logout

Scan other product

Tree Bench Shelter

This tree bench shelter has been built using recycled material coming from wind turbine blades among other sources of GFRP composite waste. Additionally, it may also contain wood particles and PP/PE particles in varying conditions. The surface finishing on the planks is achieved by a multi-layer extrusion process where two different formulations (i.e. one for the surface and another for the core) are extruded simultaneously to produce the material and the colour variations in the surface are achieved using pigments added to the surface composite formulation. The tree bench shelter serves as an example and demonstrator of these new manufacturing processes with high content in recycled materials.

Answer Survey

ECOBULK Label Scanner Stakeholder test Profile Logout

Stakeholder test

core) are extruded simultaneously to produce the material and the colour variations in the surface are achieved using pigments added to the surface composite formulation. The tree bench shelter serves as an example and demonstrator of these new manufacturing processes with high content in recycled materials.

Answer Survey

General information

Product name	Tree Bench Shelter
Manufacturer	Conenor
ManufacturerId	61961fc27ea12e4cf7a075b0
Product code	conenor_002
Width	6 m
Height	2.6 m
Length	6.25 m

Customer information

Product information [Download](#)

User manual [Download](#)

Product characteristics

FRP-waste from EoL wind turbine blades	35 %
Recycled wood fibres (nordic pine)	28 %
Recycled PP (mixed colors)	30 %
Polymeric additives	7 %

Figure 152: End-user and stakeholder platform: survey

The screenshot shows a mobile application interface for a survey. At the top, there is a teal header with the ECOBULK logo and a 'Label Scanner' icon. Below the header, a dark blue bar contains 'Stakeholder test', a 'Profile' icon, and a 'Logout' button. The main content area is a white card titled 'Outdoor Furniture' with a 'Cancel' button in the top right. The card contains two survey questions:

Talking about the product you're using

11. Knowing that the structure is built using recycled materials make the space's image better?

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neither Agree nor Disagree
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

12. Does the material used in the structure affect your experience? *

- Yes
- No

At the bottom of the card, there are two sections: 'Product information' with a 'Download' button, and 'User manual' with a 'Download' button. Below the card, a 'Product characteristics' link is partially visible.

Figure 153: End-user and stakeholder platform: survey

3.4. FCBA demonstrator, France

3.4.1. Outdoor Benches and Seats

Outdoor furniture standards

According to the NF P99-650 standard, issued in 2013, street furniture must comply with several guidelines.

In terms of safety, the surface appearance, stability and solidity must be guaranteed by the furniture.

The furniture must not show any breakage or deformation (poorly fixed parts, lack of seat slats, etc.) that could lead to serious accidents.

In terms of maintenance, street furniture is constantly maintained:

- to avoid that it gets dirty and causes health problems to the users
- to be repaired and retouch damage caused by vandalism
- to ensure the duration of use

Two French companies, not partners of ECOBULK, have shown some interest to test some solutions developed by CONENOR.

Collaboration with manufacturer Grosfillex

The company Grosfillex mainly produces injected products, but in order to be able to explore new materials they have made two bench versions with the material of Conenor. The first prototype was made with boards 1cm thick, 12 cm wide and 45 cm long. According to their reflection, the more recycled material there was, the better.

Grosfillex process

Figure 154: Grosfillex process

To evaluate the prototypes, we placed them in a circle of the product life cycle, in order to see the positive and negative points for further improvement of the product.

very solid

too heavy

poor design

Figure 155: Prototype n.2 Small Bench

This small bench is very heavy but very solid. The small bench weighs 56kg. The shape of the bench is not very attractive; however, the visual play between the empty and full forms gives a rather attractive appearance. Grosfillex has made a second version of the same bench, but in a larger size.

Figure 156: Version 2 large bench (150x 43 x 45 mm)

Figure 157: Iteration cycle of bench design

The third prototype was made with thicker (2.5 cm) solid boards and hollow boards. For this bench the technicians had more difficulty working with the boards because of their fragility when drilling and cutting them. (measurements 150x45x43 – poids 50kg)

Figure 158: Third prototype

For this prototype the weight has decreased (50kg), we have a more airy design, it remains a solid bench but, the rounded boards are not very comfortable.

Figure 159: Result of prototyping life cycle

Mechanical tests were run on the prototype in the laboratories of FCBA.

Discussions are still ongoing to maybe another product like a garden house for further experiments.

Figure 160: Grosfillex garden house images

Our exchanges with Grosfillex could not continue properly because of the Covid 19 health crisis. However, we got back to them on May 11th, end of the lockdown phase in France. This delicate situation postponed our work, since Grosfillex would be fully available for making and testing new prototypes from September onwards.

Collaboration with manufacturer Sineu graff

The Sineu graff company manufactures street furniture (benches, urban cleanliness, public sports areas, tree protection grids, etc.). Street furniture must comply with specific standards in public spaces (NFP 99 610 and NFP 99 650). In addition to the monitoring of the basic standards, companies can have a protocol to evaluate the material that will be used in the products. This is the case of Sineu graff which applies a three-step protocol to validate or not the material.

The following image illustrates the steps that Sineu graff followed for this first experimentation with Conenor's material.

Figure 161: Steps followed by Sineu graff

Sineu graff applies three prerequisites to test these products, in order to offer its customers high-performance products with a choice of colour and ease of processing. If the material does not pass the first step then there is no prototyping.

● flexural test
 Norme NFP
 99610

Sineugraff pre requirements for materials :

- 1 flexural test
- 2 range of colors
- 3 section choice (length, width, thickness)

Sineugraff feedback :
 look for mechanical characteristics similar to wood

Figure 162: Sineugraff bending test

Conenor's material in the plank dimensions 120x30mm did not pass the first test (flexural test). (Explanation of the test see picture below)

Figure 163: Sineugraff test arrangement

After a longer exchange with Sineu graff we managed to find a product range in their urban bench catalogue that could allow the Conenor material to be tested. The company will make a bench, a chair and a bench from the OPTIMA range.

Figure 164: OPTIMA product range

You can find below a list of the assembly constraints the material will be subjected to, for these models:

- Assembly of the legs at the ends of the planks -> bending stress on the planks at the most unfavourable, 2m

Figure 165: OPTIMA Bench 2m

- Wooden planks are fixed to the legs with M08 metric screws on a wooden insert that has been pre-mounted under the planks and positioned at the ends.

Figure 166: Bench wooden insert

- Possibility to add median reinforcements to connect the boards together on the median plank (mid-length). It is a flat iron -> fixed with wood screws -> One first for the seat boards and if necessary, a second for the backrest boards.

Figure 167: Flat iron in the middle of the bench

- Section of the boards for this OPTIMA range 160 mm x 38 mm thick - board length 2m. However, Sineu graff will use the boards sent by Conenor 140 x 30 mm and 2m.

New boards have been manufactured by Conenor with modifications to the content to make them more resistant. We have planned to do internal tests to compare our results with those of Sineu graff.

We received the boards from Conenor the week the lockdown started in France.

Our exchanges with the Sineu graff company did not continue because of the sanitary crisis of Covid 19. As for Grosfillex, we got back in touch with them when companies officially took over on May 11th. For this case, the manufacture of the prototypes is planned for the end of July or the beginning of September.

Working with new materials is always a challenge because you have to learn how to handle it and try to imagine it, in a product that can be sold.

Companies go through a stage of discovery of the material and sometimes, disappointment because the material is not more, or as good as, conventional materials.

That is also why institutes like FCBA are crucial in the guidance of companies, since they can facilitate a better knowledge on new recycled materials and encourage industrials to include them in their production schemes. It is through prototyping and the understanding of recycled materials that the opinion of companies changes and opens up new perspectives.

The aims of this demonstrator was to collaborate with a company who made outdoor furniture. We have chosen with the furniture company which collection could be interesting to test the material and interesting for sell.

For Sineu graff the new material must respond to different points like: aesthetic (have the possibility to choose different colours and texture), security and mechanical performance. In addition to that, they make a "vandalism test" (Sineu graff internal test) to be sure the material can be resist in the outdoor area.

Optima Chair (450 x 566 x 562 mm)

Figure 168: OPTIMA Chair with Ecobulk planks

Optima bench seat (1800 x 328 mm)

For this prototype, we had different issues. Normally we have to make two bench, but because of the deformation of the board, we decided to make just one bench. Even Sineu graff sell more the big benches, the idea was to experiment with the material and see the possibilities, not just stop at the first difficulty. The planks were twisted.

Figure 169: OPTIMA Bench 1800mm with Ecobulk planks

To prevent the boards from sagging, we have added three steel reinforcements. These reinforcements gave the boards more stability but the sagging did not disappear.

Because the length of the bench is an important selling point for the furniture manufacturer, we carried out a final test. We added a metal frame to the middle of the bench. (Image a rajouter)

We explored others possibilities for this material. We made two littles benches for kids but they can used for adults as well.

Figure 170: OPTIMA Bench 800mm with Ecobulk planks

This bench measures 80 x 40 cm and the structure is a steel metallic frame. As we can see in these pictures, we have a deformation but sagging disappear due to the measure of the bench.

The little one bench measure 40 x 30 cm and the structure is a steel metallic frame. In this prototype, we do not have any deformation.

Figure 171: OPTIMA Bench 400mm with Ecobulk planks

The test with users was on going

Figure 172: Urban furniture composed of a bench, a medium bench for adults, a small bench for children and a chair. Slats made mainly from 10% wood (pine) 20% recycled HDPE and 20% virgin HDPE.

User experiment on final prototypes

In this experiment, the focus is on the sensorial perception of the outdoor furniture manufactured. The aim is to assess users feedback regarding the use of the furniture.

This experiment lead in France was influenced by the sanitary crisis will the following adaptations:

- The furniture was installed in a private location instead of a public facility
- The experiment started after several lockdowns, in June 2021

Sixteen participants were selected to test the furniture in the real conditions of its future use, with 50% of female and 50% of male.

Figure 173: Age of participants collecting user experiments

General perception

Ten questions were asked to the participants.

About the general aesthetics of the products the first question was: "Do you like the aesthetics of the products?"

Figure 174: Answers to the question: do you like the aesthetics of the products

For the 4 products presented, the chair and the bench for adults are quite popular, unlike the small bench for children.

Beside the quantitative answers different comments were made: "Sharp edges", "Basic design", "Discreet furniture for spaces in nature", "Visual aspect of the edges not very aesthetic", "Beware of slats used vertically: dirt deposits", "Colour of the slats not very attractive", "Likes the design of the

chair”, “Shame that the inner edge of the slats (on the seats) is not identical to the visible edge”.

The users were also asked to rate from “Not at all” to “Extremely pleasant” the touch of the products.

Figure 175: Perception by touch

56% of the user found the touch of the material pleasant.

The next general question was “How would you describe the comfort of the products for outdoor furniture?”

Figure 176: Answers to the question “How would you describe the comfort of the products for outdoor furniture?”

The proportion of people find the comfort of the furniture very or suitable for outdoor furniture are 66% and 85%.

Beside the quantitative answers different comments were made:

- For the chair: "Slightly stiff", "Likes the angle of the backrest/seat", "Too much space between seat and back", "Strange tilt", "Lower back not supported", "Lacks armrests"
- For the Medium adult bench : "Bench size is not enough for two people", "Not very comfortable"
- For the Large adult bench: "Lacks a backrest for comfort", "Slight twisting of the boards"

The next question dealt with mechanic aspects: "Do you think these products are strong/resistant?"

To that question the testers believe the furniture is "very much" or "a lot" resistant, with a proportion going from 75% for the child bench to 100% for the chair.

Figure 177: Answers to the question: "Do you think these products are strong/resistant?"

Beside the quantitative answers different comments were made: "The medium bench seems less stable", "The child's bench with only two slats seems to be less resistant than the other products", "The metal structure and the panels seem to be resistant", "Solid appearance", "Thick material", "The metal structure is synonymous with solidity, but the boards of the bench less so"

A specific question was related to the children's bench: "Do you find the children's bench suitable?"

Figure 178: Answers to the question: "Do you find the children's bench suitable?"

Beside the quantitative answers different comments were made: "Size appropriate for children but usable for all", "Too high for the size of the seat", "Bench needs to be fixed to the ground", "Lack of stability", "Lacks a backrest, especially for support in case of a fall or for standing/resting", "This will depend on the age of the child, if the child is small the seat is too high", "Protruding angles", "Suitable for children from 3 to 5 years", "Enlarge the bench to have more space for two children (to play)".

Afterwards, the people were asked if they would like to see this type of furniture in different environments.

Question: "Would you like to see this type of furniture in the urban environment?"

Question: "In other outdoor spaces such as working terraces?"

"If yes, which ones?": "Garden and public places Station halls or administrative waiting area", "Dining areas in companies", "Restaurant and work terraces", "Motorway verges", "Natural areas"

Some comments were made: "Not comfortable enough to stay and work on a terrace in a company", "In natural areas, tourist sites, beaches", "In parks or gardens"

Figure 179: Answers about the likeness to have this furniture in outdoor environments

Perception of furniture according to its composition

To the question “What are the planks made of” most answerers identify the use of a synthetic resin and the presence of wood fibers. On the other hand only one user considered there was recycled content in the planks.

Figure 180: Answers to the question “What are the planks made of?”

Beside the quantitative answers different comments were made: “Interesting aesthetic appearance”, “A little rough but comfortable to sit on”, “Nice colour and feel”, “Not at all pleasant at the end of the panels”, “Aesthetics of the cut edges need to be improved”, “The material is dazzling”, “Cheap appearance”, “Does the temperature at the surface of the material change with sun?”

After that question the composition of the planks were given to the users and they were then asked for the second time “Would you like to see this type of furniture in the urban environment?” and “in other outdoor spaces?”

In that context, 87% of the respondents don’t imagine that furniture in urban environments.

Figure 181: Answers about the likeness to have this furniture in outdoor environments, knowing the composition of the plank

After that question the composition of the planks were given to the users and they were then asked for the second time "Would you like to see this type of furniture in the urban environment?" and "in other outdoor spaces?"

On the contrary, to the question "Can you imagine these panels in other types of products?"

Figure 182: Likeliness to have these planks in other types of products

Lots of products were identified by the respondents like potentially suitable for the planks: movable partitions, desks, dining tables, garden chests, garden furniture, terrace slats, picnic tables, bus shelters, cladding, facade cladding, table on motorway service areas

Too much space between backrest and seat

Photos of users during the tests.

Figure 183: Photos of users during the tests

Figure 184: Furniture with a QR code leading to the Ecobulk project page

Conclusion

In this experiment we noticed that the furniture manufactured meets some of the constraints for urban furniture. There are several areas for improvement, in terms of safety (protruding edges, rounded corners and deformation of the planks), modification of the design (size of the planks) and adaptation of the material to avoid deformation, variety of colours and roughness of the material.

Regarding the recycled aspect, users find it interesting that it is recycled material.

With regard to use, the comfort of the seat/backrest should be reviewed for the chair and also for the large bench. The size of the medium-sized adult and children's bench should be reviewed so that two people can sit on it instead of just one.

Concerning the material, several objects mentioned by the users could be considered: an adaptation of the material as well as of the design is necessary to answer in an optimal way to the final use of the object.

3.4.2.Wall Module

This part of the Ecobulk project consists of identifying new ways to recover recycled materials in construction, in particular wood construction. For this, we will start by listing the various common engineered wood elements then we will identify a wooden construction typology to introduce recycled elements as alternatives to wood materials. The criteria for choosing recycled materials are first: the expected mechanical performance, the dimensions and shapes available from manufacturers, and then we will analyze the hydrothermal performance obtained by the introduction of these recycled materials into a wooden wall.

The sawn wood consumed in European housing enters into one-floor and two-floor family houses and in apartment blocks built of bricks, stone or concrete. It is consumed either in the house itself - as a building element (in the roof structure, joists and beams covering the basement and supporting the floors and ceiling, and various framework) or in joinery (flooring, doors, windows, stairs, cupboards, etc.) - or as part of the equipment used in the erection of the house (scaffolding, and molds for concrete constructions). Of the wood that becomes a permanent part of the house, that used for the building elements is required, generally speaking, in larger dimensions and with higher strength qualities than that used for joinery.

The fact is that, till now, the use of wood as a structural element had been declined most, and that this decline was closely bound up with changed methods of construction.

Now, the new Engineered wood products, and the need of a sustainable construction, give a hopeful future to wood construction.

There are limitations on the maximum cross-sectional size and lengths of sawn timber that can be used as a structural component due to the availability of log sizes and the presence of naturally occurring defects in the timber.

These defects can be cut out and the timber reconstituted using engineered wood techniques such as finger jointing (Figure 185) to create longer lengths of timber of an assured strength grade, or laminating to form a homogeneous timber section. Combinations of timber or laminated sections with different materials such as wood-based boards or metal elements are used to create

'engineered wood products' (EWPs) whose maximum size is limited only by manufacturing, handling and transportation constraints.

Figure 185: Finger jointing of timber

In addition to engineered wood products, there are reconstituted board products that comprise smaller wood-based strands and fibers re-formed into panel products. These have structural applications but are also used extensively in the furniture-making and packaging industries.

Engineered wood products, timber and board products

EWPs including glued laminated timber, finger joints, plywood, stressed skin panels, mechanically and adhesive bonded web beams and connected and nail plated trusses, have been in existence for at least 40 years.

Recently, there have been significant developments in the range of EWPs for structural applications with materials such as laminated veneer lumber (LVL), parallel strand lumber (PSL), laminated strand lumber (LSL), prefabricated I-beams, metal web joists and 'massive' or **cross-laminated timber** (CLT) becoming more widely available.

These EWPs are typically manufactured by adhesively laminating together smaller softwood sections or laminates (e.g. glulam and CLT) or veneers or strands of timber (e.g. LVL, LSL and PSL). The varying performance of EWPs is influenced by the size of wood component used in the product. At one end of the spectrum smaller sections of timber are laminated and finger jointed to form sections of glulam, whilst at the other end, reconstituted board products such as oriented strand boards (OSBs) and medium density fiber boards (MDFs) use small wood strands or fibers bonded together.

Figure 186: Fiber size and beam types for timber products

Thin webbed joists (I beam)

I-beams are an EWP manufactured with flanges made from softwood or LVL with glued thin webs generally made from OSB, fiber board or plywood. I-beams can be used to resist either flexural or axial loads or a combination of both.

Figure 187: Use of I beams for a floor structure

Metal web or open web joist

Open web joists are shallow parallel-chord trusses manufactured using similar techniques to that used for trussed rafters comprising a member with flanges (or chords) usually made from softwood and with metal or timber strutting to form the webs (Figure 136).

The chords (and webs where timber webs are used) are generally planed softwood graded in accordance with BS EN 14081-1. The strength class of the timber is usually C27 in accordance with BS EN 338:2009 or TR26 (whose characteristic strength values are equal to that of C27 but whose characteristic stiffness values are taken from BS5268-2:2002). The depth of the chords is generally 47mm and their widths range from 72mm to 145mm. Metal webs are typically profiled, nominal 1mm galvanised light gauge steel with a zinc coating specification of Z275.

Open web joists are principally used as a roof or floor joist element. They are often preferred to I-joists as they allow a combined services and structural zone.

Figure 188: Open web joist

Plywood

Plywood is a flat panel made by bonding together, under pressure, a number of thin layers of veneers (or plies). Plywood was the first type of EWP to be widely available.

The structural properties and strength of plywood depend mainly on the number, thickness, species and orientation of the plies.

The structural grade plywoods that are commonly used in the UK construction industry are:

- American construction and industrial plywood
- Canadian softwood plywood
- Finnish birch-faced, birch and conifer plywoods
- Birch plywood gives a good fair-faced finish and is readily persuaded into curved profiles

- Swedish softwood plywood

Plywood products are typically used for roof and floor decking applications and for wall sheathing boards.

Plywood for structural applications should be specified as “having exterior glue bond to BS EN 314-2 and veneers in compliance with BS EN 636:2003”. This replaces the previous definition for the plywood of WBP exterior grade where ‘WBP’ describes the properties of the adhesive and ‘exterior grade’ describes the durability of the outer veneers.

The characteristic strength and stiffness values for plywood for use in structural design are contained in BS EN 12369-2:2004.

Figure 189: Plywood

Laminated veneer lumber (LVL)

Laminated veneer lumber (LVL) is a structural member manufactured by bonding together thin vertical softwood veneers with their grain parallel to the longitudinal axis of the section, under heat and pressure. In some cases, cross grain veneers are incorporated to improve dimensional stability.

LVL is often used for high load applications to resist either flexural or axial loads or a combination of both. It can provide both panels and beam/column elements.

The requirements for LVL are contained in product standard BS EN 14374:2004.

Figure 190: LVL

Laminated strand lumber (LSL)

Laminated strand lumber (LSL) is a structural member made by cutting long thin strands approximately 300mm long and 0.8mm - 1.3mm thick directly from de-barked logs. The strands are blended, coated with adhesive and oriented so that they are essentially parallel to the longitudinal axis of the section before being reformed by steam-injection pressing into a solid section. LSL is used in similar applications to LVL.

Figure 191: LSL

Parallel strand lumber (PSL)

Parallel strand lumber (PSL) is a structural member made by cutting long thin strands (typically 3.2mm thick, 20mm wide and up to 3.0m long) from timber veneers. The strands are oriented so that they are essentially parallel to the longitudinal axis of the section before being coated with adhesive, fed into a continuous press, and microwave-cured. PSL is used in similar applications to LVL.

LSL and PSL have recently become less widely available in the UK due to a preference for LVL and supply chain considerations.

Glued laminated timber

Glued laminated timber (glulam) is a structural member made by gluing together a number of graded timber laminations with their grain parallel to the longitudinal axis of the section. Members can be straight or curved, horizontally or vertically laminated and can be used to create a variety of structural forms (Figure 192).

Laminations are typically 25mm or 45mm thick but smaller laminations may be necessary where tightly curved or vertically laminated sections are required.

The requirements for the manufacture of glulam are contained in product standard BS EN 14080: 2013.

Figure 192: Glued laminated timber

Cross laminated timber (CLT)

Cross laminated timber (CLT) is a structural timber product with a minimum of three cross-bonded layers of timber, of thickness 6mm to 45mm, strength graded to BS EN 14081-1:2005 and glued together in a press which applies pressure over the entire surface area of the panel.

CLT panels typically have an odd number of layers (3,5,7,9) which may be of differing thicknesses but which are arranged symmetrically around the middle layer with adjacent layers having their grain direction at right angles to one another (Figure 193:8).

The structural benefits of CLT over conventional softwood wall framing and joisted floor constructions, include:

- large axial and flexural load-bearing capacity when used as a wall or slab
- high in-plane shear strength when used as a shear wall
- fire resistance characteristics for exposed applications
- superior acoustic properties

Due to its arrangement as a panel rather than a framed construction comprising discrete loadbearing elements, CLT also distributes concentrated loads as line loads at foundation level. A variant of CLT developed in Germany in the 1970s is Brettstapel or 'massive timber', which is the term commonly used for solid timber construction that does not generally use glue or nails. Fabricated from softwood timber posts connected with hardwood timber dowels, the system works by using dowels with a moisture content lower than that of the posts. Over time, the dowels expand to achieve moisture equilibrium, thus 'locking' the posts together and creating a structural load-bearing panel system. CLT should be designed using the principles given in BS EN 1995-1-1 and -1-2 together with data from the manufacturer of the product.

Figure 193: CLT

Reconstituted wood-based board products

Reconstituted board products are typically manufactured by combining smaller wood strands or fibres with adhesive. There is a structural penalty when timber is modified from a sawn product to small strands and fibres used in board products, as the effects of creep increase as the amount of glue used to join the smaller wood elements increases.

The design of reconstituted timber board materials takes the resulting reduced performances into account by the use of relatively low values for the factor k_{mod} in BS EN 1995-1-1 for OSB, particleboards and fibreboards.

Oriented strand board (OSB)

Oriented strand board (OSB) is a multilayer board made from strands of wood sliced from small diameter timber logs and bonded together with an exterior grade adhesive, under heat and pressure. OSB is manufactured in various grades with improving resistance to the effects of moisture. The minimum grade that should be used for structural applications is OSB/3 as given in BS EN 300:1997. OSB is commonly used as a structural sub deck material for floors and roofs and as a sheathing material for walls. It is also used for composite constructions such as I joist webs and structural insulated panels (SIPs).

Figure 194: OSB

Particleboard and fibre composites

There are a number of different board materials made from particle and fiber composites including fiberboards, tempered hardboard, cement-bonded particleboard and wood chipboard. The most common for structural

applications is chipboard, which is made from small particles of wood and binder.

Chipboards are classified as grades P1-P7 in BS EN 312:2003 depending on their intended use. The minimum grade that should be used for structural applications is P5 which is a moisture-resistant grade.

The characteristic strength and stiffness values for OSB, particleboards and fiberboards for use in structural design are contained in BS EN 12369-1:2001.

Figure 195: Particleboard

Summary of timber, engineered wood and board products and their structural applications

Product	Application	Common sizes
Sawn timber	Small structural framing, studs and joists, general carcassing, door panels, joinery	Length: up to 5.4m Width: 25-75mm Depth: up to 250mm
Finger-jointed softwood	Floor and roof joists, ceilings, loadbearing studs, cladding support, prefabricated multi-span 'cassette floors', laminations for glulam members	Length: up to 20m Width: 38-75mm Depth: up to 250mm
Glulam	Large structural elements, beams, columns, trusses, bridges, portal frames, post and beam structures	No theoretical limits to size length or shape. Common size range: 60 to 250mm wide by 180mm to >1000mm deep
'Massive' or cross laminated timber (CLT)	Floor slabs, roofs, beams, columns, load bearing walls, shear walls	Length: up to 20m Thickness: 50-300mm Width: up to 4800mm
Laminated veneer lumber (LVL)	Beams, columns, trusses, portal frames, post and beam structures, structural decking, I-joint flanges, stressed skin panels	Length: up to 20m Width: 19-200mm Depth: 200mm up to 2500mm
Laminated strand lumber (LSL)	Beams, columns, post and beam structures	Length: up to 20m Width: 30-90mm Depth: 90mm to >1000mm
Parallel strand lumber (PSL)	Beams, columns, post and beam structures	Length: up to 20m Width: 45-200mm Depth: 200mm to >1000mm
Particleboards	Flooring, ceiling and panel infill	Board materials typically available in 1220mm x 2440mm sheets and thickness ranges from 9 to 25mm
Oriented strand board (OSB) & plywood	Structural sheathing and decking	
Metal web or open-web joists	Floor and roof joists, ceilings, prefabricated 'cassette floors'	Length: up to 20m Width: 72-147mm Depth: 200-400mm
I joists	Floor and roof joists, formwork, ceilings, loadbearing studs, cladding support, prefabricated 'cassette floors'	Length: up to 20m Width: 38-97mm Depth: 200-500mm
Box beams, thin flange beams e.g. stressed skin panels	Beams, roofs, columns	No theoretical limits to size length or component sizes

Table 34: Summary of timber, engineered wood and board products and their structural applications

Advantages of EWPS as structural materials

Use of waste timber

Timber can be recycled and turned into strands and fibres and reconstituted into an engineered wood product.

Enhanced strength and stiffness

By building up a structural section from a number of smaller elements it is possible to reduce the variability inherent in natural timber, thereby improving the strength and stiffness of the composite section.

Increased size and scope of application

Engineered timber structures incorporate factory produced components where the constraints on length and section may be determined only by manufacturing, handling and transportation considerations rather than the constraints set by the size of log available. It is therefore possible to extend the range of timber engineering possibilities to large span and tall structures.

Reduced moisture content

The production requirements for certain EWPs may call for lowmoisture content e.g. gluing, which can result in lower movement upon drying out in service. However, in some cases (e.g. OSBs) the moisture content of the product following manufacture is lower than will be experienced during the construction phase, which can lead to problems due to dimensional changes of the product in humid environments.

Dimensional consistency

Engineered wood products disperse the natural defects inherent in solid timber and are manufactured to controlled tolerances. As a result, their dimensional consistency is significantly improved. This can be beneficial where tight tolerances may be required e.g. at connections. More regular joist depths also result in flatter floor structures than would be possible with sawn timber joists; thus avoiding some of the problems that can be associated with small variations in joist depth such as 'nail squeak'.

Ease of installing services and ease of handling

Service runs for mechanical and electrical infrastructure can easily be installed through open-web joists and, to a lesser extent, through I joists.

I joists and open web joists in particular are lighter in weight than equivalent solid timber sections and are therefore easier to handle.

Types of timber structures

Structural methods have been developed, incorporating EWPs, to provide timber structures which achieve a particular function with satisfying aesthetic form and performance e.g. timber gridshells and stressed skin panel roofs.

Portal frames and beam and post structures

Large open plan structures can be created by using portal frames and beam and post structures constructed from engineered wood products.

Platform frame construction

Methods of construction such as platform frame construction enable the construction of multi-storey timber frame structures for buildings which have a cellular arrangement of rooms and where internal loadbearing walls can be utilized.

Structural insulated panels

Other structural systems such as structural insulated panels (SIPs) are composite members which use a core of rigid insulation, not only

to provide a u-value for a building's thermal envelope, but also to form a longitudinal shear connection between plywood or OSB face layers; thus enabling it to act as a structural panel.

Table 5 provides a brief description of the types and scope of engineered timber structures that can be designed to provide structurally efficient and aesthetically appealing structures for a wide variety of building uses. These and other structural methods will be investigated in more depth in subsequent articles in this series.

System	Application	Limitations
Platform frame construction (softwood construction)	Residential, care homes, hotels, student accommodation	Commonly used for cellular-plan buildings with internal load-bearing walls. Up to 7 storeys possible, however requirements for preventing building overturning may govern
Glulam or LVL beam and post frames	Schools, atria, commercial, supermarkets	Used to create 'open' framed areas but require separate bracing systems for stability. No theoretical limits on span or number of storeys
Glulam or LVL portal frames	Halls, industrial buildings, arenas, distribution centres	Usually single storey. Large open spaces with spans of more than 30m possible. The size of the portal frames is usually only limited by transportation
Cross laminated timber (CLT) or 'Brettstapel' (massive timber)	Multi-storey residential, schools, academies, auditoria, exhibition spaces, places of worship, sports halls, theatres where an exposed timber finish is beneficial	Platform and balloon-frame construction. Tall single storey wall panels possible and structures up to 10 storeys tall have been constructed. Large panels need careful consideration in terms of transportation and handling
Structural insulated panels (SIPs)	Residential, care homes, hotels, student accommodation; infill panels to steel and concrete frames; roof panels for 'room-in-the-roof' construction	External envelope wall panels within platform frame or frame infill construction. Up to 4 storeys possible for load-bearing applications. Good thermal performance. Roof spans may be limited by shear and creep deflections of core materials
Special structures	Gridshells, arches, domes, bridges	Project specific solutions which typically span 10-50m, though there are examples of 150m span gridshells
Engineered trusses	'Feature trusses' using glulam or oak, industrial, commercial and institutional	Spans between 10 to 50m
Trussed rafters	Roofs for residential buildings, care homes, hotels, masonry, steel and concrete structures	Typically up to 12m but for special designs spans of up to 30m are practicable

Table 5. Types of timber structural systems and their applications

Design

Eurocode 5 has provided opportunities for designers to use timber for new applications that should give economic solutions, particularly as the code makes provision for the use of new materials, such as engineered wood products and new efficient jointing techniques. The code encourages engineers to gain a greater understanding of timber which will lead to more efficient and innovative designs for engineered timber structures.

Structural forms and detailing, together with examples of calculations for structural timber to Eurocode 5, will be discussed in future articles.

Limitations

In addition to the structural strength and stiffness aspects of timber engineering there are other considerations, which affect 'whole building' performance and must be considered. These include:

- Timber shrinkage and differential movement
- Design for robustness

- Architectural detailing including detailing for durability
- Fire during construction and service
- Workmanship and maintenance

Timber frame building

The Timber frame system is among the most common for building construction with one or multi floors. The system consists of walls and floors composed of wooden elements of small cross-sections. These elements are placed at a distance of 40-60 cm between them. Structural wood panels are attached to one or both sides of these elements, using nails or screws of a small diameter. The walls and floors thus created are attached to each other and to the foundation with metal angular plates, bolts, screws, and nails.

Insulation inside the timber frame completes the construction package of the walls. The insulating layer placed inside can take all the thickness. In this case, the technological systems are laid inside the insulation. Green manufacturers produce nowadays structure composed of layered elements, where each material is strictly eco-compatible and free from harmful emissions. Furthermore, the cutting-edge technologies reflect new regulations concerning seismic safety, guaranteeing complete stability of the structure.

Figure 196: Timber frame composition

In building part of ECOBULK project, we suggest innovative design using more recycled materials and with a composition inspired by timber frame compositions. The project consortium is made up of a few manufacturers of recycled materials, which could become an alternative to sawn timber used in timber frame constructions

One of current timber frame composition is used as example of inspiration. It is main timber structure and insulation, with internal and external insulation layers. [catalogue-bois-construction.fr]

Figure 197: Example of one current composition of timber frame wall

Performances required for a timber frame wall :

- 1) **Interior wall cladding** : panel without Indoor air quality respect
- 2) And 8) timber battens : C18 or C24 class of strength

EN 338 - Table 1 - Strength classes - Characteristic Values

Wood Class	Strength Properties (in N/mm ²)						Stiffness properties (in kN/mm ²)				Density (in kg/m ³)	Density (in kg/m ³)
	Bending	Tension Paralel	Tension Perpendicular	Compression Paralel	Compression Perpendicular	Shear	Mean modulus of elasticity paralel	5% modulus of elasticity paralel	Mean modulus of elasticity perpendicular	Mean shear modulus	ρ_k	ρ_{mean}
	$f_{m,k}$	$f_{t,0,k}$	$f_{t,90,k}$	$f_{c,0,k}$	$f_{c,90,k}$	$f_{v,k}$	$E_{0,mean}$	$E_{0,05}$	$E_{90,mean}$	G_{mean}		
C14	14	8	0.4	16	2	3	7	4.7	0.23	0.44	290	350
C16	16	10	0.4	17	2.2	3.2	8	5.4	0.27	0.5	310	370
C18	18	11	0.4	18	2.2	3.4	9	6	0.3	0.56	320	380
C20	20	12	0.4	19	2.3	3.6	9.5	6.4	0.32	0.59	330	390
C22	22	13	0.4	20	2.4	3.8	10	6.7	0.33	0.63	340	410
C24	24	14	0.4	21	2.5	4	11	7.4	0.37	0.69	350	420

3 -

Sd-value designates the thickness of the air layer equivalent to diffusion (in meters) the value Sd is calculated as follows: $Sd = \mu \times d$ in which d is the thickness of the material expressed in meters and μ is the water vapor diffusion factor. The higher μ is corresponding to the higher vapor resistance.

- Matériaux de perméance $\leq 0,005 \text{ g/m}^2 \cdot \text{h} \cdot \text{mmHg}$, soit un $Sd \geq 18 \text{ m}$
- Films polyéthylènes d'épaisseur $> 100 \text{ mm}$
- Films polyester d'épaisseur $> 100 \text{ mm}$

4 - **Wood stud** : massive timber or finger jointed timber

Thick 45mm - Center distance 400 or 600mm - Slenderness (width / thickness ratio) of 6 maxi - C18 or D18 mini - Compatible with use class 2 - Resistance to insects against xylophagous larvae and termites according to the Decree of June 27, 2006 (modified 2010)

5 - Insulation: Semi rigid insulation according to NF DTU 31.2 or according to DTA

6 - Bracing panel

Thickness outside seismic zone: 3S thick plywood • 7mm - OSB3 thick • 9mm - P5 type panels • 10mm - LVL thick panels • 15mm Thickness in seismic zone: 3S thick plywood • 9mm - OSB3 thick • 13mm - P5 type panels • 13mm - LVL th panels • 15mm

7 - Rain barrier layer material with permeance $\leq 0,5 \text{ g/m}^2 \cdot \text{h} \cdot \text{mmHg}$ or Sd-value $\leq 0,18\text{m}$

- Materials called "HPV" (highly permeable to water vapor) with Sd-value $\leq 0.10\text{m}$
- Tear resistant materials
- Polyethylene or polyester films
- Other materials of equivalent quality
- SB-H or MDF-RWH type wood fiber panels

9 - Exterior cladding - Ventilated cladding

10 - External additional frame to maintain over-insulation

. Thick 60 or 80 or

100mm, compatible with use class 2

Ecobulk timber and recycled composition

WPCs

Wood-plastic composites (WPCs) are composite materials made of wood fiber/wood flour and thermoplastic(s) (includes PE, PP, PVC etc.).

Chemical additives seem practically "invisible" (except mineral fillers and pigments, if added) in the composite structure. They provide for integration of polymer and wood flour (powder) while facilitating optimal processing conditions.

In addition to wood fiber and plastic, WPCs can also contain other ligno-cellulosic and/or inorganic filler materials. WPCs are a subset of a larger category of materials called natural fiber plastic composites (NFPCs), which may contain no cellulose-based fiber fillers such as pulp fibers, peanut hulls, bamboo, straw, digestate, etc.

Wood-plastic composites are still new materials relative to the long history of natural lumber as a building material. The most widespread use of WPCs in North America is in outdoor deck floors, but it is also used for railings, fences, landscaping timbers, cladding and siding, park benches, molding and trim,

window and door frames, and indoor furniture. Wood-plastic composites were first introduced into the decking market in the early 1990s. Manufacturers claim that wood-plastic composite is more environmentally friendly and requires less maintenance than the alternatives of solid wood treated with preservatives or solid wood of rot-resistant species. These materials can be molded with or without simulated wood grain details.

Figure 198: WPC decking

According to the thicknesses, dimensions, strength performances of the materials, the components likely to be replaced are the following elements :

- 1) Interior wall cladding
- 2) Interior batten : thick 40*25 mm
- 8) Exterior batten : thick 40*25 mm
- 9) Exterior cladding
- 10) External additional frame : thick 60*40 mm

Ecobulk timber prototype

FCBA has made a reference wall model with a current timber-frame wall composition identical to the previous description. Depending on the materials available from Ecobulk manufacturers, we intend to offer an identical model with the recycled materials but maintaining the main wooden structure.

The dimensions of the wall model are 900mm by 600mm, including all materials in the thickness. The whole is framed by a plywood frame, which is easily removable in order to change configuration if needed.

- 1) Interior wall cladding : Plasterboard BA13
- 2) Interior battens
- 3) Vapor barrier layer
- 4) Wood stud
- 5) Insulations: Wood wool 145mm and 40mm
- 6) Bracing panel : OSB 9mm
- 7) Rain barrier
- 8) Exterior battens
- 9) Exterior cladding :

Figure 199: Timber frame wall model view from inside

- 1) Interior wall cladding
- 2) Interior battens
- 3) Vapor barrier layer
- 4) Wood stud
- 5) Insulations
- 6) Bracing panel
- 7) Rain barrier
- 8) Exterior battens
- 9) Exterior cladding
- 10) Exterior additional

Figure 200: Timber frame wall model view from outside

In the ecobulk prototype, we maintain the main timber structure and also the water and vapor barriers layers.

Figure 149: Main timber structure

Figure 201: Ecobulk material alternatives

Ecobulk choice of materials

The choice of ecobulk materials is based on the equivalent mechanical performance expected in the wooden elements to be replaced as well as the class of use described before. The tests carried out on the materials should therefore be provided with the supply of the materials in order to justify the equivalence of performance.

On the other hand, the choice is also conditioned by the dimensions available from the manufacturer to be compatible with the method of construction of a wooden frame wall.

Example of materials suggested by ecobulk partner : CONNENOR

- 1) Interior wall cladding: PANEL 390x5mm
- 2) Interior batten: SOLID PLANK 120x30mm (plain surfaces)
- 8) External battens: SOLID PLANK 120x30mm (plain surfaces)
- 9) Exterior cladding: recycled cladding (specifications for outdoor use): PANEL 390x10mm
- 10) External additional batten: SOLID PLANK 120x60mm (plain surfaces)

*Total need for the wall prototype (model : 900mm*600mm) and for the hydrothermal tests (1900mm*900mm) :*

- PANEL 390x5mm with straight edges: 7 pieces of 900mm of length
- SOLID PLANK 120x30mm (plain surfaces) : 3 * 1900mm of length
- SOLID PLANK 120x30mm (plain surfaces) : 3* 1900mm of length
- PANEL 390x10mm with shiplap edges = 7 pieces of 900mm of length
- SOLID PLANK 120x30mm (plain surfaces) : 7 * 900mm of length

Hygrothermal behavior of timber frame wall

Nowadays, there is an increasing demand for walls allowing maximum moisture transfers following the appearance on the market of barriers and materials more permeable to water vapor as well as the design of constructive systems (original Scandinavian, German, Swiss, Austrian, etc.) allowing high humidity transfers in the walls.

The construction provisions of the current French regulations DTU 31.2 - Construction of wooden frame houses and buildings - make it mandatory to install barriers to vapor diffusion, characterized in terms of resistance to diffusion by water vapor. minimum Sd values of 18 m. This relatively high Sd value does not allow significant vapor transfers.

Influence of vapour barrier

A wall, with a bracing panel, in the external position, and without barrier to water vapor and whatever the type of insulation used, will have condensations that will be increasing from one year to the next. In addition, the amounts of the wall structure will see their water contents increase from one year to the next. After a few years, the timber structure and the entire wall will see their durability very degraded.

For the various barriers to water vapor, it turns out that the lower the Sd characteristic, the higher the water content of the various components and in particular the bracing working veil, when placed outside. We will observe the

behaviour of different ecobulk composite battens and panel under the humidity transfer in the wall.

Influence of composition or wall design

Adding an over-insulation between the plasterboard and the water vapor barrier leads to an increase in the humidity of the materials in this part.

However, the rule 2/3 and 1/3 rule is verified for all metropolitan climates studied for a maximum indoor humidity production of 5 g / m³.

External over-insulation will reduce the effects of thermal bridges and therefore of cold spots near the interior of the wall. By limiting the cold spots in the wall, the risk of condensation is reduced.

The bracing panel is a barrier to water vapor compared to other products (insulation, plasterboard, etc.). If placed on the outside of the wall, the bracing structural panel will create a barrier or there will be an accumulation of moisture. This can eventually lead to condensation if the Sd of the vapor barrier is not high enough.

Placed on the inside, the bracing working veil can act as a water vapor barrier or complement the barrier.

Ecobulk timber prototype

FCBA built a reference wall sample with a classic composition of timber frame wall. The dimensions of the prototype are 900mm wide and 1900mm high.

Figure 202: Structure of the wall prototype

A second wall prototype uses panels made from recycled wood as exterior cladding, interior cladding, interior and exterior battens instead of wood and

plasterboard. The objective is to observe the impact of these materials on the hydrothermal behavior of the wall.

Photo report of the prefabrication of reference wall prototype

In this photo report, we have the different manufacturing stages of the wood frame wall. They were prefabricated in the carpentry laboratory and then they are transported to the hydrothermal test cabins. After each report, we have the explanation of each number indicating the stages.

Figure 152: Photo report of timber frame wall prototype

- (1) implementation of the wooden frame
- (2) insulation between uprights
- (3) the vapor barrier stapled to the the timber frame
- (4) interior insulating lining maintained by wooden battens
- (5) installation of the interior plasterboard facing
- (6) waterproof seal on the contour of the OSB panel
- (7) stapling the rain barrier and the exterior wooden battens
- (8) Installation of wooden cladding on the exterior wooden battens

Photo report of the prefabrication of reference wall prototype

Figure 203: Fabrication of the wall prototype

- (1) implementation of the wooden frame
- (2) insulation between uprights
- (3) the vapor barrier stapled to the the timber frame
- (4) interior insulating lining maintained by recycled battens
- (5) installation of the interior recycled material cladding
- (6) waterproof seal on the contour of the OSB panel
- (7) stapling the rain barrier and the exterior recycled battens
- (8) Installation of recycled material cladding on exterior

Figure 204: Internal side of the two samples of walls

Figure 205: External side of the two samples of walls

Hygrothermal behaviours of Ecobulk walls :

A first validation of the wall compositions will consist in highlighting the results on the hygrothermal characteristics by tests and simulations on the wall scale with new typologies of wood-frame walls. FCBA has two adiabatic climatic chambers, which are separated by a wall. This wall can include two samples whose behaviours are to be compared with each other.

This experimental platform allows the measurement of the thermal and hygroscopic transmission properties of two walls simultaneously, subject to the same conditions on both sides of the two samples: simulation of indoor and outdoor climates. It is a question here of comparing the performance of a classic reference typology with a wall composed with Ecobulk materials.

Figure 206: FCBA Climatic chambers

External side

internal side

Figure 207: Comparison of two wall samples: dimensions 1900mm*900mm

The temperature and relative humidity of each material interface will be recorded continuously, and under the influence of indoor (23°C T and 60% RH) and outdoor climates (5°C T and 95% RH) on both sides of the two wall samples.

Figure 208: Temperature and Humidity sensors and measurement records system

Analysis of heat transfers

- Comparison of surfaces temperatures

In the cold climate, air temperature is maintained at 3°C.

Figure 209: temperature of the exterior wood cladding

Figure 210: Temperature of the external composite cladding

The means of temperatures obtained on the surface of external cladding are the same for the two walls : $T_{\text{mean}} = 4,2^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Inside the hot climate, the temperature is maintained at 23°C .

Figure 211: temperature of plasterboard on interior side

Figure 212: Temperature of composite on interior side

Temperature and relative humidity profiles are obtained throughout the wall taking into account the records at each interface.

Figure 213: Locations of sensors in interfaces of materials in the two walls

Figure 214: Temperature record in the reference wall

Figure 215: Temperature records in the composite wall

Figure 216: Temperatures in 2 typologies of timber frame

Figure 217: Profiles of temperatures in the two walls

The profiles of temperatures in the two walls are very close, the temperatures in each interfaces of materials are the same especially the ones which are near the interior and exterior sides.

Figure 218: Relative humidity in the reference wall

Figure 219: Relative humidity in wall with composites

Figure 220: Relative humidity profiles in the two walls

The variations in relative humidity in the two walls are not identical. In the wooden reference wall, the plasterboard facing allows all the humidity contained in the air of the interior cabin to pass through. We then have an accumulation of humidity at the vapor barrier (3). The difference between (3) and (4) is explained by the role of the vapor barrier which does not allow the accumulation of moisture towards the main insulation between the wooden studs. The OSB panels and the rainscreen on the exterior side of the wall allow humidity to transfer from the exterior air which is maintained at 75%. (5) in the reference wall is the external face of insulation. The relative humidity is high because of the cold from exterior side of the wall.

In the air space behind the wood siding, we have a relative humidity of 64%. The decrease in this humidity compared to the air can be due to an absorption of the wood cladding.

In the wall with composites, the interior facing acts as a barrier to the humidity of the interior air. There is less accumulation of moisture at the vapor barrier. There is still a difference on either side of the vapor barrier which does not allow the accumulation of moisture to transfer to the main insulation between the uprights. We see in the air space behind the exterior composite siding that the relative humidity of the air (14) is closer to the outside air maintained at 75% relative humidity. This is explained by the existence of air infiltration between the composite panels and their property which does not absorb moisture.

Conclusion

One of the richness of the Ecobulk project is to have industrial, technical and scientific partners coming from different worlds: plastics industry, automobile industry, furniture and construction. Communication between these partners has enabled new ideas and opportunities to emerge that allow innovation in the various fields but also the development of each person's skills. The construction component launched into a suggestion for a new wood-frame wall composition in order to recycle recycled materials in construction. We identified the constituent elements already present in wood construction or in different wood-based materials, and then the project plans to test them by a comparative analysis of the hydrothermal behavior of the walls. Collaboration with the composite materials manufacturers is expected in order to supply the alternative elements to wooden battens as well as the interior and exterior wall coatings. At the end of the project, we plan to present a model of this new generation of wall inspired by the timber frame wall, as well as the hydrothermal analysis results from tests in a climatic chamber.

By the comparison of two walls, we can conclude that the presence of composites in the wall does not significantly change the thermal behaviour of timber frame wall. Indeed, the temperature profiles at the different material interfaces are very similar.

With regard to moisture transfer, the presence of composites demonstrates a role of vapour barrier for the interior facing. This role can be useful for rooms with high humidity to avoid accumulating water in the timber frame wall. However, the relative humidity in the main insulation remains close (4) and (5) in the reference wall and (11) and (12) in the wall with composites.

Composites used as exterior cladding have spaces that allow outside air to pass through.

In the two walls, there is no presence of condensation observed.

This experiment constitutes a first validation of the use of composites as structural elements and interior and exterior wall cladding for a timber frame construction. Further technical validations would be required regarding the mechanics and durability of these composite materials, which are not tested in the project.

3.5. Compounding at Aimplas, SPAIN

3.5.1. Introduction

Thermoplastic agglomerates produced in the patented Conenor invented process incorporating GFRP-waste can be used in continuous “moulding” processes i.e. extrusions to manufacture various product shapes when the material conveying in the extruder is realized with screw or belt conveyors. While in other batch-based thermoplastics process techniques e.g. injection moulding it is important A) to maintain exact volume of the material fed into the mould as well as B) not to have free dust in the material as conveying is realized with pneumatic blowers which release the air into the manufacturing hall.

When benchmarking virgin thermoplastic materials reinforced with glass fibres one may find several manufacturers supplying global markets with products identified as Long Fibre Thermoplastics (LFTs) and Short Fibre Thermoplastics (SFTs). Examples of well-known manufacturers are e.g. Borealis with brand “Fibremod™”², and Solvay with brand “Xencor™”³. These materials are typically produced in an extruder into continuous strands (LFT) which become chopped at breaker plate into 10mm+ long where glass fibre bundles or granules (SFT) which are embedded with the polymer, typically with polypropylene PP. The most common application is automotive parts but many other such as leisure and sporting goods are typical as well.

Fibremod GD577SF					
Pos. 1 (Polymer type) H – Homopolymer R – Random copolymer B – Block copolymer T – Terepolymer E – Extastomer modified G – Glass fibre C – Carbon fibre reinforced M – Mineral filled W – Other or combinations	Pos. 2 (MFR range) B > 0.8-2.5 C > 2.5-5 D > 5-10 E > 10-15 F > 15-20 G > 20-30 H > 30-40 J > 40-100	Pos. 3 (Filler content) 0: 0-9% 1: 10-19% 2: 20-29% 3: 30-39% 4: 40-49% 5: 50-59% 6: 60-69%	Pos. 4-5 (Numerical index)	Pos. 6-7 (Application index) AE: Automotive exterior AI: Automotive interior UB: Under the Bonnet HP: High Performance SW: Sustainability SF: Short Glass Fibre LF: Long Glass Fibre WG: White goods	Pos. 8 (Production Location) S: South America C: Asia U: North America
 Under-the-bonnet					

Figure 221: Benchmarking examples of LFT and SFT material applications

² <https://www.borealisgroup.com/polyolefins/automotive/fibremod>

³ <https://www.solvay.com/en/press-release/solvays-xencor-lft-chosen-stajvelo-first-all-polymer-e-bike>

3.5.2. Conenor agglomerates compounded into granules with 35%-w. GFRP-waste

Development of LFT/SFT-materials with GFRP-waste for injection moulding applications and demonstrators is not part of the Ecobulk scope nor project plan, but for the **proof of the concept with Conenor developed agglomerates** from recycled basis it was agreed to realize compounding trials at Aimplas, Spain.

Four different Conenor recycled grades of agglomerates became compounded into granules containing two recycled polymer basis rPE and rPP and two types of GFRP-waste namely dusty fraction from manufacturing (shavings) from Exel Composites, Finland and EoL wind turbine blade waste from Demacq, Holland;

- rPP + wood fibres + GFRP-waste from manufacturing + additives
- rPE + wood fibres + GFRP-waste from manufacturing + additives
- rPP + wood fibres + GFRP-waste from EoL wind turbine blades + additives
- rPE + wood fibres + GFRP-waste from EoL wind turbine blades + additives

Figure 222: Process diagram for compounding granules with GFRP-waste

Outcome from the Aimplas trials using **recycled material basis** was successful and four grades of compounded granules as described above were produced.

Figure 223: Compounded granules from Conenor agglomerates

3.6. Recycling and Circularity of Building Products

3.6.1. Re-manufacturing recovered materials from demo sites

For proving the circularity of Conenor developed GFRP-waste reinforced thermoplastic materials and extruded products for the re-manufacturing evaluation purposes, rest pieces left over from construction works were collected from two demonstration sites at Lipor, Portugal in PP-basis and KymiRing, Finland in PE-basis to produce from those test specimens at Conenor for CNR evaluation.

Figure 224: Rest pieces collected from Lipor/POR and KymiRing/FIN

Rest pieces were shredded at Conenor at Rapid 300 re-granulator using dia 10mm sieve into processable materials.

Figure 225: Rest pieces from Lipor (PP-based) and KymiRing (PE-based) shredded

Shredded materials were mixed with new materials in the following two separate formulations for re-manufacturing;

PP-based recycled beige composites from Lipor, Portugal (91%-w.)

- crushed planks and pillars 91%
- virgin PP 7%
- coupling agent 0,5%
- processing aid 1,5%

PE-based recycled grey composites from KymiRing, Finland (95%-w.)

- crushed planks and pillars 95%
- virgin HDPE 3%
- coupling agent 0,5%
- processing aid 1,5%

The re-manufactured materials formulations were extruded at Conenor CONEX® extruder CWE 380-1 into hollow bar test specimens in dimensions 60x40x8mm. Processing was successful simple straight forward without any problems and samples were delivered to CNR, Italy for testing.

Moreover one should remember that in manufacturing the recycled composites for the demos, in-house re-manufactured material was already used 100% in the multilayer product core layer.

It was found easier to produce representative samples from the PE-based (grey) composites than PP-based (beige) and adding less new material.

Figure 226: Extruded test specimens from recovered materials

3.6.2.Characterization of re-manufactured composite materials by CNR

	S_51 (grey)	S_52 (beige)
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<p>Description</p>	The grey color samples returned from KymiRing are in HDPE+GFRP-waste basis which were crushed at Conenor and the ReMa formulation is follows (%-w.);	The beige color samples returned from Lipor are in PP+GFRP-waste basis which were crushed at Conenor and the ReMa formulation is follows (%-w.);
	chrushed planks and pillars 95%	chrushed planks and pillars 91%
	virgin HDPE 3%	virgin PP 7%
	coupling agent 0.5%	coupling agent 0.5%
	processing aid 1.5%	processing aid 1.5%

Table 36: Contents of test specimens with recovered materials from demo sites

	KymiRing S_51 (PE/grey)	Lipor S_52 (PP/beige)
DENSITY (g/cm ³)	1.184 ± 0.008	1.240 ± 0.015
FLEXURAL TEST		
Flexural modulus (MPa)	1160 ± 75	2210 ± 140
Flexural strength (MPa)	25.2 ± 1.8	24.6 ± 2.5
IMPACT TEST		
Resilience (kJ/m ²)	1.97 ± 0.29	1.73 ± 0.14
Force (N)	138 ± 8	159 ± 11
TG ANALYSIS		
T (2wt% WL), °C	280	273
T (5 wt% WL), °C	322	309
Weight residual 800°C, wt%	23.0	28.2

Table 37: CNR test results of test specimens made with recovered materials

Despite the high content of recycled product (95% for the PE/KymiRing and 91% for the PP/Lipor sample) and the low amount of virgin polymer added (3% HDPE, 7% PP) flexural properties are interesting, especially for the PP sample from Lipor.

For comparison you can see in the chart properties of the in-house recycled samples that were provided and tested at the beginning of the project:

Code	Flexural properties	
	Modulus (MPa)	Stress @max load (MPa)
PP_rec	1065 ± 75	31.9 ± 0.6
HDPE1_rec	765 ± 40	20.7 ± 0.8
HDPE2_rec	810 ± 15	20.7 ± 0.3

Table 38: Typical test results in the beginning of the project

For the impact test (performed on V-notched samples), the impact resistance (resilience) is not very bad both for the HDPE and the PP samples. Possibly the impact resistance is not higher because during recycling of the planks glass fibers are highly fragmented, thus reducing their reinforcing effect.

For both samples the thermal stability is good.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

4.1. Furniture

The solution implemented by Moretti Compact can be defined as a good solution in terms of circularity, since all the main aspects related to this field were positively kept into account.

In general, when a circular product is designed, the idea is trying to extend as much as possible the life cycle, by minimizing the production of scraps during manufacturing and after the dismissal of the furniture. If we consider this later aspect, the starting point was already good considering the positive framework in which the company is inserted. The Italian wood recycling system in fact, is organized in a circular loop so that wood-based furniture and packaging are totally recycled, without any scrap in landfill: this system is recognized as best practice to be replicated also at international level where the logistic issues can allow it: the final output is the realization of 100% recycled particleboards for the production of furniture, and Moretti Compact already uses this typology of panels for its traditional products, totally recycled and recyclable.

The real challenge was then to design and prototype new furniture with a longer life-cycle as well as reusable and recoverable. For the extension of life-cycle the first idea was to design products with neutral shapes and colors, in order to guarantee an emotional durability despite of fashion trends which could periodically change. In parallel, the quality aspect was significantly taken into account from the beginning of design activity when it was necessary to guarantee the compliance with safety and comfort requirements, beyond the final phase with all laboratory tests carried out in an accredited structure.

However, the most significant challenge was related to modularity in order to guarantee reuse and recovery, thanks to the possibility to re-assemble products in different ways. This objective was achieved in different steps, since it was necessary to comply with all requirements especially by implementing a functional and practical connection system of the different blocks, without influencing at the same time the aesthetical aspect of the furniture.

Under the theoretical point of view, the design seemed very functional but it was necessary to test the effective possibility to assemble and disassemble products for a common end user at home, so the most critical phase was the last one, with different evaluations in demosites. The results showed a complete comparability with traditional furniture since the worst rate was 83%.

Other positive outputs of the activity are related to traceability and certification: considering the first aspect, the utilization of a QR code is the most suitable solution to provide information to the end user about the circularity of the products but also for the company to facilitate the eventual take back or substitution process under the logistical point of view. Finally, a

new certification path is now available for furniture products, thanks to which it is possible to measure the material balance and then to quantify in percentage the circularity of a product: considering the positive elements above described, the circularity of furniture prototypes is about 100%, also keeping into account upholster systems for bed and chair, realizable with recycled and recyclable materials.

Figure 227: Example of circularity label for furniture products.

4.2. Construction

Conenor has invented a break-through process technique to utilise first time ever in the world wasted thermoset GFRP as reinforcement in thermoplastic materials and products and this has been developed, patented worldwide and demonstrated successfully with circular extruded multilayer products in Ecobulk large scale demonstrations in four European countries in varying climate conditions in Finland, UK, France and Portugal in two structural product applications namely in outdoor furniture and shelters. Furthermore, it has been verified that Conenor produced GFRP-waste containing agglomerates are processable into compounded granules and pellets for other process techniques e.g. injection moulding to be used in those related product applications like automotive, aeronautics, sporting & leisure goods.

Closing the loop with Conenor processing and new materials developed have been proven by collecting different left-over rest pieces from two demo sites from Finland and Portugal and shredded materials thereof have been extruded into test samples for CNR testing in Italy with good results.

Global Covid-19 pandemic has caused significant obstacles in keeping time tables in the project and especially in the Finnish demo site KymiRing MOTOGP track infrastructure installations as the racing events, and the

official inauguration and opening of the track, became cancelled both year 2020 and 2021 resulting consequent delays also in the Ecobulk demo installations till autumn 2021 and therefore user feedback in Nordic climate remained to be seen during the years to come after the project. After one year of using the recycled composites in sunny Portugues climate conditions under continuous UV-radiation show no defects, no colour fading nor any altering of the recycled composite materials' characteristics nor performance which indicate long life expectation for the structures constructed.

As in the beginning of the project there was no knowledge whatsoever existing on the upcoming new GFRP-waste containing materials' and products' characteristics or performance to become designed and produced, but it was however necessary in each demo country and demonstrator to make operative plans what to construct and which optional products to use being made available by Conenor, one had to make a best guess at the design phase and learn by doing with field experiences during the work as it was progressing.

Lipor in Portugal being the very first demo site to have started working with the new materials recognized the need of extra components to be installed to reinforce the drinking fountain load bearing components i.e. recycled composite beams and pillars. Heavy weight of composite components used in the roofing was causing static loads exceeding the load bearing capacity of the beams and pillars in the hot Portugues climate influencing the products' rigidity which is temperature dependent as known with thermoplastic materials. Reinforcing the design with extra components resolved the issue and finally everybody was happy with the outcome.

The same phenomenon was observed also in the UK by Cranfield university in bowing of the composite beams and pillars in the gazebo type shelter design by Exergy. This was not an issue in the two other equal design installations in Warwick and Coventry universities which were completed without problems using exactly the same materials. Reasoning for the difference can be explained by differences in the installation procedure where Warwick and Coventry installed the vertical side planks before the installation of roofing components but Cranfield did the opposite. It appears that the reinforcement effect given by the side planks is necessary to prevent the beams and pillars from bowing when applying the roofing components providing the static loading for the shelter.

The shelter at Cranfield was decided to be disassembled and served as a good case study for the purpose. Disassembly of the shelter was easy and realised without any problems in half a day by two workers using simple hand tools to remove the screw joints. Those components that did not see the original bowing effect did not result having any defects and could become used again as new in the same purpose or repurposed for another suitable application.

The experiments and demonstrations reveal the obvious need to have properly prepared instructions for the construction sites as the workers are not familiar with these new materials nor their characteristics. Also it was

seen that all standard wood screws are not adequate to be used with composites and give poor screw withdrawal force and therefore guidance on proper screws to be used is necessary.

Despite of a few shortcomings in the lacking information of recycled composite materials' characteristics, constructing the demos were completed successfully in general and one can be both happy and proud of the project outcome.

List of appendixes:

- A. Tables from FCBA tests on particle boards
- B. Structural study on the UK shelter design by Scott White and Hookins LLP requested by the Warwick University, 21st August 2020

Appendix A: Tables from FCBA test on particle boards

	Nb ép. / spe.	Moyenne Mean	Ecart type Standart deviation	Max	Min	Ecart max / moy. Deviation max / mean	Ecart min / moy. Deviation min / mean
Humidité / Moisture content (%) selon NF EN 322	4	11,9	0,1				
Masse volumique / Density (kg/m ³) selon NF EN 323	4	753	46	792	689	5,2%	8,5%

	Nb ép. / spe.	Moyenne Mean	Ecart type Standart deviation	Coef. de variation Coef. of variation
Cohésion interne / Internal bond strength (N/mm ²) selon NF EN 319	4	0,44	0,15	34%
Gonflement / Sw elling (%) selon NF EN 317	4	22,1	10,4	47%
Contrainte à la rupture en flexion / Modulus of rupture (N/mm ²) selon NF EN 310	3	9,0	2,1	23%
Module d'élasticité en flexion / Modulus of elasticity (N/mm ²) selon NF EN 310	3	1566	274	17%

	Nb ép. / spe.	Valeur d'émission Emission value
Dégagement de formaldéhyde / Formaldehyde release (mg/m ² .h) selon NF EN ISO 12460-3	1	< 0,2

Table 39: Results synthesis for panel C1

	Nb ép. / spe.	Moyenne Mean	Ecart type Standart deviation	Max	Min	Ecart max / moy. Deviation max / mean	Ecart min / moy. Deviation min / mean
Humidité / Moisture content (%) selon NF EN 322	4	11,6	0,2				
Masse volumique / Density (kg/m ³) selon NF EN 323	4	745	21	766	718	2,8%	3,6%

	Nb ép. / spe.	Moyenne Mean	Ecart type Standart deviation	Coef. de variation Coef. of variation
Cohésion interne / Internal bond strength (N/mm ²) selon NF EN 319	4	0,47	0,04	9%
Gonflement / Sw elling (%) selon NF EN 317	4	29,6	2,4	8%
Contrainte à la rupture en flexion / Modulus of rupture (N/mm ²) selon NF EN 310	3	10,9	2,0	18%
Module d'élasticité en flexion / Modulus of elasticity (N/mm ²) selon NF EN 310	3	1771	173	10%

	Nb ép. / spe.	Valeur d'émission Emission value
Dégagement de formaldéhyde / Formaldehyde release (mg/m ² .h) selon NF EN ISO 12460-3	1	< 0,2

Table 40: Results synthesis for panel C2

	Nb ép. / spe.	Moyenne Mean	Ecart type Standart deviation	Max	Min	Ecart max / moy. Deviation max / mean	Ecart min / moy. Deviation min / mean
Humidité / Moisture content (%) selon NF EN 322	4	11,1	0,2				
Masse volumique / Density (kg/m ³) selon NF EN 323	4	707	23	732	682	3,5%	3,5%
	Nb ép. / spe.	Moyenne Mean	Ecart type Standart deviation	Coef. de variation Coef. of variation			
Cohésion interne / Internal bond strength (N/mm ²) selon NF EN 319	4	0,39	0,12	31%			
Gonflement / Swelling (%) selon NF EN 317	4	16,6	1,0	6%			
Contrainte à la rupture en flexion / Modulus of rupture (N/mm ²) selon NF EN 310	3	6,3	0,7	11%			
Module d'élasticité en flexion / Modulus of elasticity (N/mm ²) selon NF EN 310	3	1207	93	8%			
	Nb ép. / spe.	Valeur d'émission Emission value					
Dégagement de formaldéhyde / Formaldehyde release (mg/m ² .h) selon NF EN ISO 12460-3	1	< 0,2					

Table 41: Results synthesis for panel C3

	Nb ép. / spe.	Moyenne Mean	Ecart type Standart deviation	Max	Min	Ecart max / moy. Deviation max / mean	Ecart min / moy. Deviation min / mean
Humidité / Moisture content (%) selon NF EN 322	4	11,1	0,1				
Masse volumique / Density (kg/m ³) selon NF EN 323	4	729	27	749	689	2,7%	5,5%
	Nb ép. / spe.	Moyenne Mean	Ecart type Standart deviation	Coef. de variation Coef. of variation			
Cohésion interne / Internal bond strength (N/mm ²) selon NF EN 319	4	0,41	0,07	17%			
Gonflement / Swelling (%) selon NF EN 317	4	22,7	7,4	33%			
Contrainte à la rupture en flexion / Modulus of rupture (N/mm ²) selon NF EN 310	3	7,6	1,6	21%			
Module d'élasticité en flexion / Modulus of elasticity (N/mm ²) selon NF EN 310	3	1444	123	9%			
	Nb ép. / spe.	Valeur d'émission Emission value					
Dégagement de formaldéhyde / Formaldehyde release (mg/m ² .h) selon NF EN ISO 12460-3	1	< 0,2					

Table 42: Results synthesis for panel C4

	Nb ép. / spe.	Moyenne Mean	Ecart type Standart deviation	Max	Min	Ecart max / moy. Deviation max / mean	Ecart min / moy. Deviation min / mean
Humidité / Moisture content (%) selon NF EN 322	4	11,3	0,1				
Masse volumique / Density (kg/m ³) selon NF EN 323	4	821	16	838	803	2,1%	2,2%

	Nb ép. / spe.	Moyenne Mean	Ecart type Standart deviation	Coef. de variation Coef. of variation
Cohésion interne / Internal bond strength (N/mm ²) selon NF EN 319	4	0,45	0,10	22%
Gonflement / Swelling (%) selon NF EN 317	4	16,3	6,5	40%
Contrainte à la rupture en flexion / Modulus of rupture (N/mm ²) selon NF EN 310	3	6,2	2,1	34%
Module d'élasticité en flexion / Modulus of elasticity (N/mm ²) selon NF EN 310	3	1269	134	11%

	Nb ép. / spe.	Valeur d'émission Emission value
Dégagement de formaldéhyde / Formaldehyde release (mg/m ² .h) selon NF EN ISO 12460-3	1	< 0,2

Table 43: Results synthesis for panel C5

	Nb ép. / spe.	Moyenne Mean	Ecart type Standart deviation	Max	Min	Ecart max / moy. Deviation max / mean	Ecart min / moy. Deviation min / mean
Humidité / Moisture content (%) selon NF EN 322	4	11,6	0,2				
Masse volumique / Density (kg/m ³) selon NF EN 323	4	721	17	738	699	2,4%	3,1%

	Nb ép. / spe.	Moyenne Mean	Ecart type Standart deviation	Coef. de variation Coef. of variation
Cohésion interne / Internal bond strength (N/mm ²) selon NF EN 319	4	0,31	0,04	13%
Gonflement / Swelling (%) selon NF EN 317	4	14,8	0,6	4%
Contrainte à la rupture en flexion / Modulus of rupture (N/mm ²) selon NF EN 310	3	7,6	0,6	8%
Module d'élasticité en flexion / Modulus of elasticity (N/mm ²) selon NF EN 310	3	1299	146	11%

	Nb ép. / spe.	Valeur d'émission Emission value
Dégagement de formaldéhyde / Formaldehyde release (mg/m ² .h) selon NF EN ISO 12460-3	1	< 0,2

Table 44: Results synthesis for panel C6

	Nb ép. / spe.	Moyenne Mean	Ecart type Standart deviation	Max	Min	Ecart max / moy. Deviation max / mean	Ecart min / moy. Deviation min / mean
Humidité / Moisture content (%) selon NF EN 322	4	9,6	0,1				
Masse volumique / Density (kg/m ³) selon NF EN 323	4	644	9	658	639	2,2%	0,8%

	Nb ép. / spe.	Moyenne Mean	Ecart type Standart deviation	Coef. de variation Coef. of variation
Cohésion interne / Internal bond strength (N/mm ²) selon NF EN 319	4	0,24	0,04	17%
Gonflement / Swelling (%) selon NF EN 317	4	49,7	1,3	3%
Contrainte à la rupture en flexion / Modulus of rupture (N/mm ²) selon NF EN 310	3	4,0	0,8	20%
Module d'élasticité en flexion / Modulus of elasticity (N/mm ²) selon NF EN 310	3	869	24	3%

	Nb ép. / spe.	Valeur d'émission Emission value
Dégagement de formaldéhyde / Formaldehyde release (mg/m ² .h) selon NF EN ISO 12460-3	1	> 30

Table 45: Results synthesis for panel UF1

	Nb ép. / spe.	Moyenne Mean	Ecart type Standart deviation	Max	Min	Ecart max / moy. Deviation max / mean	Ecart min / moy. Deviation min / mean
Humidité / Moisture content (%) selon NF EN 322	4	9,6	0,1				
Masse volumique / Density (kg/m ³) selon NF EN 323	4	612	16	629	596	2,8%	2,6%

	Nb ép. / spe.	Moyenne Mean	Ecart type Standart deviation	Coef. de variation Coef. of variation
Cohésion interne / Internal bond strength (N/mm ²) selon NF EN 319	4	0,39	0,04	10%
Gonflement / Swelling (%) selon NF EN 317	4	48,9	4,3	9%
Contrainte à la rupture en flexion / Modulus of rupture (N/mm ²) selon NF EN 310	3	5,7	1,4	25%
Module d'élasticité en flexion / Modulus of elasticity (N/mm ²) selon NF EN 310	3	950	64	7%

	Nb ép. / spe.	Valeur d'émission Emission value
Dégagement de formaldéhyde / Formaldehyde release (mg/m ² .h) selon NF EN ISO 12460-3	1	> 30

Table 46: Results synthesis for panel UF2

	Nb ép. / spe.	Moyenne Mean	Ecart type Standart deviation	Max	Min	Ecart max / moy. Deviation max / mean	Ecart min / moy. Deviation min / mean
Humidité / Moisture content (%) selon NF EN 322	4	9,5	0,1				
Masse volumique / Density (kg/m ³) selon NF EN 323	4	643	25	666	610	3,6%	5,1%

	Nb ép. / spe.	Moyenne Mean	Ecart type Standart deviation	Coef. de variation Coef. of variation
Cohésion interne / Internal bond strength (N/mm ²) selon NF EN 319	4	0,18	0,04	22%
Gonflement / Sw elling (%) selon NF EN 317	4	49,8	3,4	7%
Contrainte à la rupture en flexion / Modulus of rupture (N/mm ²) selon NF EN 310	3	3,5	0,8	23%
Module d'élasticité en flexion / Modulus of elasticity (N/mm ²) selon NF EN 310	3	672	170	25%

	Nb ép. / spe.	Valeur d'émission Emission value
Dégagement de formaldéhyde / Formaldehyde release (mg/m ² .h) selon NF EN ISO 12460-3	1	> 30

Table 47: Results synthesis for panel UF3

	Nb ép. / spe.	Moyenne Mean	Ecart type Standart deviation	Max	Min	Ecart max / moy. Deviation max / mean	Ecart min / moy. Deviation min / mean
Humidité / Moisture content (%) selon NF EN 322	4	9,2	0,2				
Masse volumique / Density (kg/m ³) selon NF EN 323	4	676	30	699	633	3,4%	6,4%

	Nb ép. / spe.	Moyenne Mean	Ecart type Standart deviation	Coef. de variation Coef. of variation
Cohésion interne / Internal bond strength (N/mm ²) selon NF EN 319	4	0,32	0,05	16%
Gonflement / Sw elling (%) selon NF EN 317	4	45,1	2,4	5%
Contrainte à la rupture en flexion / Modulus of rupture (N/mm ²) selon NF EN 310	3	3,5	0,3	9%
Module d'élasticité en flexion / Modulus of elasticity (N/mm ²) selon NF EN 310	3	734	27	4%

	Nb ép. / spe.	Valeur d'émission Emission value
Dégagement de formaldéhyde / Formaldehyde release (mg/m ² .h) selon NF EN ISO 12460-3	1	> 30

Table 48: Results synthesis for panel UF4

	Nb ép. / spe.	Moyenne Mean	Ecart type Standart deviation	Max	Min	Ecart max / moy. Deviation max / mean	Ecart min / moy. Deviation min / mean
Humidité / Moisture content (%) selon NF EN 322	4	9,0	0,3				
Masse volumique / Density (kg/m ³) selon NF EN 323	4	606	24	632	577	4,3%	4,8%

	Nb ép. / spe.	Moyenne Mean	Ecart type Standart deviation	Coef. de variation Coef. of variation
Cohésion interne / Internal bond strength (N/mm ²) selon NF EN 319	4	0,22	0,03	14%
Gonflement / Swelling (%) selon NF EN 317	4	43,0	2,6	6%
Contrainte à la rupture en flexion / Modulus of rupture (N/mm ²) selon NF EN 310	3	3,3	0,7	21%
Module d'élasticité en flexion / Modulus of elasticity (N/mm ²) selon NF EN 310	3	701	114	16%

	Nb ép. / spe.	Valeur d'émission Emission value
Dégagement de formaldéhyde / Formaldehyde release (mg/m ² .h) selon NF EN ISO 12460-3	1	> 30

Table 49: Results synthesis for panel UF5

	Nb ép. / spe.	Moyenne Mean	Ecart type Standart deviation	Max	Min	Ecart max / moy. Deviation max / mean	Ecart min / moy. Deviation min / mean
Humidité / Moisture content (%) selon NF EN 322	4	9,2	0,1				
Masse volumique / Density (kg/m ³) selon NF EN 323	4	667	12	677	650	1,5%	2,5%

	Nb ép. / spe.	Moyenne Mean	Ecart type Standart deviation	Coef. de variation Coef. of variation
Cohésion interne / Internal bond strength (N/mm ²) selon NF EN 319	4	0,25	0,04	16%
Gonflement / Swelling (%) selon NF EN 317	4	47,6	3,1	7%
Contrainte à la rupture en flexion / Modulus of rupture (N/mm ²) selon NF EN 310	3	3,1	0,6	19%
Module d'élasticité en flexion / Modulus of elasticity (N/mm ²) selon NF EN 310	3	663	108	16%

	Nb ép. / spe.	Valeur d'émission Emission value
Dégagement de formaldéhyde / Formaldehyde release (mg/m ² .h) selon NF EN ISO 12460-3	1	> 30

Table 50: Results synthesis for panel UF6

Appendix B: Structural study on the UK shelter design

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For the attention of Mr Tawanda Chuma

Dear Sirs,

University of Warwick, Coventry ECO Bulk Enclosure

Introduction

Scott White and Hookins LLP were commissioned by The University of Warwick to carry out a structural review of the proposed Eco bulk structure.

The aim of this report is to provide comment on the adequacy of the fixings and the structure's stability.

Our review is based on the information and Eco bulk drawings provided by the University. See proposed drawings within Appendix A. Details of our 3D analysis can be found in Appendix B.

GRP Structure Review

The proposed frame comprises hollow GRP members forming two separate flat roofs at approximately 2.7m and 3.0m from ground level. Hollow boards spanning between the GRP beams at 100mm centres form the slat roof cladding. The roof structure is supported by GRP posts bearing onto a concrete foundation.

Some elevations of the enclosure are also cladded with the hollow board and span vertically. GRP beams have been provided near the ground to restrain the vertical cladding.

The proposed GRP members typically measure 125x125mm. The proposal is for the members to be connected using steel angles and screws. It appears the cladding will also be fixed to the GRP members using screw fixings.

This report is limited to the structural behaviour of the frame. Review of the GRP elements is beyond the scope of this report.

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Our review and recommendations are as follows.

1. Our structural analysis reviewed the frame for self-weight loading. A point load of 3.0kN has been considered at 1.5m above ground level in all directions to account for potential accidental/misuse loading of the structure. Which by inspection will be greater than the maximum expected wind loading on the structure, so a separate wind analysis has not been undertaken.
2. Timber members have been used to model the GRP sections as a conservative approach. A mean Young's modulus of 17GPa has been used.
3. The proposed fixings appear to be pinned connections, i.e. no moment forces can be transferred through the connections.
4. No horizontal bracing or other forms of lateral load resistance have been provided to withstand notional horizontal loads or accidental loads. Subsequently, the structure is unstable. We recommend that fixed connection bases are introduced to provide the required lateral load resistance and stability to the proposed structure.
5. It is our opinion securing GRP sections with screw fixings will potentially cause the GRP box to split. Typical connection details for GRP sections normally include bonding technologies, lamination connections or factory standard flange connections. Bonded or laminated connections are outside of normal analysis techniques, therefore prototypes should be load tested to verify their suitability.
6. The proposals also appear to show that the GRP cladding slats will be fixed with similar screw fixed angle brackets. Due to the likelihood of the GRP splitting, these fixing details should be altered to use a bonded or lamination bracket to connect the slats.
7. The 3D model analysis indicated that the loads, deflections, and stresses on the frame are not likely to be high and should be acceptable, provided the stability and joint connection issues are resolved.

Summary

In our opinion the proposed framing was found to have inadequate fixing details to provide lateral stability to the structure. To maintain the open aesthetics of the enclosure, fixed base plate shoe type connections are recommended to provide the required base restraint.

It is our opinion the proposed screw fixed connections may cause the GRP members to split/fracture which will cause the failure of the joint connections. We recommend that the screw fixing details are replaced with a bonding or lamination type connection typical to GRP structures. As these are outside normal design techniques it may be necessary to fabricate and test trial joint connections to verify their suitability.

The proposal for the hollow board slat cladding members appears to also be a screw type connection. Similarly, these should be replaced to avoid failure of the structure caused by the GRP members splitting/fracturing. We suggest that bonded or laminated hangers are adopted for supporting the slat cladding e.g. U-shaped GRP sections.

Advice could be sought from a GRP specialist on the appropriate bonded/ laminated connections, but ultimately some proto-type joint connections may need to be made and tested to confirm their suitability to take the proposed loading.

We trust the above provides the information you require, however if you have any queries please do not hesitate to contact me.

Yours sincerely

Simba Mupani BEng (Hons) MSc

Engineer

Scott White and Hookins LLP

Appendix A – Eco bulk Proposed Design

1 Foundation Level
1 : 50

2 Structure

3 Level 2
1 : 25

4 A-A
1 : 25

5 Level 1 Floor plan
1 : 25

7 A-a'
1 : 25

9 Wall 3
1 : 20

6 Level 2 Floor plan
1 : 25

8 B-B'
1 : 25

11 Architecture 3D

12 Architecture 3D-2

Designed By: Daniela Cadena	Date: 16/12/2019
Project: ECOBULK	Observations: Updated design
Use: OUTDOOR SHELTER	Location: WARWICK UNIVERSITY

10 Wall 4-Vertical elements
1 : 10

Appendix B – 3D Analysis

Image 1: View of 3D analysis model based on Eco Bulk drawings

Image 2: Proposed fixity conditions to provide lateral restraint of frame to notional horizontal loads and accidental loads.

Image 3: Design bending moments in major axis of frame elements

Image 4: Envisage deflection values based on fixed base connection detail subject to an accidental load of 3.0kN. Short term deflections deemed acceptable.

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